

STATUS OF WOMEN IN STEM LEADERSHIP POSITIONS:
AN EXPLORATORY CASE STUDY

by

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AN EXPLORATORY CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Globally, women remain underrepresented in science technology, engineering, and mathematics fields. The problem is, compared to male counterparts; fewer women in engineering hold leadership roles in the science technology, engineering, and mathematics industry resulting in workplace inequity. The purpose of this qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to leadership positions in the science technology, engineering, and mathematics fields. The population in this qualitative exploratory case study included all males and females in the transportation departments of the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the United States. A sample of 15 males and 15 females was interviewed for collecting data to answer the research questions. Data collected from the semistructured interviews and curriculum vitae were analyzed and evaluated. Leaders in the science technology, engineering, and mathematics fields risk organizations' long-term sustainability, competitive advantage, increased organizational and team performance, and the potential of meeting strategic planning goals resulting from the lack of a gender-balanced leadership team. Six themes emerged: *(a) barriers and experiences with men in leadership; (b) leadership competencies and experiences; (c) early interests and encouragement; (d) support opportunities and hindrances in women's careers; (e) woman leadership characteristics and development process; and (f) personal and other factors in success.* Findings of the current study indicated lack of mentorship, gender prejudices, inefficient organizational support and opportunities, women's low self-efficacy, and implied leadership prototypes were obstacles to women's career advancement to leadership.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this Dissertation to my village without whose support, this would not have been possible. The strength, prayers, motivation, and encouragement have inspired me to complete the doctoral journey. I also dedicate this dissertation to my children, Stephen and Tamia. You have both driven my ambition to succeed against all odds. I hope I made you proud. To my mother who always believed in me, I love you. I dedicate this dissertation to the next generation of doctoral candidates in my family; the standard is set...now raise the bar.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) is a growing field that is highly valued with the evolving technological era, yet gender differences in pay gains and leadership roles continue to exist. Women are significantly underrepresented in STEM (Sassler et al., 2017). Qualified females do not earn the same pay, nor do they hold similar leadership positions as their male counterparts, and fewer women are pursuing and obtaining higher education in the STEM field. According to the U.S. Department of Labor (2019), in 1970, women represented 7% of the STEM workforce, in 1990 women occupied 23% of all STEM jobs, and in 2019 the number increased to 27%. The technological era seems to be rapidly advancing and the demand for the basic knowledge of computer science and technology has grown. Jones et al. (2018) believed it is critical that the workforce proactively prepare for the future to meet the projected labor demands in science and technology. Female's awareness of the STEM industry and its demand now and in the future is necessary.

Background of the Problem

According to Jones et al. (2018), "to meet the growing global demand for a STEM workforce, every segment of the United States of America (U.S.) population will need to be engaged in a successful STEM education" (p. 41). Jones et al.'s (2018) study conducted between 2012 and 2016 at the University of Virginia (UVA) School of Engineering and Applied Sciences revealed an achievement gap in higher education. Ethnicity/race and GPA greater than 3.0 were applied when determining the diversification of the high achievers graduating in the STEM academia (Jones et al.).

Observations revealed that although the number of African American graduates increased between 2012 and 2016, they still lagged far behind other ethnic groups. For example, the study results showed a 47-point differential in the percentage of African American students graduating with at least a 3.0 GPA in UVA Engineering, which meant 35% of African Americans graduated with a 3.0 and above GPA versus a total mean of 82% graduates (Jones et al., p. 42). The gap begins in early education (Carlana, 2019). STEM scholars are the future STEM leaders and, as such, it is imperative for educators to focus on the demographics of the potential leaders to create a balanced STEM workforce.

A balanced workforce may also mean women may be required to join male counterparts in leadership roles in STEM fields. However, females are underrepresented in leadership in STEM-related jobs. Looking at top level positions in 2016, only 26% of professional computing jobs in the U.S. workforce were held by women; women held 20% of the Fortune 100 chief information officer (CIO) positions, and 23% of Advanced Placement (AP) computer science test takers were female (Shein, 2018, p. 19). Korn Ferry's (2019) analysis of the top 1,000 firms in the U.S. by revenue, revealed that women trailed their male counterparts with only 18% of women advancing to CIO roles on average across all industries. The failure of women to hold more leadership positions is a contributing factor to the gender imbalance in the STEM workforce. Women scientists conduct the experiments while men scientists receive the credit for the data analysis (Voosen, 2016); and there are fewer opportunities for accessing leadership opportunities for women (Xu, 2015). The presence of leadership inequalities may lead to fewer female students pursuing a career in those related fields. Industry leaders can take actions and make changes to address the issue. The professional disadvantages of women

in the STEM workforce are evident in the number of managerial and leadership roles women possess.

Problem Statement

The STEM workforce is increasingly integral to the sustainability of America's innovative capacity and global competitiveness. Innovation is at the forefront of global development; therefore, establishing a diverse workforce may be used to drive creative tools and innovative solutions. Women hold 27% of lab leadership roles at the 46 federally funded research and development centers in the U.S. (Association for Women in Science, 2019, para 10). A report by the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2016) showed 27.2% of STEM managerial positions in computer and information systems were held by women, compared to 72.8% held by men. Information technology has 55% fewer females than males in management positions (McCabe et al. (2020, p. 396). Female underrepresentation in the STEM industry is a problem, yet the industry continues to rapidly evolve.

The problem is compared to their male counterparts, fewer women in engineering hold leadership roles in the STEM industry resulting in workplace inequity (Lewis, 2018). STEM industry leaders risk organizations' long-term sustainability, competitive advantage, increased organizational and team performance, and potential of meeting strategic planning goals resulting from the lack of a gender-balanced leadership team. Women's presence in leadership may improve an organization's performance and increase a firm's skill diversity (Noland et al., 2016). Leadership talent and creativity are important for competitive advantage and lasting organizational success. Innovation and

creativity are claimed to be the answers for a world that is constantly changing (Bligh et al., 2018).

The importance of the STEM industry to the economy has become prevalent among educators and policymakers. In 2014, President Barack Obama in his address at the White House Science Fair, spoke of the shortage of women in the STEM field and said the numbers should be changed (Lee, 2014). Under President Obama's administration, states were granted competitive preference if they exhibited efforts to close the gender gaps in the STEM workforce (Lee, 2014). In 2020, The Rural STEM Education bill was passed to support and strengthen STEM education in rural schools (Peterson, 2020).

Despite the resources and strategies provided by policymakers to create inclusion and advancement of females in the STEM industry, the leadership gap has not closed. For example, reports from the Association for Women in Science (2019) stated from 2013–2018, biotechnology companies demonstrated constant underrepresentation of women among CEOs and board of directors. Women were absent from leadership roles in nearly 15% of the 336 biotechnology companies. A balanced workforce is all around beneficial and necessary to create a strong flexible STEM industry (Rykers, 2016). Obtaining an understanding of the imbalance in leadership positions among the genders and identifying the earning inequality between men and women in STEM leadership positions contribute to the exploratory process and its findings. Therefore, the problem addressed in this study was the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions in the engineering field.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement in STEM leadership positions. Three sources of data were used to support this case study and ensure the purpose of the study is achieved. Thirty participants who are or were previously employed in the engineering industry, and who hold or held leadership positions in the Northeast region of the U.S. were recruited to participate in semistructured interviews. A stratified sample of two subgroups of fifteen males and fifteen females were used as two sources of interview data. Archival records in the form of a curriculum vitae (CV) from each participant were used to supplement interviews. CV documents served to provide insight into how participants presented themselves professionally and showed examples of knowledge and accomplishments.

Population and Sample

The population in this qualitative exploratory case study included males and females in the transportation departments of the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. In researchers' exploration for information that adds to the body of knowledge in respective fields, data is gathered from a group of individuals who shared one or multiple characteristics of interest to the study (Asiamah et al., 2017). The group of individuals are referred to as the research population. The population includes all the elements from a data set (Mikkelsen, 2020). The population guides the credibility of the sample, the selected sampling technique, and ultimately the outcome of the research (Asiamah et al., 2017).

Given that the focus of the research topic was on an event that is common in the industry, the researcher applied a systematic and organized approach in selecting study participants. First, the selection of participants from the engineering population was purposeful. Purposeful sampling was used to deliberately select the study participants. Participants were selected from organizations that employ women in STEM professions. Second, snowball sampling was used to augment participant recruitment efforts by seeking information from key personnel about other potential sources who possessed knowledge needed for the study. The sample size in qualitative research is at the discretion of the researcher and may depend on the topic of study or, more importantly, data saturation, which determines the final sample size (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014).

The sample for the study included 30 current and former employees in the engineering industry who hold or have held leadership positions. Recruitment flyers were sent to organizations that granted the researcher permission to recruit. A request was made to have the flyers posted electronically and physically in common areas for employees' access. The flyers included the researcher's contact information, and potential participants were asked to contact the researcher directly to express interest to participate in the study. The participants were comprised of males and females from transportation departments including engineering, design, highway, and administration. Participants' accessibility was required should the researcher needed to conduct multiple rounds of interviews with the same participant on different occasions. Therefore, the participants who (a) were readily available to participate in the study, (b) met the criteria for the study, and (c) were believed to have rich knowledge to contribute to the study were selected from the industry. Prior to recruitment, engineering industry leadership was

identified from known organizations that hire males and females in the Northeast region of the U.S. Phone calls followed by email requests were sent to either human resource representatives or the regional leadership of each entity. Premises, recruitment, and name (PRN) use permission form was emailed to each official requesting permission. The recruitment process of employing purposeful selection ensured the participants were qualified to contribute enough appropriate data (Campbell et al., 2020). Snowball sampling was used to supplement purposeful sampling, and to request referrals from selected participants or from individuals who were contacts of potential participants (Moser & Korstjens, 2018). The organizations were not a focus of the study. Data collection could have altered the direction of the study and generated new questions. Therefore, the researcher was receptive to transitioning sampling selection accordingly. Sampling continued until data saturation was reached (Rooddehghan et al., 2019).

Significance of the Study

The study served to inform practice by exploring the status of women in STEM leadership and to reveal the successes and challenges of the women in these positions. Organizational leaders create the path for social adaptation and learning that ultimately shapes organizational cultures (Campuzano, 2019). Leaders are responsible to promote effective and responsive organizational change. Northouse (2018) defined leadership as “a process that influences a group of individuals who share a common goal” (p. 1). Therefore, leadership is a shared process. STEM leaders and stakeholders share responsibilities of addressing the existing problems in the industry.

Women hold various positions and perform several roles in the STEM industry. The leadership roles women hold is noncomparable to their male counterparts, and all

known theories contributing to that issue is also unknown (Holman et al., 2018). Multiple theories converging may better assist with the understanding of the leadership gap between males and females. All the reasons why women enter, shun, and abscond this male-dominated environment is unknown. Lessons, experiences, and factors were to be learned from conducting this study. The findings from this study lend to contribute to the body of knowledge, organizational awareness, and organizational programs by providing an understanding of the perceived barriers to females attaining leadership positions in the engineering industry.

The results from the study contribute to an understanding of the perceptions shared from males and females in the STEM industry. Organizations may benefit from examining the problem and deriving at concepts that may be used to further address the reasons that prevent women from elevating to leadership positions in the STEM industry. Findings from the study contribute new knowledge that can explain the reasons for the disparity in female leadership. Industry and academic leaders may use new theory to develop an understanding of associated behaviors required to address and potentially eliminate the barriers that limit advancement of women's careers. Plenteous opportunities exist for change as it relates to women in the STEM industry (Diekman et al., 2019).

Organizational structure extrinsically influences individuals' behaviors. Organizational structures are planned actions and interactions that organizational members undertake to accomplish the organization's goals (Janicijevic, 2013). Findings from an investigation of gender relations in the engineering industry in an empirical setting revealed women held only 13% of the 118 managerial positions (Olofsdotter & Rasmusson, 2016). Diversifying leadership in the workplace creates an environment

where new associations are formed and could potentially increase efficiency and equality in workplaces (Rykers, 2016). A diverse leadership team outperforms homogeneous teams in innovation, decision making, complex thinking, and can potentially strengthen an organization's financial success (Association for Women in Science, 2017).

Organizations and leadership need different frames around a problem to see different solutions (Koomans & Hilders, 2016). The result from this study may help practitioners understand the types of obstacles female employees experience and could potentially increase leadership diversity in the field.

The gender inequality in the STEM field is a top global economic risk that is slowing world economic growth (Kossek & Buzzanell, 2018). Therefore, it is crucial to explore and understand the issues that exist in the industry. Learning more about the female presence in the industry and the contributing roles females have made may produce some answers to the reasons for the gender gap that exist in STEM leadership positions. The presence of more women in equally leading positions as their male counterparts may benefit employers in attracting junior female STEM students to join the industry. The presence of additional women leaders may enhance the confidence of women STEM practitioners and STEM scholars. Academic leaders may use information learned from the study's findings to promote female awareness and acceptance in STEM education. An increase in female interests in STEM academia may promote higher female college enrollments resulting in additional females joining the workplace. Findings will help other females in STEM academia and professions understand how to improve representations and drive positive change in the respective disciplines.

Nature of the Study

Research methods may be qualitative, quantitative, or mixed. Quantitative and qualitative research methods complement each other as each provides new knowledge for solving research problems (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). Quantitative research has a positivist paradigm and as such the world is viewed objectively (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020). Quantitative methodology uses deductive reasoning as its inquiry mode and data collection is represented numerically. Qualitative research methods allow for the application of various techniques to collect specific data. Qualitative research is a method used as a data collection technique to obtain statements made by individuals, conduct case study, retrieve historical information from past cultures, and acquire narratives from individuals (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). Mixed method research design combines elements of the quantitative and qualitative approaches in the same study (Farrelly, 2012). The mixed method approach requires extensive time, added resources, and enhanced skills and efforts from the researcher (Farrelly, 2012).

A qualitative approach was chosen for this study because of the social nature of the research problem. An exploratory study was selected to learn more about the status of women in STEM leadership and to ultimately collect more in-depth data to address the research purpose and the research questions. The qualitative method was selected to obtain in-depth data to understand the phenomenon from the participants' perceptions (Hancock & Algozzine, 2017). A qualitative methodology was appropriate for this study since most of the information was gathered from participants' perceptions.

The study's research questions were used as a guide to select the case study design. Exploratory case study was selected to collect more in-depth information about

what is occurring (Yin, 2018). A case study is an appropriate research design to answer research questions that ask how, what, or why, or when the behavior of those in the study cannot be manipulated. A case study design involving a stratified sample from two subsets of participants was selected for this case study (Yin, 2018). A person, program, institution, or phenomenon can be the selected unit of analysis in a case study (Merriam, 1998). In this study, the unit of analysis is males and females who were current or past employees in the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. who hold or held leadership positions. Identified boundaries are necessary for researchers (Ridder, 2017); the research boundary included in this study is specific to the Northeast region of the U.S.

Other qualitative research designs such as grounded theory and ethnography were explored for this study. Grounded theory design requires researchers to simultaneously conduct data collection and data analysis (Charmaz, 2006). The grounded theory was used to develop theory and provides a pathway to learning about the events researchers study, as well as a method of developing theories to understand them (Charmaz, 2006). More importantly, the theory must be grounded in data. Grounded theory is usually selected to study peoples' actions and reactions (Rooddehghan et al., 2019). However, the purpose of conducting the study was not to develop theory.

Ethnography research method is used when exploring the way of life in a group of people, specifically the group's culture (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). Researchers choose the ethnographic methods when the goal is to get in-depth knowledge of the subjects using mainly observation as the primary data collection instrument (Creswell, 2013). The ethnography method is inappropriate as all participants in the study were not of the same

cultural background and were not located in the same place (Creswell, 2013).

Ethnography was not selected because the purpose of this study was not to explore the cultural norms and views or behaviors of the study population.

Multiple instruments or devices are used to collect relevant data in qualitative research. The researcher is the primary instrument for data gathering and for analyzing the data through memoing, transcribing, and triangulation (Creswell, 2013). Multiple sources of data collection allow the researcher opportunities for data triangulation to help make the findings trustworthy. For triangulation, it is important to use different sources of data such as interviews with multiple participants, or multiple archival sources (Fusch et al., 2018). For this study, semistructured interview questions were directed to 30 participants who were employed or had been employed in the engineering industry, and who hold or held leadership positions in the Northeast region of the U.S. Data collection included archival records in the form of CVs from each participant. Archival records as documentation were used for triangulation with the interviews. The selected data sources were used for conducting the research differently with alternate options.

Semistructured interviews were conducted to obtain nonnumerical data. Interviewing consisted of asking participants open-ended questions that allowed for free form responses (Zarubin et al., 2017). Online synchronous interviews, using online video options such as Skype for Business and Microsoft Teams were the main medium for conducting the interviews. CVs were collected from each semistructured interview participant through email communication. Prior to being interviewed, each participant was advised that the CVs were requested. Given that there were 30 participants, receiving at least 20 CVs was sufficient to provide rich information about the leaders' professional

experiences, qualifications, and demographics. Using the CVs as archival documentation was an integral document used for triangulation, provided a succinct professional history of each interview participant, and added knowledge of some of the main facilitators of career progress.

Having various strategies to analyze data in qualitative research design was helpful since data is largely dependent on human's perceptions of what is real. Data analysis involves preparing and organizing collected data, then shrinking the collected data into themes with the use of codes and displaying the data in figures, tables, or discussions (Creswell, 2013). Transcripts from notes were read line by line and coded into NVivo to aid in data analysis of the interview responses. Words and written accounts were also analyzed.

Research Questions

The following research questions, the final component of the research triad, were constructed to obtain answers as to what data needs addressed, queried, or answered:

RQ1: What do female engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

RQ2: What do male engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

The problem is compared to male counterparts, fewer women in engineering hold leadership roles in the STEM industry resulting in workplace inequity (Lewis, 2018). The answers to the research questions are contributory to industry leadership's understanding of the inequality issue that exists in the industry. Learning more about the obstacles to females' trajectory to leadership in engineering may produce some answers to the reasons

for the gender gap that exist in the STEM workforce. Industry leadership will be better equipped to address workplace inequality with the knowledge gained from the results of the research questions. Gender equality benefits organizations with increased team and organizational performance, innovation, and corporate governance (Fine et al., 2020).

Conceptual Framework

This qualitative exploratory case study employs a conceptual framework consisting of Lord et al.'s (1984) implicit leadership theory and Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory. Concepts were used to support the foundation of the study in exploring the perceptions and experiences of STEM professionals who work in the engineering field. Self-efficacy expectations refer to a person's belief to successfully perform a given task (Betz & Hackett, 1997). Self-efficacy refers to the level of confidence individuals have in themselves to be successful in attaining a goal. Tasks can have high value to individuals and ultimately the STEM industry if an individual's perceptions of this is of high importance and if it is aligned with personal goals. The concept of self-efficacy can enhance leadership readiness, thus increasing the future leadership capacity (Shirey, 2020).

The focus of the implicit leadership theory (ILT) is on the cognitive structure people use to make generalized assumptions about others. Those who hold, practice, and apply implicit leadership paradigm may be more apt to create perceptions concerning what constitutes a leader (Swanson et al., 2020). The mental model people create conceptualizes leadership and construct its identity. Leadership is predominantly a psychological matter (Machida & Feltz, 2013). ILT relies on any version of assumptions and perceptions regarding the qualities and behaviors that differentiates a leader and a

non-leader. Individuals do not always behave according to the reality of the environments, but will respond to what they perceive (Yukl, 2013). Perception is powerful to influence behaviors.

Self-efficacy and ILT concepts informed the study of fundamentals linked to the gender imbalance in the STEM field as it relates to females' attraction and retention in the STEM workforce, as well as females' inclusion in leader roles. Self-efficacy framework was applicable to this study as females believed certain behaviors and performance will result in certain outcomes. In the 1980s, Bandura's self-efficacy theory started being applied to career development to examine the obstacles women experienced in mathematics and science careers (Betz & Hackett, 2006). The focus of the self-efficacy concept was also on expectancies for success (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002), and the concept elaborates on personal expectancy to include outcome expectancy and efficacy expectancy. Employing the ILT to understand the perceptions of leadership formed through the leader-follower interrelatedness was important and practical to this case study. Followers are as important as leaders in the leadership process (Northouse, 2018). Followership may positively contribute to leadership development and simultaneously enhance followership personal growth. Therefore, in this qualitative exploratory case study the participants' ILTs were compared to reveal any similarities or differences in the perceptions. The prototype models of leaders are representative of the ILTs individuals form (Foti et al., 2017; Tavares et al., 2018).

Definition of Terms

Significant terms used in this study were unknown and have multiple or generalized meanings that may be confusing to the readers. A set of definitions were used to provide clarity, for consistency of interpreting and understanding, and to minimize confusion in this qualitative exploratory case study. The following list provides key terms and definitions:

Disparity. Disparity refers to significant difference or underrepresentation (Landivar, 2013).

Paradigm. Paradigm is a set of assumptions about how knowledge is created in varying ways of viewing the world (Davies & Fischer, 2018).

Assumptions, Limitations, and Delimitations

Multiple assumptions were used as the basis for this qualitative exploratory case study. Assumptions are necessary unavoidable elements that are used to clarify what cannot be proved but must be assumed to conduct a study (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). The first assumption of this study was the participants would be forthcoming and honest in their responses to the interview questions. The second assumption was the efforts placed on establishing trust with the participants would increase honesty. Third, was the assumption the inclusion criteria of the sample were appropriate, therefore assuring participants were current or former leaders in the engineering industry. The fourth assumption was participants would be recruited from different STEM disciplines. The fifth assumption was the assurance of anonymity would allow female and male individuals who choose to participate to share key insights as to the gender imbalance in

STEM leadership positions. The final assumption was throughout the study, bias would be monitored and minimized.

Many limitations of this qualitative exploratory case study existed. Limitations were beyond the researcher's control and were identified weaknesses in the study's research design or methodology that could potentially affected the study's outcome (Calabrese, 2006; Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). One limitation was of the interviewer, who depended on the openness and honesty of the participants in their responses to the interview questions. The interviewer (who was also the researcher) was responsible for recording and transcribing the information received as it was provided and without added input to change the direction of the findings. Research bias was another limitation because the researcher was the primary instrument for conducting the research, analyzing the data, and presenting the findings (Hamilton, 2020).

Delimitations were used to ensure the exploratory case study was more feasible and did not become impossible to complete in the assigned timeframe. The delimitations were specific choices made by the researcher (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). Data sources were confined to virtual interviews, given the participants were widely dispersed in various office locations. A presumption was made that all participants were available to meet for a defined amount of time and be available to participate in either a telephone or virtual interview session. The scope of the study was limited to specific individuals who met the demographic criteria. Sample size was a delimiter, and the intent was to restrict the study to 30 STEM professionals (including males and females) in the transportation department. The decision to use the participant selection criteria was based on the limited time to conduct the research and complete the dissertation.

Chapter Summary

This qualitative exploratory case study was used to obtain information from STEM professionals in the transportation departments of the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. The purpose of this study was to explore reasons why women are underrepresented in STEM leadership positions. STEM has been claimed to be a male dominant industry with fewer percentages of women in leadership roles compared to males (Korn Ferry, 2019; Shein, 2018). A balanced workforce with additional women leaders may enhance the confidence of women STEM workers and STEM scholars. More young females may become attracted to a career in the STEM field when they envision themselves as future organizational and world leaders. Thus, an increase in female interests in STEM academia may promote higher female college enrollments resulting in additional females joining the workplace. Achieving gender equality in STEM may significantly advance the labor force, research, innovation, enhance the economy, and reduce the risks of women's social exclusion to the benefit of society (Fatourou et al., 2019). A balanced workforce is all around beneficial and necessary to create a strong flexible STEM industry (Rykers, 2016).

In this study, male and female professionals were enlisted and interviewed to understand from both genders, the experiences, and perceptions of the barriers to women attaining leadership positions. Chapter 1 presented a brief explanation and rationale for selecting the research method, design, and methodology of the study. Lord et al.'s (1984) implicit leadership theory and Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory were summarized and used to frame the current research. The research purpose, research questions, and the problem statement were aligned to aid in the rigorous understanding of the study's

phenomenon. Chapter 2 will provide more insight and an understanding of the barriers faced by women in attaining more leadership positions by using an extended literature review. A review of the literature related to the research questions and the research problem was conducted to review existing and previous research literature. Chapter 2 literature review will present an outline of key topics that support the study.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement in STEM leadership positions. Leadership continues its transformation (Clarke & Harrison, 2017) and organizations develop (Mewton et al., 2005). Understanding how those in the engineering industry perceive and experience obstacles to female career advancement in STEM leadership positions could contribute to current and future organizational development. Lord et al.'s (1984) implicit leadership theory (ILT) and Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory () served as two foundational theories utilized to guide the review of the literature. Literature review relevant to the study was utilized to compile information from different sources; to present comprehensive investigation of scholarly and peer-reviewed content, current and historical reports, and census data. The review of literature was necessary for identifying new knowledge gaps, and helped the researcher identify how this study could contribute to additional understandings of the research topic (Efron & Ravid, 2018).

Title Searches and Documentation

Chapter 2 presents an extensive examination of peer-reviewed literature from various journals on EBSCOhost, ProQuest, ABI/Inform, SAGE Journals, Journal of Leadership Studies, and Google Scholar, and archival documents such as historical reports, census data, and survey data. Library and database reviewed for the current qualitative exploratory case study included 197 peer-reviewed articles and journals, 54 electronic sources, and 32 books. Relevant keywords, databases, and concepts were

selected to achieve research alignment. Keywords and search terms included *women in the labor force, women in leadership, women in STEM, women in engineering, barriers and obstacles, organizational culture, biases, leadership, leadership theories, future of leadership, self-efficacy theory, and implicit leadership theory*. Historical content over five years old and current content less than five years old were included in the search parameters.

Historical Content

In this section historical content linked to the study was examined. A literature review for content over 5 years old was used to help outline how past events related to the research topic and supported this study. Conducting historical research can provide important information about the past that adds knowledge to present and future events (Law et al., 1998). The historical content is divided into multiple sections and subsections and will cover the following topics: history of working women in the U.S., leadership, and barriers and obstacles to women's advancement to leadership.

History of Working Women in the United States

Although delayed, women's participation in the workforce in the U.S. has significant relationship with the economic development of the country (Webb, 2010). In the 1820s, new opportunities from the industrial revolution created jobs for females; they could work outside the home in factories and for the first time receive paychecks. Working outside the home became customary for unmarried women. Combining work and balancing families was difficult and many women opted to remain single. In 1900, less than 5.6% of married women were employed (Webb, 2010, p. 1).

In the early 1900s, the attitudes towards gender and social roles changed. Women's participation in the labor force was still limited to single women without children, while the middle class emerged with childbearing and ending paid employment for most women (Rindfuss et al., 1996). The 1920 creation of the U.S. Department of Labor's Women Bureau paved the way to assist women seeking work outside the home (Boris & Honey, 1988). According to Rindfuss et al. (1996), most women were homemakers and worked at home caring for children prior to World War II. Doepke et al. (2015) found the immediate effect of World War II was an increased labor market with opportunities for young women, with spurring economic and social change. The mid-1900s showed a strong presence of female participation in the workforce, as family cycles dominated the female employment behaviors. The pattern changed in the 1960s with young women joining the workforce by choice rather than necessity (Weinstein, 2017). After the 1960s, women joined the workforce in vast numbers. The labor force participation rate among women increased dramatically (Doepke et al., 2015).

Between 1970 and 2012, there was a 10% increase in the employment rate of women (Seo et al., 2017). The trending women labor increase began to change early in the Millennium. In 2000, women aged 16 years and older occupied 57.5% of the U.S. labor force, and at the end of 2015 that figure fell to 53.7% (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2016). While women have made significant progress in the labor force, there seems to be undefined reasons why women were opting out of work and why they continued to drop out of the labor force.

Lee (2014) believed the labor shortage was not a suitable explanation for the change after great progress in women's labor force participation. Lee conducted a series

of shift-share analyses to document in group trends and composition effects based on disaggregation by educational attainment, marital status, and child-care responsibilities, and used population survey data from 1968 to 2010 to gain an understanding and detailed information of facts about the stagnation of the U.S. women's labor force participation. The results of Lee's analysis showed birth cohorts from the early 1950s contributed to the steady level of female labor force participation. Lee's shift-share analyses was comprehensive, covered long time periods, and provided quantitative connection between female labor force participation and related socioeconomic outcomes of women. However, results did not provide a wholistic review of women in the labor force. The sample was limited to noninstitutionalized civilian women aged 16 to 64, which excluded women in the military. In 1967, the repeal of The Women's Armed Services Integration of 1948 was historic and provided a significant surge of opportunities for women to serve in the military. For example, 265,000 women served in the Vietnam War between August 1964 to May 1975 (Aponte et al., 2017, p. 2; Newkumet, 1993, p. 2). Recognizing the total omission of noncivilians calls for questions if the early 1950s birth cohorts is mostly contributory to the lack of progress for women in the labor force.

Women in STEM

Women have been in the work force since the 1800s, joining in droves since the industrial revolution (Webb, 2010). The gender allocation of women in the STEM workforce compared to the number of women in the labor force is disproportionate. In 2009, STEM labor force consisted of 24% females compared to 76% males (Beede et al., 2011a, p. 2). According to Agassi (2008), females began to teach and learn science as early as 2,700 B.C., yet males always dominated the science field in numbers,

prominence, and position. The population of females participating in the labor force maintained steadily at an average of 50% (Dasgupta & Stout, (2014, p. 21), yet only 25% of women leaders are in the healthcare sector (Chisholm-Burns et al., 2017, p. 313). Given the number of women in the labor force compared to the number of women in the STEM workforce, women are vastly underrepresented in STEM with men's predominance in STEM careers (Landivar, 2013).

The employment numbers in the STEM fields have increased over the decades with more STEM jobs created than nonSTEM-related jobs. According to Beede et al. (2011a), key findings from a U.S. Department of Commerce Report showed between 2000 and 2010, the growth of STEM jobs were three times greater than nonSTEM jobs. Further findings showed in 2010, the STEM labor force was made up of 7.6 million people or 5.5% of the labor force (Beede et al., 2011a, p.1). Yet, the underrepresentation of women in the STEM workforce remains concerning (Hernandez et al., 2013; Smeding, 2012). More than half of the women in science, engineering, and technology (SET) fields are expected to leave the workforce over time, and about one third intend to quit within one year (Sherbin, 2015).

Women in the STEM workforce encounter disparity in salary, stereotyping, lack adequate mentors, and are not considered for promotions (Davis, 2017). Despite persistent gender stereotypes, women continue to be educated in the various STEM fields (Sassler et al., 2017). While the graduating numbers are promising, women encounter barriers to transition into STEM careers. According to Sassler et al. (2017), female STEM graduates were unlikely to pursue STEM careers. As women struggle to identify as STEM leaders, they experience low self-efficacy and potentially form implicit leadership

prototypes. Gnilka and Novakovic (2017) believed women's career self-efficacy and career perceptions are responsible for women's continuity in STEM careers. Self-efficacy and leadership perception is integral to women's presence in STEM and potentially to women's career progression to leadership positions.

Women Leadership in STEM

Women have played an integral role in the U.S. workforce through history and continue to have a strong presence. Gender should not be an issue in leadership, but it is; women are underrepresented in leadership (Nash et al., 2017). Women are motivated and aspire to be in leadership positions in organizations, yet qualified women are prevented opportunities for attaining highest positions (Haile et al., 2016). Women are underrepresented in managerial jobs in STEM-related fields. Sherbin (2015, para 4), reported 31% of SET senior leaders in the U.S. believed a woman would never get a top position in the company, regardless of their capabilities or performance, suggesting women must overcome gender barriers to attain and retain leadership positions. Mental models of prototypical and ideal leaders emanate from individuals' misconceptions of leadership.

The need for more women in leadership makes business sense and goes beyond gender equality. Beede et al. (2011b) believed having gender diversity in leadership can improve organizations' profitability and competitiveness. Better performing companies have more women in leadership positions, and companies that foster diversity and inclusion in leadership teams benefit with profitability, innovation, and respect (Development Dimensions International, 2015). Teague (2015) asserted that diverse team members prompt improved problem solving with multiplicity of talent and perspectives

that inject high performance, innovation, employee satisfaction, and improved profitability in the workplace. Diverse teams are formed to address challenges one department or function cannot undertake (Gratton et al., 2011). Despite the benefits of sharing leadership positions, the number of women in leadership remains marginal (Goryunova et al. 2017). Embracing the value women bring to individual roles, teams, organizations, and the STEM industry, suggests women's proportional share in leadership is a necessary step to closing the gender gap in the STEM workforce.

Women Leadership in Engineering

Women and men perform different tasks in the engineering industry, but men continue to dominate the engineering field (Buse et al., 2013) because women are underrepresented in engineering professions. Navarro-Astor et al. (2017) purported there is divide between the operative, professional, and leadership levels, which leads to occupational segregation. Dugan et al. (2013) examined the extent to which STEM college females showed different levels of leadership abilities and leadership efficacy, compared to nonSTEM female peers. Dugan et al.'s (2013) quantitative study used data collected from 86 colleges and universities in the U.S., with a sample size of 14,698 females. The study results revealed women in STEM and nonSTEM majors had the same levels of leadership capacity, but the women in STEM showed lower levels of self-efficacy (Dugan et al.). The engineering field is dominated by males more so than the other STEM occupational groups (Beede et al., 2011a).

Treatment of women in the STEM workforce, specifically in the engineering field, contributes to women's challenges to attain high levels of self-confidence (Cech et al., 2011). Self-efficacy is an individual's belief to capably and successfully perform a

given task (Klassen & Chui, 2010). Thus, self-efficacy is influential to individuals' confidence and capabilities. Chu and Abdulla (2014) concluded professional role confidence is significantly associated with self-appraisal. Developing the self-efficacy of women in STEM may positively influence career choices, since self-efficacy is significant in predicting leadership capacity (Dugan et al., 2013). Further exploration of the external influences to female's self-efficacy is needed to understand the purposeful connection of self-efficacy and elevating women to leadership in engineering.

Leadership

Leadership is a difficult developmental process that demands practice and direct involvement (Tabassi & Bakar, 2010). Leaders are visionaries who provide a sense of direction in organizations, focus, and possess self-control (Bargau, 2015). Leadership philosophies are based on internal traits, personalities, or culture. Leaders' roles are not specific to one single behavior; therefore, it is necessary for leaders to conduct regular self-evaluations to ensure success in groups and among followers (Pidgeon, 2017). Thus, leadership skills used in one situation or environment may not be successful in another situation or environment (Silverthorne, 2000). Leaders are required to possess multiple skills to effectively adapt to changes.

Leadership Theories

Leadership is developmental with varying perspectives. Slavik et al. (2015) claimed there are many theories and approaches to leadership that aim to identify and characterize leaders. Individuals' power and authority have guided historical theories of leadership, specifically the great man theory and the trait theory of leadership (Dambe & Moorad, 2008). However, the narrow-mindedness of individuals' perceptions overlooked

the social contexts that drive leadership development (White, 2011). Bierema (2016) claimed while there are minimal differences between male and female leadership styles, women continue to encounter barriers to attaining senior leadership positions. Leaders can inspire individuals or impede progress to an individual's career trajectory. Dambe and Moorad (2008) believed empowerment-based leadership includes power sharing and follower's development. Martin (2015) concluded an individual's style of leadership is crucial to an organization's existence.

Historical Leadership Theories

The historical theories of leadership underwent continuous evolution as researchers continued to answer criticisms to broaden and add new knowledge to the topic. Van Wart (2013) posited that each theory includes valid domains and perspectives; all have been researched and all continue to evolve. Historical theories of leadership claimed birth, traits, skills, and behaviors defined who could and could not be leaders (Germain, 2012).

Great Man Theory. The great man theory popularized beliefs that leaders were born (Shafique & Beh, 2017), and implied individuals who did not possess this innate ability could not be leaders, clearly differentiating leaders from followers. More significantly, the great man theory referred to male attributes, like heroic military leadership (Malos, 2012). The belief of leaders' innate abilities was considered myth (Bennis & Nanus, 1985). Although Bennis and Nanus (1985) did not completely refute that some individuals were born with natural gifts, the innate abilities alone were insufficient to make someone an effective leader—leadership was dependent on learned skills. The arguments raise concerns of the likelihood for anyone to acquire the required

skills and develop competencies towards leadership attainment, since individuals only need the desire to learn to become leaders (Bennis & Nanus). However, it is difficult for followers to emerge as leaders if not given a supportive environment for skills development (Dambe & Moorad, 2008).

Cawthon (1996) questioned the arguments presented by Bennis and Nanus (1985) and believed leaders have special abilities when they are born and not everyone is born with equal capabilities. To develop the competencies to become leaders, individuals are born with talent because that talent is what will be developed for successful leadership. Accordingly, Cawthon concluded there are innate differences of leaders from followers. Suggesting leadership skills can be developed, further questioning as to who determines if individuals are born with the required talent and how are the talents measured. The contradictory arguments presented by Bennis and Nanus and Cawthon raised questions as to the validity of the great man theory as the ideal theory for organizational leadership. Organizations' demands for the *great man* to lead towards organizational success and goal attainment rarely choose women (Spector, 2016).

Trait Theory of Leadership. The skills of leadership are developmental through the leaders' lives rather than obtained at birth. Leadership is defined as a process of learned behaviors and skills that are learned over time (Video Age Productions, 2014). Germain (2012) said the trait theory of leadership approach is a measure of credibility and is backed by a century of research. The beliefs and background of leaders' childhood years cultivates personal leadership philosophy as an adult (Repacholi et al., 2016). Leadership traits are learned from family values and interactions from society and even from followers.

Lemkau (1979) pointed out women in male-dominated positions were skilled communicators, emotionally healthy, and possessed good coping skills. An article in PR Newswire (1990) stated females are more likely than male counterparts to display leadership traits. The perception that women lack leadership abilities is inadmissible, yet women question personal abilities to lead (Machida & Feltz, 2013). An individual's psychological model of leadership is an important contributor to self-efficacy (Bandura, 1997).

Contemporary Leadership Theories

The historical approaches to leadership brought awareness to the complexity of leadership and may have set the foundation for future research leading to the contemporary theories of leadership. Van Wart (2013) explained that a variety of reasons, including new education in the workforce, a new technological era, and a need for less people management drastically affected recent decades of leadership perceptions and approaches. Contemporary leadership theories were established resulting from the shift in organizational and environmental changes and demands.

Situational Leadership. Situations have a significant influence on the approach to leadership. Hersey et al. (1979) recommended the situational leadership model to focus on followers' psychological readiness. Conversely, Blanchard et al. (1993) revisited the model and found some leaders' perceptions clouded judgements of followers' developmental levels. Blanchard et al.'s situational leadership II model replaced

competence dimension of the model with ability. However, with the appropriate leadership styles, followers can develop the right skills and knowledge (Blanchard et al.).

Situational approach does not clearly explain how followers are required to conform to the possible changes in leadership approach in the varying situations. More importantly, situational leadership places emphasis only on leaders, and followers' development to leadership is unconsidered (Dambe & Moorad, 2008). Aspiring leaders have no paths to career advancements to leadership positions. The perceptions of leadership dominate leader selections, limiting the involvement of power-sharing with followers (Dambe & Moorad, 2008). Leadership encounters constant challenges and changes. Factors other than situations can determine the approach individuals consider for effective leadership (Hersey et al., 1979). The situation approach requires further research and to possibly address leadership actions for change rather than reaction to change.

Transformational Leadership. The potential for organizational and leadership success is enhanced as motivated followers' levels are heightened. Wren (1995) suggested leaders in the 21st century recognize everyone in the organization has an obligation to lead and that leadership, power, and information needs to be shared throughout the organization. Transformation leadership is considered effective in any situation or culture, and there is no identified condition the transformational leadership style is inappropriate or ineffective (Bass, 1997; Yukl, 2013). To respond to current environmental demands and to prepare for the future, transformational leadership style is the style for organizational development now and in the future. Virtual teams are a main component of current organizational structures (Kahai et al., 2007). Ruggieri (2009)

conducted a study comparing the effects of transactional and transformational leaders in virtual groups. Study results revealed the transformational leadership style was better and more adequate in virtual groups (Ruggieri). Transformational leadership empowers followers to lead (Dambe & Moorad, 2008).

Nash et al. (2017) conducted a survey to examine how 61 female leaders and emerging leaders in science, technology, engineering, mathematic and medicine (STEMM) defined leadership and described individual leadership styles. The findings showed women used transformational leadership factors to define leadership and personal styles of leading. However, there were inconsistencies of how the participants defined the ideal leadership or individual leadership style. Gobaw (2017) said the key to effective leadership is having an individual who exhibits transformational leadership traits. Erkutlu (2008) said organizational leaders should invest in continued development of transformational leaders; however, specific gendered styles of leadership may be adding to the leadership gap in STEMM (Nash et al., 2017). Dodd (2012) claimed there is a relationship between successful leadership and any selected leadership style development. Eagly and Chin (2010) claimed women tend to use transformational leadership style, but women are stereotyped as being too masculine or too feminine (Eagly & Carli, 2007). Women's transformational leadership qualities are hindrances to career advancement.

Future of Leadership

Leadership style positively influences organizations' diagnosis process and ultimately organizational change. Leadership roles and styles vary depending on situations, environments, and even culture. Some qualities of leadership are timeless, but

the current era challenges old frameworks, assumptions, and beliefs (Wren, 1995). The historical leadership theories placed emphasis on leaders' traits and behaviors and leaders seemed to control the power in the leader-follower relationship (Dambe & Moorad, 2008). Purvanova and Bono (2009) believed the transformational leadership is effective in the 21st century virtual environments. Chin and Trimble (2014) postulated leaders' flexibility, continuous learning, and diversity awareness and acceptance as essential factors for leadership of the 21st century.

New realities are reshaping the future of leadership. Existing leadership skills in addition to enhanced and new talents are required for organizations to succeed in the volatile uncertain complex and ambiguous world. Leadership theories should encompass the understanding that environments are everchanging, complex, and ambiguous.

“Change simply is” (Stuke, 2013, p. 57), implying future leadership approach should focus on leader-follower relationships to include shared leadership, nonlinear understanding of leadership, and embrace the emergence of environmental changes.

Leadership is important, so leadership diversity that includes women is the best leadership (Eagly & Carli, 2007). Gender diversity in leadership plays an important role in future organizational transformations and organizational learning (Chin & Trimble, 2014). Rapid changes in technology, political and social changes, and intense business competition demand development of leadership skills for future organizational success (Cacioppe, 1998). Changes in organizations could mean change in leadership behaviors.

Summary of Leadership

The topic of leadership has been extensively discussed and reviewed for many decades and selecting one preferred theory is difficult without considering other

contributing variables. Van Wart (2013) explained each theory includes valid domains and perspectives, they all have been researched, and they each continue to evolve. Each of the identified approaches to leadership has strengths and weaknesses. The historical leadership theories placed emphasis on leaders' traits and behaviors and leaders seem to control the power in the leader-follower relationship (Dambe & Moorad, 2008). The great man theory and trait theory of leadership are power based, eliminating the opportunity for followers to become leaders. Leadership roles and styles vary depending on situations, environments, and even culture (Dambe & Moorad, 2008).

The contemporary leadership approach shifted power from leaders to incorporate followers' autonomy in the leader-follower relationship (Dambe & Moorad, 2008). The historical and contemporary leadership approaches share commonality and involve at least a leader, followers, and a vision. Chin (2010) believed amidst new social contexts, emerging global concerns, and changing population demographics, the theories of leadership are irrelevant for the 21st century. Chin (2010) and Chin and Trimble (2014) recommended leadership further develop to incorporate diversity. Wrong leadership perceptions justify the lack of consensus about leadership (Slavik et al., 2015).

Barriers and Obstacles to Women's Advancement to Leadership

Women have struggled with barriers and obstacles to earn a place in the labor force. While women's presence in the workforce has shown significant strides, there are barriers that exist for women who aspire leadership advancement (Schwanke, 2013). With women's positive progression to equality in the workplace, they remain underrepresented in leadership positions (Chin, 2011). Multiple barriers to women's advancement to leadership positions exist (Diehl & Dzubinski, 2016; Walker & Artiz,

2015). Leung (2008) claimed barriers impact career goals and decision-making. Swanson and Woitke (1997) added the barriers can be internal or in an individual's surroundings. The existence of masculinity organizational culture (Diehl & Dzubinski, 2016; Walker & Aritz, 2015), organizational prejudices in recruitment, hiring and promotion (Diehl & Dzubinski, 2016; Hart, 2016), and false perceptions or stereotypes (Bierema, 2016; Taylor et al., 2016) are some barriers that shape women's experiences. Barriers prevent women's career advancement to leadership positions (O'Reilly & Garret, 2017; Van Oosten et al., 2017).

Biases

Research findings revealed women experience implicit and explicit forms of biases in the workplace (Nosek et al., 2009). McCullough (2011) believed women advance at a slower pace than men and women are paid less than men in similar STEM roles. Overt sexism, covert sexism, and discrimination are hindrances to women's participation in STEM (McCullough). Kalaitzi et al. (2017) conducted a qualitative study to assess empirically gendered barriers to women's leadership in healthcare. The study's finding exposed 21 barriers experienced by women; including age, glass ceiling, lack of social support, sexual harassment, stereotypes, and racial discrimination (Kalaitzi et al.). Women face a plethora of barriers when seeking to attain leadership roles. Biases affect how women will pursue education and careers, and how women in the workplace react and relate to situations, organizational practices, and perceived discriminatory treatments. Biases negatively affect women's leadership opportunities (Carrasco et al., 2015).

Cultural Biases. Culture is unique shared beliefs and principles that are created or developed by a particular group (Carrasco et al., 2015; Schein & Schein, 1991). Bass

(1985) claimed culture constructs the identity of organizations; thus, culture can be one of the most influential elements in organizations. Women are equally qualified as males to attain top leadership positions, yet societal and cultural constraints impede women from succeeding (Chisholm-Burns et al., 2017). In a quantitative study, Carrasco et al. (2015) examined cultural bias against women in 32 countries and found the cultural biases affected the level of leadership position females attain. In another quantitative study, Mills et al. (2012) found segregation in feminine and masculine jobs and believed gender biases are likely to continue in society. Schein (2009) posited that culture results from what leaders' value, believe, and assume; what members experience; and the new beliefs of members and leaders. Since leadership is a form of cultural expression, what leaders stand for and communicate to employees is critical (Sergiovanni & Corbally, 1986).

Organizational Culture. Leadership shapes organizational cultures and organizational cultures effect leadership selections. Schein and Schein (1991) explained that customs, values, principles or standards of behaviors, and core assumptions that are consistently held internally by a specific group define organizational culture. Organizational cultures stem from leadership's philosophy, actions, and reactions. Every business or organization has a culture—weak or strong—with significant influences throughout the system (Wren, 1995). Culture affects everything in organizations to include promotions, policies, and decision making (Wren, 1995). Given that culture is powerful, it is assumed when leadership behavior changes, the culture of the organization shifts, specifically as it relates to leadership composition.

Carrasco et al.'s (2015) quantitative study revealed that cultural biases negatively affect females' progression to leadership positions. Importantly, behaviors displayed by

men or women were perceived and assessed differently—causing bias—which prevents women from joining corporate boards. Carrasco et al. added stereotypes might stipulate the advancement of women’s professional development. In another study, Stoker et al. (2012) found preference for women managers when there was increased female presence in the organization. Organizational leaders may consider organizational culture when forming and implementing leadership development endeavors (Hasler, 2005). Institutional culture aimed at promoting women are key barriers (Salas-Lopez et al., 2011). Creating an organizational culture with leadership that understands the barriers women encounter in pursuits to professional development will aid to negate the culture of negative bias (Hurley & Choudhary, 2016).

Inclusion of women in senior leadership improves decision making, results in high productivity and better financial performance (Glass & Cook, 2016). Gender disparity in top leadership roles is an economic problem, and not only women’s problem (Brands et al., 2017). Gender diversity is positively linked to the quality of innovation in organizations (Ruiz-Jiménez, et al., 2016). Organizational culture that value leadership diversity supports human resource practices to involve fairness, equality, and justice (Witherspoon & Wohlert, 1996). Leadership that creates an inclusive culture and provides equal opportunities encourages full value of talent, and addresses systemic discriminations (Yukl, 2013). Organizations that support diversity contribute to changing the way people think, develop acceptable standards, and form positive behaviors that can support women going into leadership positions.

Masculinist Culture. Women represent more than 50% of the world population, yet they fail to hold 50% of managerial positions anywhere in the world (Izraeli et al.,

1994). Only 5% of women in Fortune 1000 companies hold the highest leadership positions. Research findings supported assumptions that barriers for females going into high-rank leadership positions is contributed by male dominance (Kunze & Miller, 2017, p. 669). Masculinist culture can shape women's experiences, since these cultures create biases against women, devalue women, and support men (Grunspan et al., 2016; Gunter, 2009; Maatta & Lyckhage, 2011). Work related barriers prevent women from seeking leadership attainment and reduces their ability to perform (Moylan & Wood, 2016; O'Reilly & Garret, 2017). Masculinist culture is reinforced when women opt out of advancing careers to leadership and promotes leadership barriers for future generations (Moylan & Wood, 2016). Masculine attributes are assigned to leaders, hindering women from leadership who display perceived feminine characteristics that are gentle and shy (Eagly & Carli, 2007). Perceptions and masculine cultures are contributory barriers to women attaining leadership positions. Individuals' perceptions of leadership laud masculinity and deprecate femininity, making it difficult for women to be perceived as leaders (Perdue, 2017).

Leadership Perceptions

Leadership styles and the behaviors of leaders affect the behaviors of followers and their perceptions. Leadership is a social influence process (Wren, 1995). Followers respond negatively or positively to leadership behaviors. Litmanovitz (2011) explored issues affecting women in educational leadership and found society's perceptions of effective leaders were instrumental to male dominance in leadership. Implicit leadership theories are perceptions used to form acceptable traits and behaviors that individuals identify with leaders (Schyns, 2006). Similarly, self-identity influences leadership

perceptions (MacDonald et al., 2008). In the leadership process, influence is a key component, and it requires an individual or individuals who will be influenced. Women need more women in leadership to relate to and identify with for leader identity creation (Schell & Hughes, 2017).

According to Taylor et al. (2016), research fails to confirm the belief that men are better leaders than women. Taylor et al. conducted a study examining the influences of women's perceptions, specifically self-awareness and its impact on women's interest or lack of interest to leadership attainment. Study results showed false perceptions were barriers hindering women from progressing to leadership positions (Taylor et al.). The negative perceptions concerning women leaders can be a result of people's preconceived notions about leaders and women (Eagly & Carli, 2007). Negative perceptions surrounding women's leadership abilities exist, although women and men share similar leadership styles (Seo et al., 2017). Seo et al. (2017) posited that gender differences do not account for leadership effectiveness. Perceptions of who leaders are and how leaders behave affect women's leadership perceptions and self-efficacy. Machida and Feltz (2013) believed that as women question personal abilities to lead, self-efficacy is lowered, negatively affecting career advancement to leadership.

Current Content

Current content linked to the study is discussed in this section. A literature review for content less than five years old connected to the study was examined. The current content is divided into three major sections and will cover the following topics: history of working women in the United States, leadership, and barriers and obstacles to women's advancement to leadership.

History of Working Women in the United States

In the 1920s, female had up 20% participation in the workforce- (U.S. Department of Labor, n.d.). Prior to the 1930s, women's gainful unemployment defined women's labor force participation (Rose, 2018). World War II triggered restructuring of the labor force resulting in an influx in women's participation in new work categories (Rose, 2018). The increased presence of women in the labor force created the rise to women's equality and the projection for long-term change in American workforce composition. Shatnawi and Fishback (2018) reported employers were satisfied with female workers. Yet, women experienced discrimination from unions and employers, preventing women from participating in supervisory positions (Rose, 2018).

Women in STEM

The gender gap in STEM careers continues, causing an issue in the U.S. workforce (Swafford & Anderson, 2020). Wajngurt and Sloan (2019) explained there is gender inequality within STEM and women's input is needed to stimulate innovation. The female participation rate in STEM fields vary. In 2017, women were considerably underrepresented at 9% in construction, 30% in manufacturing, 24% in transportation and utilities (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2018). Schmitt et al. (2021) believed the underrepresentation of women in STEM fields contributes to their struggles for career development. Women's struggle in STEM fields was displayed when Ellen Swallow Richards, the first woman admitted into the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) was denied her degree conferment after successfully completing the requirement to receive her master's degree (White, 2019). Information from the National Center for Educational Statistics (2019) showed 140,000 women graduated in STEM fields in 2016.

Seyranian et al. (2018) postulated sex discrimination as the reason why women do not receive equal opportunities as men when entering STEM careers. On the contrary, Herbst (2020) asserted lack of support as contributory to women's struggle to form leadership identity and build a career in STEM.

Women Leadership in STEM

Despite women making up most of the workforce, men occupy more leadership positions. Women are underrepresented in leadership (Epperson et al., 2020; Li et al., 2019; Main et al., 2021; Randsley de Moura et al., 2018). McCullough (2020) conducted a study to examine the number of women in STEM fields that were in leadership positions, and how many women in leadership positions possessed STEM-related backgrounds. McCullough's study results showed women were significantly underrepresented in senior leadership levels in higher education. In the U.S., the number of women in leadership positions are low; 30% are presidents in colleges and universities and there are more male than female CEOs in the STEM industry (McCullough, p. 1). Hartman and Barber (2019, p. 92) and Moak et al. (2020, p. 1243) found women represented only 6.6% of CEO roles in Fortune 500 companies. Fox et al. (2019) said women remain underrepresented in leadership in many industries. According to Thornton (2020), women simply are underrepresented in executive roles when compared to men.

Makarem and Wang (2020) explained women were not regularly accepted in STEM fields, and there were barriers to their entrance and persistence in STEM's male-dominated field. More importantly, compared to men, women struggle to successfully develop careers in STEM (Makarem & Wang). Thus, without representation, it may be difficult for women to become leaders in STEM professions. McCabe et al. (2020, p.

396) found gender differences in STEM leadership and reported that 64% of STEM leaders were males. A study by McCabe et al. revealed that women were admitted into elite STEM graduate programs, and possessed the abilities, upbringing, interests, and personality to excel in STEM. GAO Reports (p. 6) showed in 2018, women held 31% of senior-level management positions in the financial services industry. Baker et al. (2019) argued that equal representation in leadership provides diversity, allowing for alternatives in organizational decision-making, knowledge sharing, and increased team creativeness (Ruzgar, 2018). Given the proposed benefits of leadership diversity relating to gender, more women leaders may have substantial influence in progressing the STEM industry.

Women Leadership in Engineering

Careers in engineering positively impacts individuals, organizations, the industry, and the world. Helman et al. (2020) argued that careers in engineering offer opportunities that advance knowledge, create opportunity for everyone by uplifting communities, while improving access and sustaining the planet. Unfortunately, women encounter barriers advancing to leadership positions, and so women do not pursue or persist in engineering careers (Helman et al.). Makarem and Wang (2020, p. 42) purported that although women held 44% of the science labor force in the U.S, women represented 14.5% of the architecture and engineering employment. Lewis (2018) posited there is a leadership gap with the increasing unused talent in STEM leadership.

Globally, women remain underrepresented in STEM fields, such as engineering and technology (American Association of University Women, 2019; Catalyst, 2020). Since the 1970s, women have steadily entered the engineering fields—from 3% to 15% in 2019 (Martinez & Christnacht, 2021, para 10). Despite the positive changes, women

still struggle to maintain jobs in engineering fields. Only 21% of engineering majors are women, and only 24% of females who majored in engineering pursue careers in engineering (American Association of University Women, 2019). With the large disparity of women's presence in engineering, it poses a critical concern of how many women are in engineering leadership and what dictates the trend. Women struggle to advance careers in engineering (Lewis, 2018) and men continue to dominate the field (Han et al., 2018; Hickey & Cui, 2020).

Han et al. (2018) explained discrimination is unconscious bias and are predominant determinants to women's presence in STEM, especially in engineering. Loy (2019) believed that instead of increasing women's acceptance in STEM, organizations can strategically incorporate women in leadership positions in engineering. A study conducted by Fernando et al. (2018) listed ways that enabled women engineers to remain in the field, and potentially obtain leadership positions. Self-confidence in women's skills and abilities—self-efficacy—was one listed personal attribute to help retain women engineers (Fernando et al.). Self-efficacy can positively or negatively influence women's progression to leadership positions.

Leadership

The topic of leadership has been examined and researched for centuries and yet it continues to be developed. Arikan (2020) posited that for 50 years there has been a focus on leadership studies. Northouse (2018) added that over the years, leadership has been defined and theorized in various ways. Leadership is critical for an organization's success and performance (Al Khajeh, 2018). Personal characteristics may differ from one leader to another. Leaders may be people oriented, process oriented, or results oriented (Arikan,

2020). However, the selected leadership approach should not necessarily prevent goal attainment and leadership success. Effective leadership develops and creates a good organizational climate, while helping to attain identified goals and visions (Gaviria-Rivera & Lopez-Zapata, 2019). Leadership is a process that is complex and highly valued, and leadership also creates change and movement (Northouse). Northouse added that leaders motivate and inspire others in attaining a shared goal. The assumption is there are indeterminate definitions of leadership, and the topic is of great importance for its continued research and evolution (Arikan, 2020; Benmira & Agboola, 2021; Rosenbach, 2018).

Leadership Theories

Historical leadership theories paved the way for the evolution of the contemporary theories of leadership. The dynamic evolving process of leadership has many concepts and constructs. Effective leadership is not bound to just one individual (Pretorius et al., 2018). Leadership is no longer grounded on a single individual's actions or characteristics, but rather is an activity shared between a team of individuals (Kukenberger & D'Innocenzo, 2020). Leadership styles impact organizational performance, so selecting the appropriate leadership style is significant (Arikan, 2020; Al Khajeh, 2018).

Historical Leadership Theories

Early works on leadership are as old as the history of people (Asrar-ul-Haq & Anwar, 2018). The focus of the earliest historical leadership approaches was on the leader as a *great man* or *great person*. Then researchers focused leadership on defining an individual's trait to determine a great leader. Leadership shifted focus on behaviors

and leaders' actions (Rosenbach, 2018). The skills or trait-based leadership approach focused on an individual's competences, suggesting individuals have certain characteristics and cannot emerge as leaders if those traits were missing (Turner & Baker, 2018). The historical leadership theories evolved from perceptions that leaders were only born, to leaders possessing certain traits and then focused on the ideal behaviors of leaders.

Great Man Theory. The great man theory was one of the first approach researchers used to study leadership. Leadership inquiries and analysis began with the great man theory, which claimed individuals are born as leaders (Benmira & Agboola, 2021). Researchers believed leaders were born with similar qualities and characteristics of great social, political, and military leaders (Northouse, 2018). According to the great man theory, only individuals born with the natural abilities of greatness are leaders (Dziak, 2019; Northouse, 2018). Benmira and Agboola (2021) believed leadership skills are not learned and may not be developed over time. Leaders are geniuses who are powerful, influential heroes capable of partaking in multiple roles simultaneously (Dziak, 2019; Mouton, 2019). The great man theory assigned innate abilities to leaders, but Dziak (2019) argued that society influenced leadership. The theory failed to include follower's contributions to leadership success (Mouton, 2019).

Trait Theory of Leadership. In the mid-20th century, the trait theory of leadership evolved as the questions on leadership continued. Northouse (2018) argued that leaders were different from followers and traits were the contributing factors to defining leadership. Successful leadership was not solely dependent on one individual, and there were personalities that contributed to successful leadership outcomes.

According to Benmira and Agboola (2021), leaders were either born or created from training or skills development. Leaders possessed intelligence, self-confidence, determination, integrity, and sociability (Northouse, 2018). Rosenbach (2018) disagreed that leaders were exceptionally intelligent, more energetic, and dynamic; and study results revealed leaders were only a bit more intelligent than the average person and not significantly energetic nor dynamic. Although the trait theory of leadership provided a level of standard for employers and it was consistent with the perception of leadership, it failed to link traits to behavior (Northouse (2018).

Although the trait theory of leadership was extensively researched and its focus was on leaders, followers, and situations, the theory was not a common style for all situations and was not useful for leadership theory and development as it was ambiguous and uncertain at times (Northouse, 2018). The assumption was individuals were not born as great leaders, but leaders were born with specific traits. Kamalizeni et al. (2018) conducted a study to investigate the under representation of women leadership in public enterprises in Swaziland. The purpose of the study was to establish the barriers impeding women from rising to leadership positions. The findings of the study identified several barriers including women's low self-esteem, masculine perceptions towards women's leadership, as well as women's paucity in leadership skills (Kamalizeni et al.). The study results also revealed some traits in women, which were believed to contribute towards organizational success. Women possess traits that are transferrable to positively influence leadership in organizations. Women compared to men have no significant differences in leadership abilities (Place & Vardeman-Winter, 2018).

Contemporary Leadership Theories

The historical leadership approaches were reviewed, analyzed, and upgraded with the contemporary leadership approaches. The contemporary leadership approach shifted power from leaders to incorporate followers' autonomy in the leader-follower relationship. The contemporary approach to leadership includes situational leadership, transactional leadership, adaptive leadership, and transformational leadership (Northouse, 2018). The contemporary approaches to leadership acknowledge the importance of the leader-follower relationship; recognize the need for leadership flexibility; focus on shared influence and power with followers; and emphasize the followers' need to grow and to develop.

Situational Leadership Theory. In 1969, researchers Hersey et al. (1979) developed the situational leadership theory. Northouse (2018) explained that situational leadership approach allowed leaders to adjust leadership styles depending on the needs of the followers. Benmira and Agboola (2021) added leadership styles were continually assessed and varied depending on the situation. Situational approach to leadership was flexible, which meant leadership was not recognized as constant and relying mainly on who the leaders were perceived as. Rather, leadership incorporated individual and environmental needs (Walls, 2019), and leaders' primary roles were to direct, coach, support, and delegate (Northouse 2018). Any individual can emerge as leader depending on the situation and given time (Arikan, 2020).

The fluidity of the situational leadership approach influenced and developed followers' confidence since followers may have deemed the style as personal custom-made design, which may have also contributed to followers' commitment to the common

goals (Walls, 2019). Certain situations may warrant a follower to assume the role of a leader and may shape leaders' behaviors and effectiveness (Dipboye, 2018). Arikan (2020) believed leaders naturally emerge from situations. Fowler (2021) agreed and said each team member can take on different roles for different situations. Northouse (2018) argued that although the situational approach to leadership has been extensively used in leadership training programs, few studies have been conducted to support its validity. Followers, including women, may emerge as leaders.

Transformational Leadership Theory. Transformational leaders motivate followers by engaging and connecting with the followers while helping to achieve full potential (Northouse, 2018). Transformational style of leadership connects with followers and places emphasis on a follower's need to grow and develop and contribute to organizational creativity (Arikan, 2020). Northouse (2018) confirmed transformational leaders are attentive to the needs of the followers, and leaders tend to be charismatic, inspirational, and intellectual. Leaders allow followers autonomy to perform assigned duties without the leader's continuous direction and involvement or until leadership intervention is needed. The transformational leadership approach builds trust with followers and encourages creativity as it recognizes their accomplishments (Northouse, 2018).

The potential for organizational and leadership success is enhanced as motivated followers need levels are heightened. Organizations with the transformational leadership theory facilitate followers' personal growth and confidence while building trusting leader-follower relations (Busari et al., 2019). However, Northouse (2018) believed the approach lacked theoretical clarity, was not applicable for all environments, and did not

define a link between leaders and the changes in followers and organizations. On the contrary, Benmira and Agboola (2021) believed transformational leadership was appropriate in organizations, and positively influences organizational change. Saint-Michel (2018) said the transformational style of leadership was associated to females more than males.

Future of Leadership

Leadership studies and theories continue their evolution. Rapid changes to organizational structure and advancements in communication and technologies require an effective and responsive leadership approach (Atasoy, 2020). Leadership is of great importance for its continued research and development. However, to meet the challenges and complexities of organizations and its environments, modifications to the contemporary leadership theories are required (Turner & Baker, 2018). To effectively lead organizations in the existing complex environment, a transformation is required. Traditional leadership approaches failed to incorporate the demands of digital transformations in the new digital era (Gierlich-Joas et al., 2020). Leadership is required to redesign forms of control and implement new employee empowerment. Klein (2020) believed leaders benefit from reassessing skills and traits to successfully understand the new digital cultures and talents that exist in organizations.

Contemporary and current leadership excludes the emergence of the leaders' world. Predicting the future is challenging, so organizations that are adaptive to changes will survive and succeed (Wyrwicka & Chuda, 2019). Internal and external factors demand continuous changes for organizations to remain competitive, profitable, and positioned for future evolution. In groups, teams, and organizations, decision making is

one of the most important tasks for leadership, because the decisions impact the successes or failures for that entity (Kozioł-Nadolna & Beyer, 2021). Continued leadership development with diversity and inclusivity can meet the demands of the STEM industry. Minehart et al. (2020) postulated there were advantages to addressing the challenges of gender stereotypes in leadership and to promote an inclusive leadership approach. Chyu et al., (2021) agreed that adopting an inclusive leadership culture will increase diversity and gender equality in leadership. Gender diversity in leadership is beneficial to decision making, strategic thinking, and overall performance of an organization.

Summary of Leadership

Researchers began examining leadership, its components, and its outcomes since the early 19th century. The varying contributions from researchers have not clearly defined one universal meaning of leadership. Many disagreements exist about leadership, but one commonality among all theories is leadership is important (Benmira & Agboola, 2021; Gandolfi & Stone, 2018). Yates (2019) believed an individual's uniqueness was the only commonality, as there are different leadership approaches and styles individuals may select when leading others. A selected approach may be impacted by situational or environmental changes (Benmira & Agboola, 2021). Therefore, leadership is more effective when leaders can adapt to unexpected changes. Understanding leadership and its components are important for leadership change and organizational successes.

Barriers and Obstacles to Women's Advancement to Leadership

The presence of more women in equally leading positions as male counterparts may benefit employers in attracting junior female STEM students to join the industry, potentially increasing women's presence in STEM. Growing concerns of gender equality

and implementation initiatives for accelerating women's careers in organizations is present (Kossek & Buzzanell, 2018). Yet, women still encounter barriers to attaining leadership positions (Griffiths et al., 2019). In the U.S., women remain at an alarming disadvantage in career paths, rewards, retention, and advancement. Women experience barriers and obstacles in career trajectories (Kossek & Buzzanell, 2018). The marginalization of women from leadership is problematic and concerning, drawing attention to explore reasons for the underrepresentation of women in STEM leadership positions.

Biases

Unconscious bias, racism, lack of leadership programs, and exclusion from male-dominated positions were cited as some of the challenges encountered by women aspiring to advance to leadership roles. (Madsen & Andrade, 2018; Simona & George, 2018). Bordalo et al. (2019) believed women's absence from leadership is due to gender bias. Moss-Racusin et al. (2018) conducted a study to examine whether gender bias causes gender gaps in STEM engagement. In one of the experiments, women anticipated less sense of belonging, positivity toward, and aspirations to participate in STEM than men when shown STEM gender bias. However, the gender differences disappeared when participants were told STEM exhibits gender equality, thus suggesting gender bias promotes STEM gender gaps. Study results also revealed that focusing only on bias awareness and initiatives were inadequate to address the gender bias in STEM (Moss-Racusin et al.). Biases are implicit or explicit, intentional, or unintentional prejudices toward a person, thing, or group.

Cultural Biases. Workplace diversity is predominant, and many organizations establish significant goals to achieve a diverse workforce (Flory et al., 2021), but cultural bias is unescapable, and everyone experiences cultural bias (Crawford et al., 2019). While some groups are targeted and experience discriminations, other groups are protected because of individual culture (Crawford et al., 2019). Gender instills culture in organizations with about a quarter of leadership positions being held by women (Coleman, 2020). Women experience cultural biases from organizational culture and masculinist culture while advancing to leadership positions (Coleman, 2020; Nash & Moore, 2019).

Organizational Culture. An organization's culture becomes a key construct in the development of management and organizational development. The rapid evolution of organizational changes challenge leadership to create a corporate culture that appeals to everyone in its workforce. Creating a diverse leadership team consisting of multigender and multigenerational workforce naturally fosters a more inclusive environment leading to management and organizational development (Burton et al., 2019). Top female candidates are inclined to obtain employment with gender diverse organizations. According to Turban et al. (2019 para 12), 61% of females consider gender inclusivity when making decisions of where to work. Rajput et al. (2019) believed a multigenerational workforce leads to a multifaceted environment, potentially creating a natural shift in organizations.

Nash and Moore (2019) explored women's underrepresentation in STEMM leadership worldwide. The leadership experiences of a group of 25 women from 5 countries were examined over a 2-year period from 2016 to 2018. The study's

participants shared experiences of difficulties, including organizational structures and masculinist culture, while working in the STEMM field. Notably, one participant suggested women need to be selected as leaders to exhibit leadership (Nash & Moore). In another study, Coleman (2020) interviewed 60 women in leadership roles from varying fields. The research questions were asked to women for their perceptions on career barriers to attaining leadership positions, the main facilitators of career progress for women, and changes they have seen or want to see for women leaders at work. The results of Coleman's study revealed masculinist work culture as a predominant barrier along with discrimination and the glass ceiling; gendered stereotyping; and family-work-life balance difficulties. Specifically, participants said personal perceptions driven by culture, self-doubt, and implicit leadership prototypes were experienced (Coleman). Leadership benefits from building a culture based on diversity and inclusion (Brown, 2019), and diversity fuels innovation (McCausland, 2021). Individuals learn from each other, leading to a creative process that stimulates the innovative ideas of the individuals (Super, 2020).

Masculinist Culture. Male dominance in the workplace can be a hindrance to women's performance, contributing to less than favorable opportunities regarding leadership potential. According to Shinbrot et al. (2019), there are gendered organizations with cultures that favor men, leaving women at a disadvantage. Dean and Perrett (2020) believed organizations with masculinist cultures create barriers to women's advancement to leadership. According to Shinbrot et al. (2019), assertiveness and confidence are leadership qualities linked to masculinity, and women who display these traits are ostracized. Notably, self-confidence is associated with social status, better performance,

and effective leadership (Guillén et al., 2018). Perceptions that senior leadership is masculine, results in women's personal perceptions of their own abilities to perform assigned roles (Smyth et al., 2018).

Leadership Perceptions

Leadership perceptions are used to preclude women equal opportunities to attain leadership positions. Van Esch et al. (2018) explained that women are perceived as unmotivated and uncommitted to jobs. Contrary, men in leadership are perceived as confident, and perception is associated with better performance and effective leadership (Guillén et al., 2018). Preconceptions of leadership may influence decision-making and promotions, thus impacting women's ability to advance careers to leadership positions. Bloodhart et al. (2020) reported that women grapple with personal doubts of abilities and talent.

Leadership perceptions contribute to women's career advancement. According to Van Esch et al. (2018), women are a risk when being considered for hire or promotion. Compared to men, women are perceived as less committed to jobs and lacked ambition (Van Esch et al.). Women's perceptions of masculinity or femininity could determine behaviors in roles. The implication is perceptions determine women's self-efficacy and how women perceive themselves as leaders (Smyth et al., 2018). Furthermore, when women form STEM identity and leadership identity, women develop a sense of belonging in STEM (Rodriguez et al., 2019).

Conceptual Framework Literature

Conceptual frameworks are analytical and methodical sets of theories utilized to create the foundation of the research (Caffrey, 2020). Beginning with the historical great

man theory, leadership was embedded in a social construct of internal and external perceptions. Positing connectedness of self-efficacy, implied beliefs, and perceptions to shaping individuals' ability to successfully accomplish tasks. Bandura's (1986) self-efficacy theory and Lord et al.'s (1984) implicit leadership theory were the conceptual frameworks utilized as foundation for exploring participants' perceptions and experiences of obstacles to females' advancement to leadership in STEM.

Self-Efficacy Theory

Beliefs are influential in stimulating positive or negative actions. Bandura's (1997) theory on self-efficacy determines how an individual's belief influences behaviors; beliefs precede actions. Bandura's self-efficacy theory links psychological principles of human thoughts to confidence, motivation, and behaviors. A study by Baker et al. (2016) revealed self-efficacy directly contributes to leadership intentions. Self-efficacy possibly is a determinant of females' path to career advancements. According to Hadary and Henderson (2013, p. 26), females' goals for growth result in high accomplishments.

Bandura (1986) explained individuals with low self-efficacy set lower goals, doubting their personal capabilities. Hence, people with strong self-efficacy are more likely to be motivated to set high goals for themselves and work diligently to achieve the goals. In contrast, people with low self-efficacy may doubt capabilities and do not aspire for challenging roles. People with high self-efficacy are willing to strengthen determinations and persist longer in overcoming barriers to the attainment of goals (Bandura, 1986).

Mindset can positively or negatively affect females' representation in leadership. Using a standard regression approach, Burnette et al. (2010) assessed individual differences in implicit theories of leadership ability and self-efficacy for leadership. Results showed women with low self-efficacy reported lower self-evaluations after experiencing stereotypical threats. Women with high initial leadership self-efficacy withstood the negative effects of stereotype threats on self-esteem and post threat self-efficacy. Additionally, the results of Burnette et al.'s study supported the important role of self-efficacy for people to navigate leadership challenges. Self-efficacy augments motivation, behavior, and performance (Shirey, 2020). Self-efficacy is measurable and can be developed. With the available sources of self-efficacy, females in STEM may build effective leadership development strategies and advance to leadership positions.

Implicit Leadership Theory

Lord et al.'s (1984) ILT may be used to explain why women are not equally advancing to leadership within organizations. Schyns (2006) examined the effects implicit leadership theory has on the careers of leaders. The study was constructed on the idea that implicit leadership theories affect promotion decisions. Positive perception of leaders results in good performance appraisal, while consequences of negative perception of leaders results in a very bad performance appraisal. Schyns' study revealed a relationship between implicit leadership theories and promotion decisions. Supervisors' implicit leadership theories and personal perceptions of a subordinate leaders negatively affect the subordinate's performance appraisal and decreases the chance of promotion (Schyns, 2006). Notably, the perceptions of women as leaders are the most significant

barrier encountered by women leaders (Lord & Maher, 1991). The image of leadership could be crucial to careers and advancement of potential female leaders.

The ILT asserts leadership is perceptions—cognitive structures formed to determine who leads and who does not. Leadership is not essentially innate abilities, traits, and behaviors of aspiring leaders. Traits of gifted individuals are only cognitive abstractions formed by others. According to Lord et al. (1984), each person has a belief system that holds features distinguishing leaders from nonleaders, forming leader prototypes. Followers, leaders, and aspiring leaders mentally create the ideal leadership. MacDonald et al. (2008) purported leadership prototypes are different between perceivers and in individual perceivers. People who do not fit the prototype can experience bias perceptions and assessment, hence the ILT is directly relevant to perception and evaluation of female leadership (Hoyt et al., 2012).

Perception is powerful to shape behaviors. What is especially pernicious about these perceptions is they may be unspoken and possibly unconscious. Women are sensitive to others' opinions and perceptions, and about people's expectations of the role of women (Hadary & Henderson, 2013). The question arises whether false perceptions are impediments to female's career advancement to leadership positions. Perceptions of the ILT subsequently are used to select leaders from individuals who fits the leadership image, resemble leaders, and behave as leaders. The ILT is a scale for defining who is a leader and who is not (Swanson et al., 2020), and the leadership prototype serves as a guide. Through life experiences and social constructs from society and organizations, people are shown others in leadership roles in the peripheries of a specific image. Schyns et al. (2011) noted people form mental models of leaders using traits and behaviors that

fit in the leadership context. The implications are people may not see themselves as leaders, and aspirants may not fit the leader prototype.

Methodological Literature

Qualitative and quantitative research are two dominant research paradigms; the quantitative research methods use numerical data format while the textual data format is generated with the qualitative research method (Avison et al., 1999; Dobrovolny & Fuentes, 2008). When used appropriately, the qualitative approach is equal in value to quantitative research approach (Avison et al., 1999). Qualitative and quantitative research methods are similar in some ways because they each produce raw data to analyze, are used to measure the results of the data collected, and participants are necessary (Dobrovolny & Fuentes, 2008). Research questions guide the choice of the research methodology (Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2005). Dobrovolny and Fuentes (2008) agreed research questions are used to determine the selected methodology, and further suggested researchers use evaluation tools to decide which paradigm to choose.

Qualitative research is based on constructivist approach, and researchers believe reality is subjective, thus relying on the participants in the study to understand social realities (Creswell, 2013). While qualitative researchers rely on large samples, qualitative researchers employ purposeful sampling with one or few individuals or groups to understand certain phenomenon (Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2007). Accordingly, this qualitative method research will use approximately 30 participants to explore how those in the engineering industry experience and perceive obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership.

Quantitative Method

Xu (2015) selected quantitative research to examine the gender-based earning gap between men and women in the STEM field. Xu aimed to identify the earning equality between men and women in STEM and nonSTEM-related fields between 1994 and 2003 and found women's position in the STEM industry did not grow although men and women shared comparable GPAs in undergraduate majors. Additionally, Xu found the pay gains for women were marginal compared to male counterparts over the same period. The prolonged wage disparity is potentially one explanation for the lack of career advancement for women.

In another quantitative study, Reinking and Martin (2018) conducted extensive research to review existing literature by consolidating and summarizing the findings from various studies to efficiently investigate the gap in the STEM related fields. Using summative content analysis, common themes were found throughout the process of coding. Reinking and Martin confirmed the presence of gender gap in STEM professions.

Qualitative Method

Hart (2016) used an interpretivist research paradigm methodology, specifically a qualitative case study that evaluated midcareer women in STEM and the workplace factors that contributed to career outcomes and development. A small sample size of 25 female faculty at Land Grant University were interviewed to obtain answers from individuals' perspectives of the institutional processes that constrained careers (Hart). Hart found participants in the STEM department encountered many challenges, specifically bias with females who were required to participate in multiple varying committees while men were assigned to fewer. Additionally, findings from Hart's

qualitative study showed there were barriers to women's career development at the university.

Mixed Method

Makarem and Wang (2020) used a mixed-method approach to conduct a systematic literature review to explore women's career experiences in STEM fields. Two sets of predeveloped criteria guided the screening of 165 publications, resulting in 28 articles for final review (Makarem & Wang). Makarem & Wang found women's career experiences are shaped by individual characteristics to include motivation, self-efficacy, and passion; women are influenced by males in the workplace, parents, and human resource practices. Additionally, Makarem and Wang explained women encounter numerous challenges in careers, and commonly espouse coping mechanisms to advance in careers.

Similarities and Differences in Method Literature

Each researcher addressed the STEM-related fields, and the relationship females share in its existence and growth. The data collected was generalized to existing situations in STEM. Hart (2016) used a qualitative research method to collect data and focused on a small group with a case study to explore and understand the existing situation. Hart's research was subjective and was constructed by individuals through the responses provided. Reinking and Martin (2018) conducted extensive research to review existing and previously researched literature. A qualitative research method known as historical research was employed by Reinking and Martin to collect, verify and synthesize data.

Makarem and Wang (2020) used a mixed-method approach to conduct a study that revealed women's experiences are influenced by individual characteristics, males in the workplace, parents, and human resource activities. Researchers (Hart, 2016; Makarem & Wang, 2020; Reinking & Martin, 2018; Xu, 2015) gathered data from women thus restricting experiences and perceptions to female's leadership attainment to one gender. Including the experiences and perceptions of males as it relates to female's advancement to leadership in STEM may provide new perspectives on the topic, adding valuable knowledge to the literature. The researchers (Hart, 2016; Makarem & Wang, 2020; Reinking & Martin, 2018; Xu, 2015) failed to provide a more in-depth exploration of the role of cognition to females' selection to leadership nor did the researchers link cognition to leadership development.

Rather than approaching measurement, it was believed selecting a qualitative approach was best to explore and understand the study phenomenon. Shah and Al-Bargi (2013) argued interpretivists do not believe reality exists and it awaits to be found. So, individuals create what is real and create realities through knowledge. Kalman (2019) believed researchers have the knowledge and technical skills, along with flexibility, inquisitiveness, and creativity, to successfully conduct qualitative researchers.

Researchers select a qualitative research design to get an understanding of real-world problems (Korstjens & Moser, 2017). Korstjens and Moser (2017) added interpretive and critical frameworks are best suited for qualitative research since it is not possible to separate the object reality from the research participants who experience and live the situation or event. Suggesting problems relating to social phenomena are best suited for qualitative research. Problems affecting or impacting individuals and personal

experiences may be best suited for qualitative research. The current qualitative exploratory case study could expose new themes in connection with self-efficacy and implicit leadership theories in connection with individuals' experiences and perceptions in the engineering fields and females' advancement to leadership.

Research Design Literature

A case study research design with a stratified sample from two subsets of participants is selected to gain an in-depth understanding of the obstacles and experiences of females in engineering leadership positions (Yin, 2018). Case studies use multiple sources of data (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015; Yin, 2018). Thomas (2013) added case study design consists of comprehensive and precise research into one case or a small set of cases. Rashid et al. (2019) identified four phases when conducting case studies: foundation, prefield, field, and reporting phases. The foundation phase involves the philosophical consideration, inquiry technique consideration, and research logic considerations.

The foundation phase is important because ambiguity in understanding may lead to limitations in the later stages of the case study. Implying researchers understand the ontology, epistemology, axiology, and paradigm choices, to help regulate the boundary and shape of the study. Rashid et al. (2019) added the researcher determines and selects the research questions and decides on an appropriate research method in the second phase. The researcher may have to seek permission and obtain ethical consideration approval before proceeding with the next phase of the research. Data collection is conducted where participants are contacted, and communication takes place. Data is then evaluated and analyzed before the case study report is prepared and presented.

Rashid et al. (2019) suggested the report include case descriptions, participant description, relationship description, details of field protocol, empirical material interpretation, and analysis and conclusion. The purpose of the study was to understand how those in the engineering fields perceive and experience obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. The transportation industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. was used to explore and illustrate the phenomena. The information gained from the study results could be useful to add to the collection of knowledge data to further assist stakeholders in narrowing the gender gap in STEM leadership.

Conclusions

Extensive research of the literature revealed what researchers discovered about the status of women in STEM leadership positions. The simplicity of one's social environment can cause people to have varied aspirations and advance differently. Exploring the literature to understand what influential factors impeded women's advancement to leadership in STEM portrayed decades of females' struggles for gender equality in the workforce. The continued global competition and technological advancements prompts the need for diverse leadership and perspectives (Bierema, 2016; Curtis, 2017). With this information, the assumption is females should have equal representation in leadership. Self-efficacy determines how people motivate themselves, feel, think, and ultimately how they behave (Bandura, 1997). Self-efficacy is adaptable and can be changed with confidence. Thus, leadership emergence can be developed from individual and social context variables (Bracht et al., 2021).

Chapter Summary

Chapter 2 included discussions on disparities between women and men in leadership positions in STEM, specifically engineering fields. A discussion on the history of females' labor force participation in the U.S. from the early 1800s to the present revealed females continued struggles for equality (Gipson et al., 2017; Haile et al., 2016; Lee, 2014; Rindfuss et al., 1996; Webb, 2010). Additional and relevant to this study topic, females' presence in STEM was examined. The framework of the exploratory case study based on the ILT (Lord et al., 1984) and the self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1997) were introduced and supported using germinal and current literature on the theories. Chapter 2 demonstrated the applicability for selecting qualitative research to explore the reasons why females working in STEM are incomparable to males in progressing to leadership positions. Chapter 3 will be divided into 10 sections to explain in detail the research methodology, and the planned steps of the exploratory case study in answering the research questions.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

When compared to men, women have no significant differences in leadership abilities and possess the necessary leadership traits to positively contribute to organizational success (Kamalizeni et al., 2018; Place & Vardeman-Winter, 2018; Ruzgar, 2018). Yet, women still encounter barriers to attaining leadership positions and are highly underrepresented in leadership (Fox et al., 2019; Griffiths et al., 2019; Kossek & Buzzanell, 2018). The purpose of this qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Chapter 3 consists of an in-depth discussion of the details, which include the research method and data appropriateness, research questions, population and sample, informed consent and confidentiality, process of instrument to be used to collect data, field test, credibility and transferability, data collection, and data analysis, and concludes with a summary.

Research Method and Design Appropriateness

Paradigms are varying ways of viewing the world and it often affects the basis for research approach (Davies & Fisher, 2018). Paradigms serve as maps or guides that help researchers determine answers to various problems or issues (Kivunja & Kuyini, (2017)). Therefore, a researcher's knowledge of paradigms and the outcomes of each set of ideas or perspectives may be necessary when conducting various investigations. Positivist, interpretive, critical, and pragmatic research paradigms are four guides or maps that researchers may use to successfully assist in the research process. The focus of each of the four research paradigms is on the different ways the world is viewed. An important

issue is for researchers to understand research paradigms and the research methods that exist to determine the most feasible selection when conducting experiments and findings.

Positivist research paradigm is one of many paradigms researchers use to conduct investigations and determine answers and obtain information. Positivist paradigm, also known as scientist paradigm, was developed in the 18th century by the French philosopher Auguste Comte (Shah & Al-Bargi, 2013). Positivism assumes only one reality exists, and that the reality is objective (Davies & Fisher, 2018). The reality is present, and it awaits to be discovered. Therefore, even if no one is aware of the reality, the fact that it exists remains true. Positivist researchers may apply various methods to generate data. The focus of positivist research methodologies is on explaining relationships between variables that are consistent in time and settings (Shah & Al-Bargi, 2013). As positivist researchers embark on answering the questions of what reality is and how does one know of the reality, experiments may be applied to conclude discoveries and to explain the realities. Tests, scales, questionnaires, interviews, and observation tools are other quantitative research methodologies researchers may use to objectively produce predictive and generalized data (Davies & Fisher, 2018; Shah & Al-Bargi, 2013).

Interpretivist research paradigm also known as naturalistic, constructivist, humanistic, and anti-positivist seeks to describe, explore, and understand human social realities (Shah & Al-Bargi, 2013). Reality is not known beforehand—neither is it clear. Therefore, the reality of the subject is created, and discoveries are determined by researchers. Researchers will interpret the knowledge obtained to understand the reality. Shah and Al-Bargi (2013) argued an interpretivist does not believe reality exists and it

wants to be found. Individuals create what is real and make their own realities through knowledge. Humans help researchers answer the question of why people act the way they do. Interpretivist research paradigm methodology obtain answers from individuals' perspectives, experiences, and life events. Shah and Al-Bargi explained individuals contribute vast amount of data through various methods. Researchers employ different techniques to obtain specific data. Case study, historical information from past cultures, narrative research, and grounded theory are a few data collection techniques used by interpretivists. Interpretivist research paradigms use qualitative research methods to develop theories.

The critical research paradigm's main objective is to raise awareness and promote social change by focusing its research on societal issues such as inequality (Davies & Fisher, 2018). Inequalities and injustice are predominant and common in society, and researchers use real world scenarios and issues to help to reveal the injustice and bring awareness to its existence. "The critical paradigm research tries to emancipate people by changing social, political, and cultural settings" (Shah & Al-Bargi, 2013, p. 259). Investigation and action are key research methods used in the critical research paradigm. Power, control, equality, and individuals' societal position are some of the concerns critical paradigm researchers seek to address. Critical research paradigm methodology may use dialogues with participants as one of the main sources of information. A researcher's goal is to derive at answers to make changes to the existing social issues of major concern. In doing so, researchers may use ideology critique or action approach, such as civil actions (Shah & Al-Bargi, 2013). Civil actions may be beneficial to research as it brings awareness to an existing issue and concern and focus to a specific group of

individuals. Voices can be heard with the use of critical research paradigm methodologies. Positive outcomes result from civil actions. Critical research generally uses qualitative research methods to collect data.

The main objective of pragmatic research paradigm is to solve real world problems, as it does not embrace the ontological and epistemological arguments as previously mentioned paradigms in this study; it recognizes there are single and multiple realities (Davies & Fisher, 2018). Pragmatism may be considered as a practical research paradigm since the focus is on what may really work in a real world, everyday situation. Mixed-methods research is used in the pragmatic research paradigm; qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection may be used for data collection. The use of the mixed methods research approach allows for flexibility and may get varying answers by combining the qualitative and quantitative methods.

Positivist research paradigm uses quantitative methods for data collection while interpretive and critical research paradigms use qualitative research methods. The pragmatic research paradigm incorporates a mixture of qualitative and quantitative research methods for data collections. Positivist research paradigm does not account for individual experiences, it accepts a single known reality, and it is objective (Davies & Fisher, 2018). The interpretive approach views reality as subjective and it uses inductive reasoning to develop theories. Pragmatic research approach is flexible, which may lead to confusion during the data collection process. The critical and pragmatic research paradigms are similar as they seem to focus on existing environmental concerns.

With knowledge of the four paradigms, researchers can select one of two methodologies to conduct research. Research methods may be qualitative, quantitative, or

mixed combination approach (Creswell, 2013). Quantitative and qualitative research methods complement each other, and each method provides new knowledge for solving research problems (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014); however, qualitative and quantitative are two distinct research methodologies. The quantitative methodology uses deductive reasoning as its inquiry mode, statistical analysis to help with determining the internal and external validity, reliability, and objectivity of an event, and data collection is represented numerically (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019). Quantitative research uses tools such as questionnaires or rating scales to numerically measure variables. The nature of quantitative research is focused and established and employs large representative sample (Leedy & Ormrod, 2018).

A qualitative approach was chosen for this study because of the social nature of the research problem. Leedy and Ormrod (2018) posited the quantitative method is appropriate to find correlation between variables or events, but the intention of this study is not to explain connections or to examine relationships between variables or events. Individuals create what is real and create realities through knowledge. With the interpretivist research paradigm methodology, answers may be obtained from individuals' perspectives, experiences, and life events. Qualitative research methods allow for the application of various techniques to collect specific data (Nassaji, 2020). Individuals may contribute a vast amount of data through various methods. Qualitative research is a method used as a data collection technique to obtain statements made by individuals, conduct case study, retrieve historical information from past cultures and acquire narratives from individuals (Farrelly, 2012; Gerring, 2017). Accordingly, a qualitative method was employed, since the intent was to learn more about the status of

women in STEM leadership and to ultimately collect more in-depth data to address the research purpose and answer the research questions. The qualitative method was selected to obtain in-depth data to understand the phenomenon from the participants' perceptions and experiences (Hancock & Algozzine, 2017). A qualitative methodology was appropriate for this study since the information was gathered from participants' perceptions.

The research questions for this study were used as a guide to select the case study design. Selecting the appropriate research design was of great importance in the research process. The selected design is the plan or strategy researchers use for guiding a research study (Cook & Cook, 2016). The research question leads to the research design selected. Exploratory case study was selected to collect more in-depth information about what is occurring. A case study was an appropriate research design to answer research questions that ask how, what, or why, and when the behavior of those in the study cannot be manipulated (Yin, 2018). Grounded theory and ethnography are two other qualitative research designs that were considered for this study.

Grounded Theory

Grounded theory method requires researchers to simultaneously conduct data collection and data analysis. The grounded theory is used to develop theory and provides a pathway to learning about the events researchers' study as well as a method of developing theories to understand them (Charmaz, 2006). More importantly, the theory must be grounded in data. Grounded theory is usually selected to study people's actions and reactions (Rooddehghan et al., 2019). However, the purpose of conducting the study was not to develop theory. Grounded theory is best suited for topics and subjects that are

understudied or with no research (Charmaz, 2006). The research topic of the underrepresentation of women in leadership was studied, but the phenomenon persists and requires additional exploration.

Ethnography

Ethnography research method is used when exploring the way of life in a group of people, specifically the group's culture (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). Researchers choose the ethnographic methods when the goal is to get in-depth knowledge of the subjects using observation as the primary data collection instrument. However, the ethnography method is inappropriate for this study as all participants in the study are not of the same cultural background and are not located in the same place (Creswell, 2013). Ethnography was not selected because the purpose of this study was not to explore the cultural norms and views or behaviors of the study population.

Case Studies

Case studies consist of a subject and an object; the subject is a person, situation, event, or incident, and the object is the analytical frame and is said to be the purpose of the study (Thomas, 2013). When selecting a case study as a research methodology, researchers first identify the subject and the object. Researcher may select the subject dependent on personal interest or to understand more about the case or cases (Yin, 2018). The researcher then makes a choice of conducting a single study or multiple studies. Rashid et al. (2019) identified four phases when conducting a case study: foundation, prefield, field, and reporting phases. The foundation phase involves the philosophical consideration, inquiry technique consideration, and research logic considerations. The foundation phase is important because ambiguity in understanding may lead to

limitations in the later stages of the case study, which requires researchers understand the ontology, epistemology, axiology, and paradigm choices (Rashid et al.), because their decision will regulate the boundary and shape of the study. In the second phase, the researcher determines and selects the research questions and decides on an appropriate research method. The researcher obtains permission and ethical consideration approval before proceeding with the next phase of the research. In the third phase, data collection is conducted where participants are contacted, and communication takes place. Data is then evaluated and analyzed before the case study report is prepared and presented in the fourth and final phase. Rashid et al. suggested the report include case description, participant description, relationship description, details of field protocol, empirical material interpretation and analysis, and conclusion.

Researchers can face challenges when conducting a case study. Providing details of participant descriptions may be impossible because of ethical considerations. Rashid et al. (2019) suggested the researcher provide a short overview of participants to overcome this challenge. When interpreting data, the researcher may unintentionally misrepresent information, so using recorded interviews and cross-checking interview notes may help to overcome this challenge. Case study is time consuming because of data coding and data analysis, specifically the coding process requires extensive time (Campbell, 2015). The researcher may choose to effectively manage time, remain focused on the study, and become knowledgeable of skills required for data coding to effectively address the challenge. Although there are identified drawbacks of using the case study design, there are recommendations for addressing the challenges (Rashid et al., 2019).

Case study was selected as an appropriate research design for this study because it is a method of inquiring used to investigate an event affecting specific participants (Yin, 2018). The researcher used a case study design to explore perceptions of participants to understand a phenomenon and contribute knowledge to STEM industry leadership and to existing research. The case study design allowed the researcher to create stories from the participants' perceptions to guide understanding of the phenomenon. The case study design is best suited when attempting to answer how, what, or why questions (Yin, 2018). Neuman (2011) explained researchers use qualitative case studies to find common themes. The case study was the best way to obtain the perceptions of leaders and former leaders concerning the underrepresentation of women in STEM leadership positions.

Research Questions

The following research questions were created for the case study to align with the purpose of the study, which was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions:

RQ1: What do female engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

RQ2: What do male engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

Population and Sample

In researchers' exploration for information that adds to the body of knowledge in respective fields, data is gathered from a group of individuals. The individuals share one or multiple characteristics of interest to the study (Asiamah et al., 2017). The group of

individuals are referred to as the research population. The population includes all the elements from a data set. The population guides the credibility of the sample, the selected sampling technique, and ultimately the outcome of the research (Asiamah et al., 2017). The population in this exploratory case study included all males and females in the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. Participants were chosen from organizations in the engineering industry that hire males and females and that reside in the Northeast region of the U.S. When conducting research, identified boundaries are necessary for researchers (Ridder, 2017). The research boundary included in this study was specific to the Northeast region of the U.S.

Sample

The research sample differs from the population. The sample is a subset of the population, a smaller group selected from the population. Qualitative and quantitative research follow protocols for selecting appropriate sample size and techniques. No clearly defined sample size for conducting qualitative research exists, and the topic of sample size appropriateness continues to be an area of conceptual debates (Blaikie, 2018; Vasileiou et al., 2018). Researchers use guidelines to help in determining appropriate sample size. Various factors are considered when deciding on the appropriate sample size in qualitative research, as it is impossible to know the appropriate sample size prior to beginning qualitative research (Blaikie, 2018). However, Vasileiou et al. (2018) believed sample sizes in qualitative researchers tend to be small and purposeful, allowing for greater efficiency and rich data collection, while Sim et al. (2018) believed there are distinctive approaches that may assist qualitative researchers determine appropriate sample sizes.

The use of the rule of thumb approach has been suggested by researchers to aid in determining sample size (DePaulo, 2000; Guest et al., 2006). Researchers use numerical guidelines and statistical formulae to help determine an appropriate sample size (Sim et al., 2018); however, Malterud et al. (2016) did not recommend researchers use formulae to determine sample size. Therefore, dependent on the research design, researchers may use the suggested number of participants from researchers' recommendations (Morse, 2000). For example, Creswell (2013) recommended 20–30 participants for a qualitative case study. Morse (2000) suggested approximately 30–60 participants when using semi-structured interviews. One group of authors believed it may require 50 or more participants to conduct quality data and analysis in interview studies (Sim et al., 2018).

Varying recommendations in the rule of thumb approach exhibits inconsistencies in an appropriate sample size using that approach. Implying sample size may be determined based on the aim of the study, nature of the topic, quality of data, and research design (Morse, 2000). Data saturation is a good way to determine when the sample size is achieved and is deemed appropriate (Malterud et al., 2016; Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). Daniel (2019a) believed the appropriate sample size is dependent on research schedule, resource availability and the objective of the study. Therefore, the initial sample size is the researchers' choice to make. The sample size for this qualitative exploratory case study was 30 participants or until data saturation was reached.

Sample Selection Process

Researchers find people and sites using various methods. Researchers may choose a method to identify and obtain participants and sites for the study depending on the nature of the study, the main research questions, and the research objectives. Researchers

identify the appropriate participants and site that suit the individual research before embarking on finding the people and places. Participant selection is achieved by applying inclusion and exclusion criteria (Killaw et al., 2014; Patino & Ferreira, 2018). For this qualitative exploratory case study, purposeful sampling followed by snowball sampling were selected.

Purposeful Sampling

Purposeful sampling was used based on the researcher's decision about the appropriate informants who will provide useful knowledge specific to the case (Babbie, 2010; Johnson et al., 2020). Given the focus of the research topic was on an event that is common in the industry, the researcher applied a systematic and organized approach in selecting study participants. The selection of participants from the engineering population was purposeful. Participants were selected from organizations that employ women in the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S.

After identifying organizations and obtaining the signed PRN forms, a research participant recruitment flyer was emailed to each organization's leadership for posting (see Appendix A). The purposeful sampling selection process helped the researcher ensure the participants were qualified to contribute enough appropriate data (Campbell et al., 2020). The participation inclusion criteria, purpose of the study, and researcher's contact information were included on the recruitment flyer. The sample included a total of 30 participants. The sample consisted of 15 males and 15 females who were leaders or former leaders in STEM engineering industry, in the Northeast region of the U.S. A stratified sample of two subgroups of males and females was used as two sources of interview data collection.

Snowball Sampling

Snowball sampling was used to augment participation recruitment efforts by seeking information from key personnel about other potential sources who possessed knowledge needed for the study (Johnson et al., 2020). Snowball sampling is used if insufficient responses are received from the purposeful sampling efforts. Each respondent to the recruitment invitation and all confirmed participants who signed the informed consent forms were asked to recommend additional individuals for participating in the study. Respondents were reminded of the interview inclusion criteria to narrow the field of potential informants to the individuals who were former or current leaders in the engineering industry and who were in the Northeast region of the U.S. Snowball sampling ended once data saturation was achieved.

Informed Consent and Confidentiality

As humans share stories, perceptions and experiences, ethical conduct becomes paramount. Ethical consideration is very important in research (Arifin, 2018; Rashid et al., 2019). Obtaining voluntary participation helps to eliminate intrusion into peoples' lives and protect the research participants; however, even with voluntary participation, anonymity and confidentiality should be guaranteed. Ethical concerns should be addressed for all research studies, specifically for research that involve human participation for data collection (Arifin, 2018).

Prior to study participation, prospective participants chose to voluntarily participate, and were provided adequate information to make the informed decision (Yin, 2018); however, pertinent researcher actions were required before recruiting human subjects for the study. Known organizations that employ females in the engineering

industry from the Northeast region of the U.S. were identified and four were selected to obtain permission for participant recruitment. Telephone contact was made to each organization's leaders to introduce the study purpose and request permission to recruit subjects for participation in this study. An email introducing the study topic and purpose and requesting permission to recruit was sent to each organization's regional leader (see Appendix B). The Premises, Recruitment, and Name (PRN) Use Permission Form was prepared and included in the email as an attachment that was sent to each organization's leader. Four signed PRN forms were returned via email from the identified facilities granting the researcher permission to recruit subjects for participation in the study. The PRN form was included in the IRB package.

Informed Consent

Using informed consent forms aided the researcher in protecting participants and provided each participant with written assurance of rights to decline or withdraw from participation in the study. Obtaining a signed informed consent form from each participant and to formally provide details of the study was important (Yin, 2018). For the current qualitative exploratory case study, the informed consent form was prepared after obtaining the signed PRN forms. The recommended IRB informed consent guidance and checklist document were used as guides to include the list of items required for this study. The informed consent form was emailed to each interested participant and the signed forms were returned prior to conducting interviews (see Appendix C).

Confidentiality

Researchers are required to consider participants' anonymity and confidentiality before and during the research process. Researchers guarantee confidentiality for

participants, which is addressed in the informed consent form (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). Confidentiality is one tool researchers use to protect human participants in qualitative research. Ensuring confidentiality is exercising respect for participants (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). In this study, participants' identity and data remained confidential. Once participation was agreed upon, each participant was assigned a pseudonym that was used for the entirety of the project. Participants were advised the interview sessions would be audio recorded and were asked before being interviewed to verbally grant permission to the researcher. The information received from the interview sessions were transcribed and the data coded to protect each participant's identity.

The confidentiality of the research participants and their organizations were maintained. Guaranteeing confidentiality in qualitative research is an ethical standard (Surmiak, 2018). The names of the participants or organizations were not mentioned or named in the dissertation document. A voice recorder was used during the interview, but participants' names were not used during the interview. The principal investigator (PI) who was also the researcher in this study, is the only person to have direct knowledge of each person's identity. All documents and research devices strictly utilized the participants' pseudonyms. Information obtained from the interview sessions was transcribed and the data coded to protect participants' identity. Data is kept secure in a locked drawer in the researcher's residence. Electronic files were kept on a password protected digital device. All paper files and audio recordings were destroyed as soon as data was transcribed, and member checked. Hard copy data was shredded, and audio recordings deleted from the recording device that was exclusively used for collecting interview data.

Instrumentation

Instrumentation is used to help researchers collect data (Hinds, 2002).

Researchers are the primary instrument in qualitative research and use tools or research instrumentation to help with the data collection process. Some of the tools used by researchers aid with data collection and include questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, observations, and diaries (Nassaji, 2020). For the qualitative exploratory case study, the research instrumentation included the researcher and interview questions.

The Role of the Researcher

The researcher is considered an instrument (Wa-Mbaleka, 2020). The researcher for this study was tasked with conducting or leading the research efforts through completion and presentation of the research findings. The researcher has experience working with women in the STEM industry and held multiple roles from entry level to leadership in STEM. The professional experiences have enhanced awareness and knowledge of the research topic. Researchers have influence in all phases of the research; how data are gathered, analyzed, and how the findings are presented (Tufford & Newman, 2012). Establishing boundaries are necessary and was used to assist in mitigating research bias. Santos et al. (2020) suggested researchers use triangulation to manage researcher bias. Importantly, adhering to ethical considerations and following all IRB guidelines specific to this case study aided the researcher to mitigate researcher bias. An ongoing process to continually self-evaluate for researcher bias was performed (Thurairajah, 2019).

Interview Questions

Interviews are a logical way for researchers to talk and listen to people to obtain and share information (De la Croix et al., 2018). One-on-one semistructured interviews with the sample participants were used to obtain participants' experiences and perceptions pertaining to the research topic. Semi-structured interviews are most appropriate when researchers want to use open-ended questions in a more relaxed and friendly setting and focus on the same theme in each interview session (De la Croix et al., 2018). The benefits of data obtained during qualitative interviews is dependent on the researcher's ability and the quality of the research questions (Roberts, 2020). Therefore, aligning the interview questions with the study's research questions was critical.

Instrumentation relevant to this case study, defined as interview question (see Appendix E) is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Interview and Research Questions Alignment

Research Questions	Corresponding Interview Questions
R1. What do female engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership?	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. How did you become interested in STEM? When did your STEM career begin?2. Describe your experience as a leader working in the STEM industry.3. What challenges, biases, or barriers (if any) did you encounter ascending to leadership role in STEM?4. Describe a time when you believe gender played a negative role in a female obtaining a leadership role in STEM?5. Describe a time when you believe gender played a negative role in a male obtaining a leadership role in STEM?6. What leadership competencies have you acquired that are necessary for a STEM leadership role?7. Is there anything else you would like to discuss or add regarding obstacles to career advancement in STEM?

Research Questions	Corresponding Interview Questions
R2: What do male engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Describe your promotion and tenure process in your current position. 2. Who do you feel contributed to your success achieving a leadership role? 3. What professional development opportunities have you had that contributed to your role? 4. What professional development opportunities or training do you feel will be beneficial for women who want to advance to leadership positions in STEM? 5. What do you think is contributing to the underrepresentation of women in STEM leadership positions? 6. Have you mentored women seeking leadership roles in STEM? 7. Do you think there is an ideal leadership prototype? If so, can you describe what leadership competencies are required for a STEM leadership role? 8. Is there anything else you would like to discuss or add regarding the facilitators of career progress to STEM leadership?

Note: The table identified two research questions and corresponding interview questions as developed by the researcher.

Field Test

Qualitative research uses the perceptions of participants and human reports as contributing components of collected data. Field testing in qualitative research helps researchers create reliable measures of cross-checking data (Babbie, 2010). Researchers conduct field tests before the real data collection phase begins (Hayashi et al., 2019). Field tests are used to help researchers determine if the interview questions are appropriate to effectively answer the research questions and to provide valid information on the research topic.

A field test was conducted for this qualitative exploratory case study to assist the researcher in determining if the instrumentation items, defined as interview questions, aligned with the research questions. Three subject matter experts (SMEs) received a copy

of the interview questions (see Table 1) to review and provide feedback pertaining to the clarity of the interview questions and if the interview questions would answer the research questions. For the field test and to protect the identity of the SMEs, the participants were referred to as Participant 1, Participant 2, and Participant 3. The participants were not included in the sample of the proposed study but were used to review the interview questions for clarity and comprehension.

The valuable feedback from the expert review panel were reviewed by the researcher, allowing for refinement and revisions to some of the interview questions. Participant 1 stated the questions were good provocative qualitative questions, but recommended rephrasing four of the questions for specificity and adding one additional question to disclose information pertaining to support practices in the engineering industry. The recommended changes were made and a question about the mentoring availability to women was added for RQ1. Participant 2 said the questions were appropriate to the context of the study but recommended revisions of two questions. Participant 3 stated the questions were appropriate for the context of the study and provided no additional feedback. The researcher reviewed the suggestions received and the recommended changes were discussed with the dissertation chair via Microsoft Teams. Subsequently, changes were made to RQ1 interview questions 3, 4, 5, and 6, and RQ2 interview questions 3, 4, and 7. The revised interview questions were used to collect data (a copy of the revised interview questions are attached as Appendix F). Performing field testing in qualitative research is beneficial. Testing instrumentation allowed for rigor and validity, and for simply checking for any potential problems (Brooks et al., 2016).

Credibility and Transferability

Researchers' knowledge of what is real may or may not correspond with the reality of the research participants. Suggesting there are multiple realities on a given topic when employing human subjects. Researchers utilize different strategies to achieve credibility and transferability, which is important (Amankwaa, 2016; Liao & Hitchcock, 2018). As researchers communicate with humans to access knowledge and then decipher received data, there are varying perceptions, allowing for challenges to constructing and communicating human's reality. For these reasons, researchers use different strategies to ensure obtained data is credible for communicating to others and for transferring to the body of knowledge.

Credibility

Conducting a member check or participant validation assists researchers in obtaining credibility to ensure the data and findings are real, replicable, and representative of what was collected (Birt et al., 2016; Daniel, 2019b; Korstjens & Moser, 2018). Hyett et al. (2014) suggested qualitative researchers use a checklist for asking pertinent questions for assessing quality. The checklist included questions such as, *Were sufficient raw data presented? Does the report have a conceptual structure? Is the report easy to read?* For this qualitative exploratory case study, a checklist was used as a guide to produce rigor and serves as an *audit trail*, which is a strategy researchers use to increase credibility of the data collection process (Liao & Hitchcock, 2018).

Triangulation and member checking are two other strategies that were used to establish credibility in the exploratory case study. Within one week of each interview, member checks consisted of communication with each participant after transcribing interview

data. Each participant was asked to verify written information for accuracy and to make changes if needed. The member checks were recorded and electronically filed, and the information used for data analysis.

Triangulation is critical to research credibility (Amankwaa, 2016; Daniel, 2019b). The triangulation process of employing multiple interview participants and obtaining CVs from each research participant were established to accomplish credibility. Collecting and analyzing data from varying and numerous participants helped the researcher determine if the information presented was adequate to support the assertions made pertaining to the underrepresentation of women in STEM leadership.

Transferability

Transferability is achieved in research when research results have pertinence to other context and is contributory to the body of knowledge (Daniel, 2019b; Korstjens & Moser, 2018). Thick description is an essential strategy for facilitating transferability (Amankwaa, 2016). Detailed information about every aspect of the research and its findings is presented to enable readers to determine the applicability of the research findings to other settings. Clear statements of the context of this study, including location setting, timeframe, detailed and rich information about the participants' experiences will aid readers to determine the transferability of the findings (Korstjens & Moser, 2018). Daniel (2019b) suggested researchers discuss delimitation of the research to attain transferability. The delimitation of this case study was clearly explained in Chapter 1. Importantly, open-ended interview questions were asked to each participant to solicit detailed and personal responses (Amankwaa, 2016). The findings of this case study are

transferable, will offer valuable information to other individuals, and serve as lessons learned to guide STEM industry leadership behaviors.

Data Collection

Researchers choose different data collection strategies to conduct research. The strategies include case study, interviews, focus groups, observations, surveys, and document analysis. The selected strategy must be appropriate for the research to help researchers answer the research questions. For example, qualitative researchers may use interview questions to obtain pertinent information to answer the research questions (Maxwell, 2018). Primary data collection is the first strategy researchers employ and secondary data is the strategy that follows.

In qualitative research, multiple and varying data collection strategies are used to add credibility to research results and for triangulation purposes (Maxwell, 2018). Interviews are a logical way of talking and listening to people to obtain and share information (De la Croix et al., 2018). In qualitative research, varying approaches to conducting interviews are used to communicate with the sample participants who can contribute knowledge to the study. Depending on the purpose of the study and the research questions, the researcher may choose to conduct a one-on-one interview using the semi-structured, open, or structured interview approach (De la Croix et al., 2018). Group interviews may also be used where researchers conduct interviews in groups rather than interacting individually with each individual participant.

Semistructured Interview

The primary source of data collection for this qualitative case study was semi-structured interviews with 30 leaders and former leaders strictly from STEM

organizations. PRN forms were obtained from four organizations granting permission to collect data. The selection of the potential participants was limited to leaders and former leaders who work or have worked in the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. A participant recruitment flyer (see Appendix A) requesting volunteers for the study was emailed to each organization's leadership for posting electronically on the organizations' intranet, employee resource sites, and physically in common locations accessible to employees. The researcher's contact information was included on the flyers for potential participants to directly contact via email to express interest for participation in the study. After receiving contact from potential volunteers, an individual email containing a copy of the solicitation flyer and the informed consent form (see Appendix C) were sent to each participant. Potential participants were asked to review, sign, and return the informed consent form prior to being interviewed.

The geographical separation of participants and researcher was challenging since participants were in several states in the Northeast region of the U.S. Depending on a participant's preference, interview sessions were conducted online and via the telephone to mitigate the geographical separation challenge. The researcher worked with each participant to schedule the interview based on the participant's availability. Interview time frames were proposed on Mondays to Fridays after 5 p.m. Eastern Standard Time and on weekend days. Once a mutually conducive date and time were confirmed, the researcher sent an email invitation to the participant. Each interview was scheduled for 60 minutes.

Participants were advised the interview sessions would be audio recorded and, before being interviewed, each participant was asked to provide verbal permission to

participate. Once participation was agreed upon, each participant was assigned a pseudonym that was used for the entirety of the project. The interview protocol in Appendix E was prepared and was used as a guide for the semi-structured interviews. Conducting audio recordings of the interview sessions was helpful to the researcher. The researcher played back the audio recordings to listen to exactly how questions were asked and answered. Audio recordings of each interview was transcribed and saved in a private folder on a personal computer. The transcriptions were also saved on an external drive to protect the data and serves as an alternate storage device should the files be lost on the personal computer.

Within one week of each interview session, participants were emailed copies of the audio recording transcript to review for accuracy. Participants had the opportunity to correct any inaccurate or misrepresented content. The audio recordings and electronic and paper data copies were destroyed once the data was member checked. Participants were asked to return comments within one week after receipt of the transcriptions. Participants were advised if comments were not provided within the requested 1-week deadline, it would be assumed no further updates were needed. Member checking increases credibility of the research findings (Birt et al., 2016; Daniel, 2019b; Korstjens & Moser, 2018).

Documentation

Curriculum vitae (CVs) were used as the secondary data collection method for the exploratory case study. Documents and artifacts are used to compliment data collected from interviews and it is relevant to case study topics (Yin, 2018). Within one week after receiving contact from potential participants, email correspondence was sent to the

individuals advising persons current CVs are requested and were electronically collected via email communication from each individual either at the time of the interview or prior to the interview session. CVs were used to help with triangulation of the collected data.

Participants' identity and data remained confidential. Ensuring participants' confidentiality was necessary for establishing respect for participants (Tavakol & Sandars, 2014). Once the CVs were received, each participant was assigned a pseudonym that was used for the entirety of the project. Hard copies of CVs were kept in a locked and secured file drawer at the researcher's residence, where only the researcher had access. Electronic copies of CVs were saved and stored on the researcher's personal laptop that was password protected and only accessible by the researcher. All hard copies were shredded, and electronic copies deleted from all devices once the data collected from the CVs were entered in NVivo for analysis. The collected CVs were used solely for this study.

Parameters were not placed on the type of CVs or its content to be collected, allowing for the collection of immense information diversity. The information on the CVs provided the researcher with abundant information about each participant. Data on domains such as number of years in leadership, number of leadership positions held, participation in professional organizations, and level of education was expected to be obtained from each participant's CV. Themes from each CV were extracted and coded. CVs were used to help the researcher with triangulation of the collected interview data. Employing different sources of data such as archival sources was useful in achieving triangulation (Fusch et al., 2018)

Data Analysis

Moving from data collection to data analysis requires information obtained be examined and explained. Yin (2018) explained the collected data in a qualitative study is significant and should be carefully examined. Data analysis is a process of deconstructing and separating the raw collected data. Qualitative researchers can choose to manually analyze data or employ data analysis software. Case study is time consuming because of data coding and data analysis, specifically the coding process requires extensive time (Campbell, 2015). The researcher chose to effectively manage time, remain focused on the study, and became knowledgeable of skills required for data coding to effectively address the challenge.

Before data analysis, the data in the case study was organized and filed for easy access and review. Data analysis involves preparing and organizing collected data, then shrinking the collected data into themes with the use of codes and then displaying the data in figures, tables, or discussions (Creswell, 2013). Reviewing the data allowed for general knowledge of the collected contents. The data analysis procedure was primarily inductive requiring the researcher to continuously be engaged in the data to derive at theories. Having various strategies to analyze data in qualitative research design is helpful since data is largely dependent on human's perceptions of what is real.

Data Coding

Coding is one of the first steps in the data analysis process. Saldana and Omasta (2018) said coding is a process which transitions from data collection to data analysis. Coding is one of the main data analysis method used in qualitative studies (Rashid et al., 2019). Therefore, interview transcripts from notes were read line by line and coded into

the computer-assisted software, NVivo, to aid in data analysis of the interview responses. The software program was used to assist with the organization of data, especially for extensive interview transcriptions. Information from the CV data were reviewed and uploaded in the NVivo software for coding, theme generation, and then analyzed. The aim is to identify codes and themes, and any related subcodes, categories, and subcategories. Data collection may be extensive depending on the sample size, therefore placing codes to meaningful subsections of information was helpful to easily generate patterns or relations among what had been collected.

Playing with the data or testing the codes more than once is recommended (Yin, 2018). Saldana and Omasta (2018) explained codifying or coding and recording the data follow the initial coding activity; therefore, the practice of coding was done several times to get various codes into the data sets. Saldana and Omasta further recommended three rounds of coding. Thus, for this case study, during the first review of the data, the researcher highlighted words or phrases that seemed important. During the second read through of the data the researcher wrote a brief memo of personal perceptions of what was said. Finally, descriptive coding was done by assigning labels to a chunk of the participants' words. The researcher constantly went back to examine the interview and CV data for more keywords or phrases. Any newly identified ideas or codes were added in NVivo.

Thematic Analysis

Codes were sorted into themes. Thematic analysis process was used to help researcher structure collected data and to identify main themes. Emerging themes derived from coding was examined. Identified themes were reviewed and the initial codes

categorized into broader themes. Reviewing themes was useful to help the researcher identify any contradictions or overlaps of the codes. If there were multiple contradictions or overlaps with a theme, the theme was split in a separate code. The completed codes were combined into broader headings and placed into associated groups. Attention was paid to commonalities of any identified themes (Leedy & Ormond, 2018). Condensing the information collected into sections and assigning names for each section was beneficial when identifying themes and patterns (Creswell, 2013).

NVivo software was useful for assisting researcher with the data analysis of generating themes and sorting codes to appropriately fit into the various themes. Coding and generating themes are the main data analysis method used in qualitative studies (Rashid et al., 2019). Codes were established in relationship with the two research questions, literature review dimensions, and problem statement. Themes emerged based on NVivo software capabilities. A report was prepared, and word frequencies were used to clearly present the results and analysis of the case study.

Triangulation of Data

Different sources of data are important to achieve triangulation. For example, a combination of interviews with multiple participants and archival sources are appropriate methods used to increase the credibility and validity of research findings (Fusch et al., 2018). For this study, triangulation was achieved with analysis of interview responses and CV documents. Semistructured interview questions were directed to 30 participants who were STEM professionals and who were employed or previously employed in the engineering industry, and who hold or held leadership positions in the Northeast region of the U.S. Data collection included archival records in the form of CVs from each

participant. Archival records and documentation were used for triangulation with the interviews. Using the CVs as archival documentation was an integral document used for triangulation and to provide a succinct professional history of each interview participant and add knowledge of some of the main facilitators of career progress.

The selected data sources were used for conducting the research differently with alternate options. Having various strategies to analyze data in qualitative research is helpful since data is largely dependent on humans' perceptions of what is real. Triangulation was used as a validation strategy, to address researcher bias and to help ensure reliability and validity of the data interpretations (Santos et al., 2020). Finally, the analysis of the collected data is presented (Yin, 2018).

Chapter Summary

Women encounter barriers to attaining leadership positions and are highly underrepresented in leadership (Fox et al., 2019; Griffiths et al., 2019; Kossek & Buzzanell, 2018). In Chapter 3, a discussion on the appropriate research method and design selected for this study were reviewed. The qualitative approach was chosen for this study because of the social nature of the research problem and to gather in-depth data to understand the phenomenon from the participants' perceptions and experiences (Hancock & Algozzine, 2017). Case study was selected as an appropriate research design because it is a method of inquiring used to investigate an event affecting specific participants (Yin, 2018). The purpose of current qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions.

Stratified sample size of 15 males and 15 females from the engineering population in the Northeast region of the U.S. was established. The geographic location of the research study was identified with detailed information about the interview location. Using purposeful add snowball sampling, 30 participants shared perceptions during semi-structured interviews and each participants provided a CV. The selected data sources were used for conducting the research differently with alternate options, and was useful when achieving triangulation (Fusch et al., 2018). Case study is time consuming because of data coding and data analysis, specifically the coding process requires extensive time (Campbell, 2015). Therefore, NVivo computer assisted software was selected and utilized to aid with data analysis.

Participants' confidentiality was maintained. Informed consent documents were provided to each participant and appropriate research protocols were followed. Multiple strategies were used to enable credibility and transferability in the study (Amankwaa, 2016; Liao & Hitchcock, 2018). Member checking and triangulation were strategies utilized in the current study. The instrumentation of interview and role of the researcher were considered to mitigate research biases. Chapter 3 provided a detailed description of the process, procedures, methods, and steps taken during the exploratory case study. The analysis of the types of evidence to collected were discussed in the data analysis section. Chapter 4 will present the research results from data collection and analysis. Chapter 4 will include a detailed description of the data, and the data collection and analysis processes. Details collected from the semi-structured interviews and CV data sources will be presented as results, in a manner that align the two research questions with the themes that emerged during the study.

Chapter 4

Analysis and Results

The purpose of the qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Three sources of data were used to support the case study and to ensure the purpose of the study was achieved. Thirty participants who are employed or were previously employed in the engineering industry, and who hold or held leadership positions in the Northeast region of the U.S. were recruited to participate in semistructured interviews. A stratified sample of two subgroups of fifteen males and fifteen females was used as two sources of interview data. Archival records in the form of a CV from each participant were used to supplement interviews. CV documents were used for triangulation and served to provide insight into how participants presented themselves professionally and showed examples of personal knowledge and accomplishments. Chapter 4 contains six sections: (a) research questions, (b) data collection, (c) demographics, (d) data analysis, (e) results, and (f) summary.

Research Questions

The following research questions align with the purpose and problem statements of this qualitative exploratory case study:

RQ1: What do female engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

RQ2: What do male engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

Data Collection

Prior to beginning any data collection, the University of Phoenix IRB approval was obtained. The selection of the potential participants was limited to leaders and former leaders who work or worked in the engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. A participant recruitment flyer (see Appendix A) requesting volunteers for the study was emailed to leaders in each organization for posting electronically on the organizations' intranet and employee resource sites, and physically in common locations accessible to employees. After receiving contact from potential volunteers, an individual email containing the Informed Consent form (see Appendix C) was sent to each participant. Potential participants were asked to review, sign, and return the Informed Consent form (see Appendix C) prior to being interviewed. Research participants were reminded in the initial contact and prior to the interview sessions of the rights associated with human participation research. The Informed Consent form (see Appendix C) detailed (a) the study's purpose, (b) voluntary participation statement, (c) study's protocols and procedures, (d) principal investigator's contact information, and (e) limitations to participant's privacy and confidentiality. All interested participants expressed support and interest to contribute to the research and said the research problem was important.

Signed Informed Consent forms (see Appendix C) were collected from each participant before conducting interviews. The interviews were semistructured interviews with 30 leaders and former leaders strictly from STEM organizations. The semistructured interview protocol was used to guide the interviews using a separate set of questions for

males and females. The interviews took place from May 11, 2022, to July 1, 2022. The duration of each interview was approximately 20 minutes.

CVs were used as a different source than the two subgroups of interviews for data triangulation. CVs were requested in the email invitation sent to each participant. All participants provided a personal CV. Data collected from the interviews and CVs were coded alphanumerically to protect each participant's identity and for confidentiality. Thirty interview sessions were audio recorded and the collected data were transcribed using NVivo. The audio recorded data was deleted after transcription. The interview transcriptions were reviewed for grammatical errors. Copies of the transcriptions were returned to the participants for member checking. Only four participants returned the transcribed data with corrections. The received updates were accepted, changes incorporated, and the revised interview transcriptions used for data analysis. Valuable information was shared relating to perceived obstacles to women's career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Participants shared additional information related to organizational and leadership changes to address and minimize the gender gap in leadership.

Demographics

All research participants (N = 30) met the inclusion criteria for the study. The sample included a total of 30 males and females. The sample was 15 males and 15 females who are leaders or former leaders in the STEM engineering industry in the Northeast region of the U.S. Participants' ages ranged from 35 years to 54 years. A stratified sample of two subgroups of males and females was used as two sources of interview data collection. The selection of participants from the engineering population

was purposeful. Purposeful sampling was used to deliberately select the study participants. Participants were selected from organizations that employed women in STEM professions. Secondly, snowball sampling was used to augment participant recruitment efforts by seeking information from key personnel about other potential sources who possessed knowledge needed for the study. Table 2 displays participants' demographic characteristics by age, gender, levels of educational, and employment status.

Table 2

Demographic Characteristics

Demographic	<i>n</i>	%	Range
Age	30	100	35 - above 54
Gender			
Male	15	50%	
Female	15	50%	
Levels of education			
High school	30	100%	
Associates degree	1	3%	
Bachelors	14	47%	
Masters	14	47%	
Doctoral	1	3%	
Employment status			
Full-time	27	90%	
Part-time	1	3%	
Unemployed	1	7%	

Data Analysis

Semistructured interviews and archival document in the form of a CV were the data collected to bind this case study. Before data analysis, data was organized and filed for easy access and review. Data analysis involved preparing and organizing collected data, then shrinking the collected data into themes with the use of codes, and then

displaying the data on tables. Information collected from audio recordings were compared with NVivo software's transcription data to validate the information and identify noticeable discrepancies. Field notes taken during the interview data collection phase were reviewed and compared with the audio interviews and transcripts. The data analysis procedure was primarily inductive requiring the researcher to be continuously engaged in the data to derive at themes.

Coding Strategy

Manual coding was one of the first steps in the data analysis process. During the first review of the data, words or phrases that seemed important were highlighted. The highlighted words or phrases were the initial codes applied to the data. Several preliminary codes emerged from the interview transcriptions based on characteristics; 780 and 735 initial codes for males and females, respectively. The preliminary codes were then reduced to 671 and 613 for males and females, respectively. Descriptive coding was done by assigning labels to a chunk of the participants' words. Descriptive coding is a short phrase, usually a noun, and assigned topic to the qualitative data. Data was reviewed multiple times to examine the interview data for more keywords or phrases. Playing with the data or testing the codes more than once is recommended; therefore, the practice of coding was done several times to get various codes into the data sets.

The interview transcripts were uploaded into NVivo software to be further coded for the identification of themes, trends, and patterns. Interview and CV files were entered into NVivo software individually. Each research question was assigned level one headings: RQ1 was labeled as female codes and RQ2 was labeled as male codes. Codes were established in relationship with the two research questions, literature review

dimensions, and problem statement. Coded data were reexamined multiple times to help establish trustworthiness.

Theme Analysis

NVivo software was utilized for assisting with the data analysis of generating themes and sorting codes to appropriately fit into the various themes. The thematic analysis was inductive, and codes emerged from the transcripts during the analysis process. Thematic analysis process was used to guide how collected data was analyzed and resulted in six main themes. Emerging themes derived from coding was examined. Identified themes were reviewed and the initial codes categorized into broader themes. Reviewing themes was useful for identifying any contradictions or overlaps of the codes. Attention was paid to commonalities of any identified themes. Condensing the information collected into sections and assigning names for each section was useful for identifying themes and patterns. NVivo software was useful for assisting with the data analysis of generating themes and sorting codes to appropriately fit into the various themes. The appropriate themes emerged based on NVivo software capabilities. NVivo is the computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software designed for directly coding themes in digital files and for thematic analysis.

CVs were used for data triangulation and provided rich information about the participants' career histories. Thematic analysis was also used to code CV data for the 30 research participants. The CVs were individually imported to the NVivo software for the identification of previously established categories believed to provide succinct professional history of each interview participant and add integral information of some of the main facilitators of career progress. Four categories included information regarding

the participants' years in leadership, number of leadership positions held, participation in professional organizations, and levels of education were obtained from the CVs.

Triangulation enhanced the rigor of the study by improving the trustworthiness and credibility of interview data.

Results

The research results were based on the information provided by the participants and triangulated with data from CV documentation. Presentation of the study's results were organized into themes. Themes of the interview are presented first, followed by the themes from the CVs. A total of six themes emerged from the interview data analysis, three for the female participants and three for the male participants. Research results and relationship to the research questions, with supporting quotes from the participants are discussed below.

Research Question 1

RQ1 was asked to explore the obstacles perceived by female STEM leaders and former leaders in the engineering industry. A total of three themes emerged from the analysis showing females' experiences being STEM leaders in the engineering field. Most participants perceived a lack of career advancement opportunities, and the majority of females perceived hurdles from management practices which resulted in women working harder to ascend to leadership positions. The results of RQ1 were organized by three themes: (a) leadership competencies and experiences, (b) barriers and experience of men in leadership role, and (c) early interest and encouragement are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

RQ1 Themes

Themes	Files	References
Barriers and experience with men in leadership	15	222
Leadership competencies and experiences	15	251
Early interest and encouragement	15	95

Theme 1: Barriers and Experience with Men in Leadership

Female leaders shared several factors perceived as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. The first female emergent theme was barriers and experiences with men in leadership. According to the participants, women experience the obstacle because of gender and lack of resources. Participant F11 shared that the engineering field is male dominated, making it difficult for women to get accepted. Participant F11 also said the credibility of information shared by women was questioned and only accepted once confirmed by a male colleague. Participant F11 spoke openly about a personal experience when gender and age were the subject of a joke, and stated:

I think that the biggest obstacle was fighting against the perception that women may not know everything or that the information needs to be verified or confirmed. And then, as soon as I was able to confirm that information with a male peer, the information was accepted and was never a question.

Females experienced difficulties because of gender and constant objections from management. Participant F5 shared similar comments about the challenges of being a female. Participant F5 said:

Many believed women will do anything to earn a promotion and are easily

exploited. Even back in that day, that was when people were becoming much more aware of biases, like a woman excelling then that maybe she was willing to do a lot more personal things. Kind of like dating your way to the top was a conversation at the time.

Participant F6 believed individuals had a perceived image of the role being performed by gender, making it difficult for women to be accepted in some roles because women were perceived as fragile. Participant F6 stated, “There is a certain picture, I think, that people have in their minds about what a safety manager or a construction manager looks like and not being female and being also very petite too.” Participant F12 said it was difficult to get respect from colleagues because of gender. Participant F12 stated, “It’s just getting a little bit better, but it is still tough in the beginning. Like nobody will kind of respect you. You have to work very hard to show.” Women’s abilities were underestimated, and leadership skills were questioned because of gender and femininity.

Women lacked resources to enhance soft and technical skills and did not have a female mentor or role model who could support career advancement endeavors. In addition, women of childbearing age did not get proper support. Participant F13 felt taking time away from work because of an expanding family was one of the biggest challenges in a woman’s career, and experienced lack of supported during maternity leave and worked more to cover the knowledge gap upon return to work. Participant F13 stated, “I think the toughest barrier I face as a woman is taking time away from work and then trying to catch back up.” Under the same concept, Participant F7 believed the lack of

resources made it difficult to master skills and get the support when needed. Participant F7 stated:

It was a little bit of a struggle at first, because I did not have support. The lack of resources early on and on the soft side of things. So, not even just like client relationships or business development or that sort of thing, but like, project management skills and team leadership skills. And I have never had a formal mentor or formal mentor relationship set up.

Women perceived lack of resources as a contributory barrier experienced with male in leadership positions. Women encountered career barriers with men dominating leadership.

Theme 2: Leadership Competencies and Experiences

Leadership competencies and experiences emerged as the second theme for RQ1. Communication skills, emotional intelligence, collaboration, ability to help people grow, good knowledge, and management skills were the most desirable characteristics of a leader. Participant F5 believed men had good communication skills and could easily interact with others. Participant F5 stated, “Men are really good at it, kind of saying a lot of words, but never really saying anything in particular.” According to Participant F4, a leader needs to understand followers’ differences in personalities to utilize abilities. Participant F4 stated, “So definitely the ability to mentor and coach and have a lot of patience and empathy and understanding of different personalities and how to work with them to get the best out of their abilities.” Participant F9 also emphasized the importance of understanding employees and reported:

I think one of the most important one is to be able to know that you are leading one smart people, so understanding of individuals. Some people by nature are not one-size-fits-all. Everybody comes with a different skill, comes with a different competence.

Female participants believed leaders have diverse skills and experiences, which allows for ability to effectively relate to others. Participant F11 emphasized the significance of a leader's knowledge and complete grasp of the field. The information related to the field be readily available by a leader to be utilized when needed. Participant F11 stated, "So making sure that they, the individual, is very familiar with their book of knowledge, making sure that they could go back and reference that information readily." Participant F14 explained that the ideal leader has decision-making power, compassion, and the ability to admit mistakes and quickly rectify errors. Participant F14's ideal leadership included, "Someone who can make a decision, someone who has compassion for the people he is leading, someone who is not afraid to make a mistake." Participant F11 shared women had to consistently clear doubts, thus having high self-efficacy.

Women struggled to prove themselves as leaders and to be self-confident. Participant F11 stated, "So there seems to be doubt, and you almost have to reassure and establish yourself as a trusted leader for some time before people are willing to take confidence in you." Participant F3 wanted to learn more to achieve career success and stated, "Success as a leader requires commitment, time, and effort. I think just that drive to succeed and always want to do better and better yourself and better your company and better the people you work with." Women were challenged to establish themselves as trusted leaders, be confident in personal abilities, search for different mentors to learn

new skills, have success drive, and have the required training to improve knowledge to attain leadership positions.

Theme 3: Early Interests and Encouragement

Female participants shared different experiences leading to careers in STEM-related field, including a passion for science, early STEM awareness, and being influenced by someone. Participant F9 was always interested in science and stated, “I always had an inclination in the sciences, so that is what I specialized in and then went into civil engineering as my undergraduate degree.” Early awareness piqued Participant F13’s interest in STEM. Participant F13 stated, “In high school, I did a program at RPI Technical College, and that introduced me to all different types of engineering studies.” Participant F8 always had an aptitude for STEM since childhood and stated, “My first thought was when I was two years old, my father left out for work, my mother was busy, and I took a screwdriver and removed the back from our TV.” Early awareness and interest in STEM academia positively influenced some participants’ decisions to pursue careers in various STEM related fields.

Female participants shared opinions about what may lead to encouragement of younger women into a STEM field. Participant F15 believed there was insufficient awareness about the engineering field, and women were unaware of its content, making it difficult for women to pursue STEM careers. Participant F15 stated, “I think the problem generally is that you don’t have a lot of people, they do not really know about engineering.” Participant F7 shared similar sentiments and recommended early advocacy for STEM because females were unaware of the potential STEM offers. Participant F7 stated:

Trying to be encouraged at the younger level really is one way to make sure that girls understand the opportunities that are there and that being an engineer does not mean you just sit in a stuffy little cubicle and do your computer stuff all day.

You have opportunities to get outside of that and be a leader.

Although biases and cultural norms have been changing, some women remain uninterested in STEM. Information about STEM related career options is recommended for encouraging younger women into a STEM field.

CV documents utilized in the triangulation detailed convergent information related to females' interest in STEM. Information obtained from the CVs indicated few of the female participants started early STEM educational preparation or careers. Participant F2 was initially interested in business and pursued a bachelor's degree in global business, then switched to accounting, before finally completing bachelor and master's degrees in accounting. Women are hindered from pursuing STEM careers without early awareness of STEM education and are not encouraged or empowered to engage in STEM careers.

Research Question 2

RQ2 asked to explore the obstacles for women's career advancement perceived by male STEM leaders and former leaders in the engineering industry. A different set of semistructured interview questions were directed to the subset containing 15 male participants. A total of three themes emerged from the 15 interviews with males in the industry. The analysis revealed that males perceived cultural and societal norms, and barriers in women's career advancements to STEM leadership positions. They also supported women engineers and recommended women join professional organizations to enhance career growths. Men believed organizational culture was shifting, and women's

participation had recently increased. Men shared personal contributing factors to career successes. The results from RQ2 were organized by the three themes and are presented in Table 4: (a) support opportunities and hindrances in women’s careers, (b) woman leadership characteristics and development process, and (c) personal and other factors in success.

Table 4

RQ2 Themes

Themes	Files	References
Support opportunities and hindrances in women’s career	15	273
Woman leadership characteristics and development process	15	239
Personal and other factors in success	15	116

Theme 4: Support Opportunities and Hindrances in Women’s Careers

All male leaders shared opinions on what was perceived as obstacles to women’s career advancement in the engineering industry and proposed various reasons. Men agreed STEM is a male-dominated industry making it difficult for women to join. Cultural norms, the stigma associated with the field, stereotypes and biases against women, lack of diversity, and simply being a woman were some hindrances to women’s careers. Participant M8 shared culture wanted a man in leadership positions, and women faced difficulty getting acceptance as a leader. Participant M8 stated, “I think there is a culture that still pushes men to be the leaders.” Participant M1 believed because men have been in the field for a long time, there is a formed culture that rejects women and is harmful to women’s personal and professional growth. Participant M1 stated, “I think a lot of that has to do with longstanding engineering business environment cultural restrictions that I feel are unnecessary and damage business and personal growth.”

Participant M9 stated that “Different expectations placed upon women in terms of what their life path looked like made it difficult for women to go beyond the expectations of the implicit leadership prototype.” Cultural norms, the stigma associated with the field, stereotypes and biases against women, lack of diversity, and simply being a woman were some hindrances to women’s careers.

Participant M2 stated, “People are not ready for change, especially people with old mindsets, since STEM was always a male-dominated industry.” Participant M7 believed there was stigma associated with women being in the STEM fields in the past two decades and stated, “In this day and age where, I am not going to say that that did not exist 20 years ago with the older generation you know this is man’s work or something like that.” Participant M6 believed women’s unawareness of STEM education led to more men in the field and a lack of diversity. Participant M6 said:

Math and the STEM fields were not a focus for women. I think it is based on their Historical. I guess the lack of focus on women in STEM that has led to where we are with discrepancies that we have today.

Participant M4 believed being a female was a major hindrance to start a career in a male-dominated field. Participant M4 stated, “Too shocking to learn it, to see it in action and where women would be interviewed, and they would leave, and the bosses would talk about them, not as engineers, but as women.” Gender stereotypes and biases against women were hindrances to women’s career trajectories to leadership.

Participant M8 believed interest in STEM should start from the school level, and women’s willingness to take STEM courses would lead to more women joining the industry in future. Participant M8 stated, “It starts when you are in high school and

college, and part one is how many women really want to get into the field.” Participant M10 believed more work was needed to include diversity and stressed the importance of addressing the biases related to age in the industry. Participant M10 stated:

There is more work that needs to be done. I think when you sit around a boardroom table and look at the participants, we could no longer and should no longer be dominated by old males. And the subject could get even more complex beyond male female and could also involve age.

Females’ early awareness and interests to STEM are contributory to STEM career selections. Importantly, shift in cultural norms to include diversity in STEM is important when addressing the perceived biases in the industry.

All male participants believed women should join professional organizations to enhance STEM career opportunities. Participant M1 encouraged women to join a professional organization and believed women should join because more men are in these organizations, indicating a lack of diversity. Participant M1 stated, “Women working in the engineering workplace should be encouraged to become involved in professional organizations as many have a high percentage of male participation.” Participant M6 believed the Woman Transportation Seminar was an excellent opportunity for women because they provide professional support. Participant M6 added “I think that they do a tremendous job of providing training, providing opportunity, counseling, and mentorship.” Participant M11 believed joining a professional organization was always beneficial and leads to *professional development* and is “Rewarding in some way, shape or form.” Women’s involvement in professional organizations may facilitate mentorship, training, and counseling opportunities for enhancing career development.

Theme 5: Woman Leadership Characteristics and Development Process

Leadership positions were attained from hard work, by actively searching for opportunities, or by being asked to be in leadership roles by colleagues and supervisors. Participant M15 transitioned into a new position with the “help of his boss, allowing the latitude to develop those leadership skills.” Participant M8 shared “success in business development and project management were the reasons for ascending to the current leadership position.” Participant M9 said progression to leadership happened in milestones, and stated:

I am currently the director of civil engineering here at a small civil and environmental firm. My hire date as the leader of the civil group was in April of 2019. Prior to that, I was an assistant group leader for a large engineering firm. That position was, I do not know, three years, I believe, and before that, a project manager and a civil engineer starting in 1999. So, my progression into this role has been through a series of milestones or positions, if you will. Over a 20-year period.

Participant M1 said qualifications and 32 years of experience were reasons for the current leadership position attained, and stated, “my promotion was based on my time and qualifications in my field which include management, engineering, technical design, and construction on major projects, and I was deemed qualified for my current position.”

Participant M2 underwent an annual evaluation process consisting of feedback and employee performance and when “opportunities come up,” companies “promote those best qualified.” Leadership development was a process, with many male participants ascending to leadership over many years.

Seven participants (47%) believed there is no ideal leadership prototype; every leader is different, and every profession needs different leadership characteristics. Participant M7 believed leadership is situational because “as a leader, you need to be dynamic in that the situation is going to change. You know how you lead one person may not be how you need to lead another person.” Participant M3 also explained that there are flexible characteristics of leadership and stated, “I do not think there is one type or one characteristic that provides or will guarantee a leadership position or being successful at it.” However, two male participants believed there was an ideal leadership prototype and shared individual perceptions of leadership. Participant M5 believed that a leader should be “democratic.” Participant M12 stated, “I think leadership in any service area requires someone having the ability to listen.” Leaders have unique characteristics.

While some male participants said there were no distinct leadership prototypes, individual characteristics were described that contributed to good leadership. Participant M2 said “A good leader is going to allow people to develop and to change career paths and help them and guide them to what that person wants to achieve within their career.” According to Participant M8, a leader will “Come and make themselves present and available to their staff and show them well with empathy and courage.” Most male leaders had many years of experience in STEM, ranging from 10 to 38 years. Years of experience, leadership characteristics, work ethics, available opportunities, and support received from other male colleagues positively contributed to men’s leadership development.

Theme 6: Personal and Other Factors in Success

Male participants shared personal factors believed to have contributed to career successes, including having mentors, available opportunities and support, and investment in personal development and involvements. Participant M6 said “I had very good mentors” and was given “a chance and an opportunity” for success. Participant M7 shared mentors was helpful to career success. Participant M7 stated, “I started off in the field as an employee, and I was just fortunate enough to have very good mentors along the way.” Participant M1 had “Excellent staff and management support, positive client feedback and overall experience, and strong family support” as contributory success factors. Participant M14 explained “So there was a lot of midlevel managers, coworkers and even senior management that helped me along the way too. Those are some good drivers.” Mentor relationships, available opportunities and support positively influenced males’ career successes.

Male participants suggested different paths to careers advancement, including training for managers, asking job-related questions, improving diversity in organizations, investing in employees, and understanding the importance of motivation of employees. Participant M11 stated, “Nothing wrong facilitating your career” and “keep asking questions.” Participant M1 believed staff should be provided opportunities and financial support from existing management to facilitate career advancements. Participant M1 stated:

I think to facilitate staff career development, there needs to be opportunity, but

there also needs to be support from existing management and financial. By investing in STEM, a firm can better achieve diversity and balance across executive levels of management.

Supportive organizational culture may facilitate career advancements. Hard work, education, experience, drive for success, persistence, work ethics, and beneficial personality characteristics were cited as other success factors. Participant M11 credited personal desires to succeed and said, “hard worker” was an important success factor. Participant M4 believed for success, one has “to keep working at it hard.” Participant M6 believed qualification contributed as one of the biggest reasons, along with “work ethic and my education are factors. I went to further with my education, so that was a big factor.” Participant M12 said “I was able to learn.” Participant M8 said “the combination of having some mentors and doing my homework really helped tremendously.” Personal factors including investment in personal development are pathways for women’s career advancement. Education, experience, self-efficacy, and organizational support are important factors for career growth.

Curriculum Vitae

The information on the CVs provided rich information about each participant. CVs were collected and analyzed for each of the 30 participants. CV data were analyzed and utilized for triangulation with the interview data. Parameters were not placed on the types of CVs requested, so there was diversity among them. Four domains were consistent with each document. Data on domains included number of years in leadership, number of leadership positions held, participation in professional organizations, and levels of education were obtained from each participant’s CV.

Years in Leadership

Each CV document was reviewed to find the first identified leadership experience of each participant. Leadership experiences were noted on individual CVs using words such as *manager, director, vice president, president, and department leads*. Male and female participants had extensive years of experience working in the STEM fields. Females' STEM work experiences ranged from a minimum of 10 years to a maximum of 34 years—a difference of 24 years. Males' STEM work experiences ranged between a minimum of 10 years to a maximum of 40 years—a difference of 30 years. Females did not always document the number of years in leadership. Participant F7 held multiple positions and was a senior consulting manager, but the current leadership position was not detailed on the CV.

Levels of Education

Female participants and male participants had different levels of education. Participants' levels of education ranged from high school diploma, bachelor's degrees, master's degrees, and a doctoral degree. One male, Participant M7, held the lowest level of education, which was a high school diploma. Participant F9 was the only participant who obtained a doctoral degree. Males and females had various levels of educational qualifications including bachelor's degrees in civil engineering, advertising, construction, civil engineering, and environmental science; master's degrees in accounting, arts, civil engineering, public health, and business administration; and a doctoral degree in transportation engineering. Participants' levels of education are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Male and Female Educational Level

Level of Education	Males	Females
Diplomas	1	N/A
Bachelors	9	8
Masters	6	6
Above Masters	N/A	1

Number of Leadership Positions Held

CV data provided a career timeline for each participant. The number of leadership positions provided in each CV were not always consistent with verbal explanations of participants' career history. Female leaders held different leadership roles during their careers, with the 15 female leaders collectively holding 180 positions. Participant F3 had the highest of 29 career positions, steadily ascended to leadership and has been the president of an organization for 4 years. Male leaders collectively held 258 career positions. Participant M11 had over 38 years total experience and 5 leadership career positions. Participant M3 reported in the interview having a career expanding more than 30 years with various leadership positions including assignment manager, project manager, and program manager. Written document was inconsistent with the verbal information provided, detailing fewer leadership positions held over a 20-year period.

Participation in Professional Organizations

The CVs of 12 female leaders listed affiliations with different professional organizations. Participant F1 was associated with two professional organizations during her career. Participant F14 had participated in 10 different organizations, including American Council of Engineering Companies (ACEC) and American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO). Seven male leaders reported

affiliations with professional organizations. Participant M1 reported in the interview that he was associated with various professional organizations and had leadership roles. Participant M1 documented involvement in 11 professional organizations. Verbal information was consistent with information provided on the CV.

Chapter Summary

Chapter 4 included data collection, data analysis, a presentation of research results based on perceptions shared by 30 interview participants, and the CV document utilized for data triangulation. The data analysis was based on exploring the perceptions of male and female leaders and former leaders in the engineering industry as they pertained to females' accession to leadership positions in the STEM field. A qualitative exploratory case study was selected because it allowed the participants to share key insights as to the gender imbalance in STEM leadership positions. Purposeful and snowball sampling were used because the researcher studied a specific group of participants who was believed to have the knowledge and experience relevant to the study. There were 15 males and 15 females who agreed to participate in the study, and each participated in semistructured interview sessions and provided a CV. The responses to the interview questions provided an in-depth understanding from the males' and females' perspectives of obstacles females encounter in attaining STEM leadership positions, specifically in the engineering industry. The data analysis revealed three themes for each research question directed to male and female participants. Six themes emerged: *(a) barriers and experiences with men in leadership; (b) leadership competencies and experiences; (c) early interests and encouragement; (d) support opportunities and hindrances in women's careers; (e) woman leadership characteristics and development process; and (f) personal and other*

factors in success. Results of the study revealed women encountered and continue to experience multiple obstacles in advancement to leadership in the STEM industry.

Chapter 5 discussions will connect the results to existing literature presented in Chapter 2, and conceptual frameworks focusing on self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1997) and the implicit leadership theory (Lord & Maher, 1984). The research results are discussed in the next chapter. The recommendations to leaders and practitioners, recommendations for future research, and conclusion of the study are also presented in Chapter 5.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Recommendations

The purpose of this qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceived as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Three sources of data were utilized to support the case study and to assist with ensuring the purpose of the study was achieved. Thirty participants who are employed or were previously employed in the engineering industry, and who hold or held leadership positions in the northeast region of the U.S. were recruited to participate in semistructured interviews. A stratified sample of two subgroups of 15 males and 15 females was used as 2 sources of interview data. Archival records in the form of CVs from each participant were used to supplement interview data. CV documents served to provide insight into how participants presented themselves professionally and showed examples of personal knowledge and accomplishments. Chapter 5 includes the research questions, a descriptive discussion of the findings, limitations identified during the study, recommendations to leaders and practitioners, and recommendations for future research. The summary for Chapter 5 will conclude the dissertation research study.

Research Questions

Two research questions were created for this qualitative exploratory case study to align with the purpose of the study and to guide the research.

RQ1: What do female engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

RQ2: What do male engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions?

Discussion of Findings

Inequality exists in the STEM industry. The problem is when compared to their male counterparts, fewer women in the engineering field hold leadership roles in the STEM industry resulting in workplace inequity (Lewis, 2018). Women are underrepresented in the STEM fields. Research results revealed barriers prevent women's career advancement to leadership positions (Botella et al., 2019; McGee, 2018; O'Reilly & Garret, 2017; Van Oosten et al., 2017). A qualitative exploratory case study was selected to explore the perceptions of females and males in the STEM industry to understand what leaders and former leaders perceived as obstacles to the advancement of females to STEM leadership positions. Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory and Lord et al.'s (1984) implicit leadership theory (ILT) were two theories used to provide a framework for exploring participants' perceptions in this qualitative exploratory case study. Open-ended, conversational, semistructured interviews were conducted to learn real events and experiences pertaining to the obstacles to women's trajectory to leadership positions in STEM. Six themes emerged: *a) barriers and experiences with men in leadership; (b) leadership competencies and experiences; (c) early interests and encouragement; (d) support opportunities and hindrances in women's careers; (e) woman leadership characteristics and development process; and (f) personal and other factors in success.* The themes emerged from the recounted experiences and perceptions of 15 male and 15 female leaders and former leaders in the STEM industry. CVs

provided by each participant were used for triangulation in this research. The discussion of findings is detailed in themes below.

Theme 1: Barriers and Experiences with Men in Leadership

Women leaders' abilities were underestimated and questioned by male counterparts in leadership. Women experienced unconscious biases, racism, scarcity of mentors or advocates, and were excluded from male-dominated professions (Madsen & Andrade, 2018; Simona & George, 2018). Findings of the study indicated lack of professional development opportunities, and unconscious gender biases were obstacles for women. Female leaders were subject to gender prejudices and were perceived as fragile in roles requiring physical labor. The results of Coleman's (2020) study similarly revealed women were reassigned from positions associated with masculinity to positions considered more feminine, such as human resources. Significant gender disparity with images of men dominating leadership makes it more likely women will experience biases and low leadership self-efficacy, leading to low performance expectations (Yates & Skinner, 2021). Individuals who do not fit the ideal leadership prototype experienced biased perceptions and judgements. Women's perceived gender was indicative of the implied perceptions of leadership identity and characteristics (Tabassum & Nayak, 2021).

Theme 2: Leadership Competencies and Experiences

Participants in this study successfully pursued STEM careers, yet most females faced obstacles pertaining to perceived qualified leadership competencies and experience. An appropriate mix of competencies is helpful for avoiding possible conflicts in diverse teams (Martinez et al., 2017). Female participants attempted to become leaders by

demonstrating confidence in their personal abilities; however, the capabilities of women in this study were questioned, resulting in women's self-doubt and low self-efficacy. Individuals' perceptions and cognitive structures are used to for leadership selections, rather than individuals' innate qualities, traits, and actions (Sims & Weinberg, 2022). Implicit biases were contributory to women's difficulty to advance to leadership positions (Braddy, 2020; Yates & Skinner, 2021). Implied competencies and perceived expectations were deterrent to women's career progress.

Levels of self-efficacy negatively or positively influence behaviors. Women's confidence significantly influences attainments (Macklem, 2020). Some women questioned personal abilities while men believed in personal abilities even when not best suited for roles. Males overestimated their capabilities (Herbst, 2020). Women in the engineering industry worked harder to establish and maintain confidence because of a masculinist culture that questioned their credibility and leadership competencies. Negative experiences encountered by women in the engineering industry is contributory to women's levels of self-confidence and career decisions (Yates & Skinner, 2021).

Theme 3: Early Interests and Encouragement

The STEM industry is male-dominated, and lack of advocacy and early engineering awareness were cited as major obstacles preventing women from entering STEM leadership positions. Makarem and Wang (2020) said STEM professions were initially unwelcoming to females, which provided obstacles for females to join and maintain existence in the male-dominated industry. Perceived gender differences diminished after participants were educated that STEM was gender equal, indicating the importance of gender bias in STEM gender discrepancies (Moss-Racusin et al., 2018).

Women continued their education into elite STEM graduate programs showing abilities and personalities to achieve in STEM (McCabe et al., 2020).

Early awareness and education in STEM for girls from all ethnicities was an effort that encouraged the empowerment of more female representations in STEM careers. Women leaders in this study who were introduced, educated, or influenced in a STEM field as children pursued STEM career choices. Many women created career plans and developed strategies for understanding the required steps for reaching career levels (Flippin, 2017). Early STEM awareness and education create opportunities for females to enter STEM fields, and open doors for organizational change for advocating diversity and inclusion in leadership. Early STEM awareness and education for young females is contributory to their career choices, benefits organizational success, and supports global competitiveness. More women in STEM careers benefit organizations and support global competitiveness in the U.S. (Alfred et al., 2019).

Theme 4: Support Opportunities and Hindrances in Women's Career

Male leaders viewed cultural and societal conventions as impediments to women's careers. Women experienced cultural biases from organizational culture and masculinist culture while advancing to leadership positions (Coleman, 2020; Nash & Moore, 2019). Cultural biases limit female advancement to STEM leadership positions (Carrasco et al., 2015; Yates & Skinner, 2021). Male leaders expressed support for women and acted as mentors for women in STEM and believed in leaders taking initiatives to promote diversity. An organization that fosters an environment in which leaders acknowledge the difficulties faced by women during professional development is

better geared to assess and support individuals' career progressions (Yates & Skinner, 2021).

Women in this study believed more support from leadership and implemented organizational policies is required to successfully mitigate hindrances in pathways to career achievements. Chyu et al. (2021) believed that adopting an inclusive leadership culture increases diversity and gender equality opportunities in leadership. Culture affects everything in organizations to include promotions, policies, and decision making. Fostering a supportive environment with success opportunities in organizations that embrace diversity may change peoples' minds, set acceptable norms, and form favorable habits that can help women in leadership roles (Coe et al., 2019). An inclusive organizational culture creates equal opportunities and integrates the total value of talent to addresses systemic prejudices. Systemic organizational and industry changes influence change as standard expectations (Burke, 2018).

Theme 5: Woman Leadership Characteristics and Development Process

The male participants in this study took risks, sought opportunities, and readily switched jobs to attain positions that matched personal assessed success levels. Klein (2020) supported the study results that leaders benefit from reassessing skills and traits. Men made career changes if they felt unjust or unsatisfied with their current career situations. Males' responsiveness depicts leadership flexibility. Situations shape leaders' behaviors and effectiveness (Dipboye, 2018). Male leaders enhanced their careers and established networks outside the workplace, demonstrating their determination to set ambitious goals for themselves. According to Bandura (1986), people with high self-efficacy established high goals and worked hard to achieve them, thus helping them

overcome hurdles to goal attainment. Most male participants cited years of experience, skills, and competencies as reasons for career success and for deserving of attained leadership positions in STEM. High levels of self-efficacy boosts individuals' confidence and skills and can potentially influence career aspirations (Baker et al., 2016; Eibl et al., 2020; van Aalderen-Smeets et al., 2019). Individual leadership characteristics and personal development processes positively influence career opportunities and can potentially assist women in efforts to attain leadership positions.

Theme 6: Personal and Other Factors in Success

Participants suggested different paths to career advancement, including leadership training, asking job-related questions, investing in employees, mentorship, and advocates who create opportunities. Flippin (2017) believed mentorship forms leadership abilities and self-efficacy. The male participants ascribed personal factors to success as positive characteristics such as hard work, taking advantage of opportunities, and social networking. The current research findings emphasize the importance of building and developing personal resources outside of the organization. Networking and building relationships outside of the workplace are recommended actions for women to succeed in STEM. Women could enrich personal development abilities and create opportunities by building professional, networking, and mentorship relationships. However, males dominate various levels of leadership and significantly participate in STEM-related professional organizations. Women have unequal access to networking and mentorship opportunities and automatically are disadvantaged; since opportunities are afforded to those who are in the right network (Yates & Skinner, 2021).

Comparison of Males' and Females' Resultant Themes

A stratified sample of 15 males and 15 females were utilized and 2 separate research questions directed to each gender. Separate and distinct themes emerged for each subset. Regarding the challenges and obstacles women leaders face in STEM professions, men and women leaders had similar perspectives. Male and female participants acknowledged being a woman is a challenge in women's leadership careers and women encounter difficulties because of cultural and societal norms, stereotypes, biases, a lack of diversity, male dominance, lack of representation in leadership, and underestimation of abilities in comparison to men.

Women encountered more obstacles and hurdles in advancing to leadership positions. The findings of this study supported previous research suggesting women face implicit and explicit forms of biases in the workplace (Hutchinson, 2020). A comparison of male and female leaders' self-accounts of struggles revealed women lacked resources such as a mentor, networks outside the work environment, work-life balances, and sufficient training for professional development. However, males did not encounter similar challenges. Women's engagement in STEM is hampered by overt and subtle sexism and prejudice (Coleman, 2020; McCullough, 2011; Yates & Skinner, 2021).

Most women were formally mentored by men, whereas men received more casual and formal mentoring, providing them with an advantage. A previous study by Coleman (2020) highlighted the paucity of mentoring, particularly from senior female leaders who subsequently serve as role models. Men created social resources more easily through networking in a male-dominated environment, where women are restricted for accessing and forming social relationships. Women found it incredibly difficult to access all

essential associations in STEM sectors (Coleman, 2020). When men's and women's participation in professional organizations was compared, women encountered problems developing networks outside the workplace through professional organizations. Men reported more significant engagement with professional organizations and formed relationships that possibly influenced career advancements and leadership developmental skills. Men emphasized the importance for women leaders to join and actively participate in professional organizations.

Personal attributes and high leadership self-efficacy were contributory to men's career success in attaining leadership positions in the STEM fields. Women's inclination to doubt leadership abilities and lower self-efficacy negates professional advancement to leadership (Tabassum & Nayak, 2021). Women worked harder to gain leadership positions, ascribing achievement to a supportive atmosphere or opportunity. Individuals' preexisting assumptions about leaders and women contribute to negative judgments (Tabassum & Nayak, 2021). Negative judgments of women's abilities to lead impacts women's leadership perceptions and self-efficacy (Seo et al., 2017; Tabassum & Nayak, 2021).

Limitations

The initial number of interested male participants and the time it took for conducting interviews and analyzing data were limitations. STEM is a male-dominated industry with significant numbers of males in leadership positions (Han et al., 2018; Hickey & Cui, 2020). Purposeful sampling was used to deliberately target STEM leaders to share valuable knowledge specific to the case (Babbie, 2010; Johnson et al., 2020). However, fewer males compared to females expressed interests in participating in the

research. Male participants were not forthcoming. The semistructured interview process for females was completed in three weeks; for males, the process lasted six weeks, with three males rescheduling multiple times and one male who did not meet at the agreed meeting time. The time constraints limited planned data analysis schedules and contributed to time management implications.

Recommendations to Leaders and Practitioners

Lessons learned from the research participants' shared experiences support organizational learning and effective change in STEM. Organizational learning is an essential ingredient in organizational development and successful leadership decision making. There is a direct correlation between organizational learning and organizational innovation strategies (Iqbal et al. 2021). Knowledge provides leadership with tools to improve decision making and better adapt to internal and external changes in STEM organizations.

Early STEM Awareness and Educational Opportunities

Early STEM awareness and exposure support females' interest and may enhance their decisions to pursue careers in the industry (Blotnick et al., 2018). Therefore, it is recommended for leadership to create intentional STEM awareness and educational programs to attract younger females to become interested in STEM. Women at various career levels from all available ethnicities in the engineering industry can be facilitators at STEM awareness and outreach initiatives. More young females may become attracted to a career in the STEM field when they envision themselves as future organizational and world leaders. Similarly, an increase in female interests in STEM academia may promote higher female college enrollments resulting in additional females joining the workplace.

Another recommendation is for industry leaders to recruit interns from diverse backgrounds and genders and provide practical meaningful work experiences. Team composition with members who have visible and nonvisible differences is good. There are multiple disciplines in STEM, and it is recommended leadership share all possible career opportunities that exist in the STEM industry.

Enhanced Mentorship Programs

The findings of this study highlighted the importance of mentorship for women in STEM organizations, specifically those who aspire to attain leadership positions.

Mentoring is a pathway for women to advance in the workplace (Li et al., 2018; Welsh & Diehn, 2018). Female and male participants in this study indicated mentors were critical to facilitating career progress. One recommendation is to establish all-encompassing purposeful mentorship programs easily accessible by all employees from the new hire acclimation period. In addition, women particularly benefit from similar gendered perspectives when paired with women mentors (Block & Tietjen-Smith, 2016).

Workplace advocacy and sponsorship are additional recommendations beyond mentorship, where mentees are protégés. Women in the workplace who are perceived as proteges benefit from mentors' support and advocacy (Welsh & Diehn, 2018). Leaders are accountable for establishing, monitoring, and measuring goals to ensure program effectiveness.

Organizational Development

It is recommended diversity be a core ingredient in the organization's employment policy where diversity and inclusion are embedded and supported by executive management in the organization. Creating a culture of inclusion and diversity

in the workplace significantly opens the pathway for new and existing employees to respectfully collaborate and strengthen interpersonal professional relationships (Coe et al., 2019). Merely recommending females get involved in professional organizations is insufficient for emphasizing its importance to career progression. Senior leadership could support women's professional organization involvement by providing financial support and time for networking events. Another recommendation involves employee training and development programs that create a clear pathway for aspiring and current leaders. Organizations that support diversity contribute to changing the way people think, developing acceptable standards, and forming positive behaviors that support larger numbers of women being accepted into leadership positions.

Recommendations for Future Research

An understanding of the current imbalance in leadership positions among the genders and identifying the varying perspectives between men and women in STEM contribute to the exploratory process and its findings. New knowledge explaining the reasons for the disparity in female leadership are findings from the study. Interviewing male leaders in a male-dominated industry was important for obtaining diverse perspectives on the research topic. A recommendation for future research is to replicate the current qualitative exploratory case study from a larger subset and with nationwide participation across a wide group to result in more meaningful workplace data about obstacles to women's advancement to STEM leadership positions. A second recommendation is to employ a quantitative study that utilizes questionnaires, allowing for high numbers of participants, respondents anonymity, and flexibility of participants' locations. Further studies are needed to establish the generalizability of this study's

results to include all gender identities in STEM professionals. Males and females were the subject groups for this study, which limited participation of many others who choose other gender identities. A third recommendation for researchers would be to utilize qualitative explanatory case studies to explore and understand the influences of professional and networking engagement in comparison to mentorship and sponsorship initiatives, and to assess the value of networking compared to professional involvement in preparing women to assume leadership roles.

Chapter Summary

The design of the qualitative exploratory case study was utilized to explore the perceptions of male and female engineering industry leaders related to obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Chapter 5 was used to summarize conclusions and recommendations of the research study. Conclusions were summarized based on the thematic elements that emerged from the data analysis of 30 semistructured interviews and CVs provided by male and female leaders in the engineering industry. Two research questions were created for the exploratory case study to align with the purpose of the study and to guide the research. The purpose of this qualitative exploratory case study was to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to leadership positions in the science technology, engineering, and mathematics fields. Three themes emerged from two unique research questions directed to each gender. The first research question asked what female engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Theme 1: Barriers and experiences with men in leadership, Theme 2: Leadership competencies and

experiences, and Theme 3: Early interests and encouragement emerged from RQ1. The second research question asked what male engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Theme 4: Support opportunities and hindrances in women's career; Theme 5: Woman leadership characteristics and development process; and Theme 6: Personal and other factors in success were the emergent themes from RQ2.

The study results were considered when providing recommendations to leader and practitioners related to early STEM awareness and educational opportunities, enhanced mentorship programs, and organizational development. There is a need for practitioners to develop employment policy with diversity and inclusion embedded in corporate cultures. The study contributed added perspectives to the related research topic, and recommended future research exploration using similar and different research methodologies. Future research may uncover additional information from employing a larger sample size from wider geographical locations with participants from all gender identities.

Female underrepresentation in STEM leadership positions is a problem, yet the industry continues to rapidly evolve. The results from this study can help practitioners understand the types of obstacles female employees are experiencing and enable appropriate actions to increase leadership diversity in the STEM field. The results and findings serve industry and academic leaders to develop an understanding of associated behaviors required to address and potentially eliminate the barriers that limit advancement of women's careers. Plenteous opportunities exist for change as it relates to women in the STEM industry (Diekman et al., 2019).

References

- Agassi, J. (2008). *Science and history: A reassessment of the historiography of science* (Vol. 253). Springer.
- Al Khajeh, E. H. (2018). Impact of leadership styles on organizational performance. *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 2018, 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.5171/2018.687849>
- Alfred, M. V., Ray, S. M., & Johnson, M. A. (2019). Advancing women of color in STEM: An imperative for U.S. global competitiveness. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 21(1), 114–132. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1523422318814551>
- Alharahsheh, H. H., & Pius, A. (2020). A review of key paradigms: Positivism VS interpretivism. *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 39–43.
- Amankwaa, L. (2016). Creating protocols for trustworthiness in qualitative research. *Journal of Cultural Diversity*, 23(3), 121–127.
<https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-5366-3.ch008>
- American Association of University Women. (2019). *The STEM gap: Women and girls in science, technology, engineering and mathematics*.
<https://www.aauw.org/resources/research/the-stem-gap/>
- Aponte, M., Balfour, F., Garin, T., Glassgow, D., Lee, T., Thomas, E., & Williams, K. (2017). *Women Veterans Report: Past, present, and future of women veterans*. Office of Data Governance and Analytics. https://www.va.gov/vetdata/docs/specialreports/women_veterans_2015_final.pdf

- Arifin, S. R. M. (2018). Ethical considerations in qualitative study. *International Journal of Care Scholars*, 1(2), 30–33. <https://doi.org/10.31436/ijcs.v1i2.82>
- Arikan, C. L. (2020). An overview on leadership styles for organizations. *Romanian Economic and Business Review*, 15(3), 45.
- Asiamah, N., Mensah, H. K., & Oteng-Abayie, E. (2017). General, target, and accessible population: Demystifying the concepts for effective sampling. *The Qualitative Report*, 22(6), 1607–1621. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2017.2674>
- Asrar-ul-Haq, M., & Anwar, S. (2018). The many faces of leadership: Proposing research agenda through a review of literature. *Future Business Journal*, 4(2), 179–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2018.06.002>
- Association for Women in Science. (2017). *Biotech boom: A bust for women*. <https://www.awis.org/biotech-boom-a-bust-for-women/>
- Association for Women in Science. (2019). *Transforming STEM leadership culture*. 2019 Association for Women in Science Report. <https://www.awis.org/leadership-report/>
- Atasoy, R. (2020). The relationship between school principals' leadership styles, school culture and organizational change. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 16(5), 256–274. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2020.277.16>
- Avison, D., Lau, F., Myers, M., & Nielsen, P. A. (1999). Action research. *Communications of the ACM*, 42(1), 94–97. <https://doi.org/10.1145/291469.291479>
- Babbie, E. R. (2010). *The practice of social research* (12th ed.). Cengage Learning.

- Baker, D. F., Larson, L. M., & Surapaneni, S. (2016). Leadership intentions of young women. *Journal of Career Assessment, 24*(4), 718–731.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1069072715616124>
- Baker, M., Ali, M., & French, E. (2019). The impact of women's representation on performance in project-based and non-project-based organizations. *International Journal of Project Management, 37*(7), 872–883.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2019.06.001>
- Bandura, A. (1986). The explanatory and predictive scope of self-efficacy theory. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology, 4*(3), 359–373.
<https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.1986.4.3.359>
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. Henry Holt & Co.
- Bargau, M. A. (2015). Leadership versus management. *Romanian Economic and Business Review, 10*(2), 181–188. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529714395.n351>
- Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and performance beyond expectations*. Free Press.
- Bass, B. M. (1997). Does the transactional–transformational leadership paradigm transcend organizational and national boundaries? *American Psychologist, 52*(2), 130–139. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.52.2.130>
- Beede, D. N., Julian, T. A., Langdon, D., McKittrick, G., Khan, B., & Doms, M. E. (2011a). STEM: Good jobs now and for the future. *U.S. Department of Commerce, Economics and Statistics Administration Issue Brief, (3–11)*.
https://www.commerce.gov/sites/default/files/migrated/reports/stemfinaljuly14_1.pdf

- Beede, D. N., Julian, T. A., Langdon, D., McKittrick, G., Khan, B., & Doms, M. E. (2011b). Women in STEM: A gender gap to innovation. *U.S. Department of Commerce, Economics and Statistics Administration Issue Brief*, (04–11).
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228196398_Women_in_STEM_A_gender_gap_to_innovation
- Benmira, S., & Agboola, M. (2021). Evolution of leadership theory. *BMJ Leader*, 5(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1136/leader-2020-000296>
- Bennis, W., & Nanus, B. (1985). *The strategies for taking charge*. Harper & Row.
- Bess, C. (2019). Unpacking the STEM Disciplines. *Science & Children*, 56(6), 52.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/26901408>
- Betz, N. E., & Hackett, G. (1997). Applications of self-efficacy theory to the career assessment of women. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 5(4), 383–402.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/106907279700500402>
- Betz, N. E., & Hackett, G. (2006). Career self-efficacy theory: Back to the future. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 14(1), 3–11.
<https://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1069072705281347>
- Bierema, L. L. (2016). Women’s leadership: Troubling notions of the ideal (male) leader. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 18(2), 119–136.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1523422316641398>
- Birt, L., Campbell, C. Cavers, D., Scott, S., & Walter, F. (2016). Member checking: A tool to enhance trustworthiness or merely a nod to validation? *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13), 1802–1811. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732316654870>

- Blaikie, N. (2018). Confounding issues related to determining sample size in qualitative research. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 21(5), 635–641.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2018.1454644>
- Blanchard, K. H., Zigarmi, D., & Nelson, R. B. (1993). Situational leadership after 25 years: A retrospective. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 1(1), 21–36.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/107179199300100104>
- Bligh, M. C., Kohles, J. C., & Yan, Q. (2018). Leading and learning to change: The role of leadership style and mindset in error learning and organizational change. *Journal of Change Management*, 18(2), 116–141.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14697017.2018.1446693>
- Block, B. A., & Tietjen-Smith, T. (2016). The case for women mentoring women. *Quest*, 68(3), 306–315. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2016.1190285>
- Bloodhart, B., Balgopal, M. M., Casper, A. M. A., Sample McMeeking, L. B., & Fischer, E. V. (2020). Outperforming yet undervalued: Undergraduate women in STEM. *PloS One*, 15(6), e0234685. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234685>
- Bloomfield, J., & Fischer, M. J. (2019). Quantitative research design. *Journal of the Australian Rehabilitation Nurses Association*, 22(2), 27–30.
<https://doi.org/10.33235/jarna.22.2.27-30>
- Blotnicky, K. A., Franz-Odendaal, T., French, F., & Joy, P. (2018). A study of the correlation between STEM career knowledge, mathematics self-efficacy, career interests, and career activities on the likelihood of pursuing a STEM career among middle school students. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 5(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-018-0118-3>

- Bordalo, P., Coffman, K., Gennaioli, N., & Shleifer, A. (2019). Beliefs about gender. *American Economic Review*, *109*(3), 739–773.
<https://doi.org/http://www.aeaweb.org/aer/>
- Boris, E., & Honey, M. (1988). Gender, race, and the policies of the Labor Department. *Monthly Labor Review*, *111*(2), 26.
- Botella, C., Rueda, S., López-Iñesta, E., & Marzal, P. (2019). Gender diversity in STEM disciplines: A multiple factor problem. *Entropy*, *21*(1), 30.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/e21010030>
- Bracht, E. M., Keng-Highberger, F. T., Avolio, B. J., & Huang, Y. (2021). Take a selfie: Examining how leaders emerge from leader self-awareness, self-leadership, and self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *11*, N.PAG.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.635085>
- Braddy, P. W., Sturm, R. E., Atwater, L., Taylor, S. N., & McKee, R. A. (2020). Gender bias still plagues the workplace: Looking at derailment risk and performance with self–other ratings. *Group & Organization Management*, *45*(3), 315–350.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601119867780>
- Brands, R., Fernandez-Mateo, I., & Brewis, K. (2017). How to stop women leaning out. *London Business School Review*, *2*, 32–33.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/2057-1615.12172>
- Brooks, J., Reed, D. M., & Savage, B. (2016). Taking off with a pilot: The importance of testing research instruments [Paper presentation]. *15th European Conference on Research Methodology for Business and Management Studies*. Kingston University London, Kingston, United Kingdom.

- Brown, J. (2019). Introduction: From unaware to advocate. *How to be an inclusive leader: Your role in creating cultures of belonging where everyone can thrive*, (pp 1–15). Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Burnette, J. L., Pollack, J. M., & Hoyt, C. L. (2010). Individual differences in implicit theories of leadership ability and self-efficacy: Predicting responses to stereotype threat. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 3(4), 46–56.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jls.20138>
- Burton, C. M., Mayhall, C., Cross, J., & Patterson, P. (2019). Critical elements for multigenerational teams: A systematic review. *Team Performance Management: An International Journal*, 25(7/8), 369–401.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/TPM-12-2018-0075>
- Busari, A. H., Khan, S. N., Abdullah, S. M., & Mughal, H. (2019). Transformational leadership style, followership, and factors of employees' reactions towards organizational change. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 14(2), 181–209.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-03-2018-0083>
- Buse, K., Bilimoria, D., & Perelli, S. (2013). Why they stay: Women persisting in US engineering careers. *Career Development International*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/cdi-11-2012-0108>
- Cacioppe, R. (1998). An integrated model and approach for the design of effective leadership development programs. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 19(1), 44–53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437739810368820>
- Caffrey, C. (2020). *Conceptual framework*. Salem Press Encyclopedia.

- Calabrese, R. L. (2006). *The elements of an effective dissertation and thesis: A step-by-step guide to getting it right the first time*. Rowman & Littlefield Publishing Group.
- Campbell, S. (2015). Conducting case study research. *Clinical Laboratory Science*, 28(3), 201–205. <https://doi.org/10.29074/ascls.28.3.201>
- Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D., & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: Complex or simple? Research case examples. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(8), 652–661. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>
- Campuzano, M. V. (2019). Force and inertia: A systematic review of women’s leadership in male-dominated organizational cultures in the United States. *Human Resource Development Review*, 18(4), 437–469. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484319861169>
- Carlana, M. (2019). Implicit stereotypes: Evidence from teachers’ gender bias. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 134(3), 1163–1224. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjz008>
- Carrasco, A., Francoeur, C., Labelle, R., Laffarga, J., & Ruiz-Barbadillo, E. (2015). Appointing women to boards: Is there a cultural bias? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 129(2), 429–444. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2166-z>
- Catalyst. (2020, August 4). *Quick take: Women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM)*. <https://www.catalyst.org/research/women-in-science-technology-engineering-and-mathematics-stem/>

- Cawthon, D. L. (1996). Leadership: The great man theory revisited. *Business Horizons*, 39(3), 1–4. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-6813\(96\)90001-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-6813(96)90001-4)
- Cech, E., Rubineau, B., Silbey, S., & Seron, C. (2011). Professional role confidence and gendered persistence in engineering. *American Sociological Review*, 76(5), 641–666. <https://doi.org/10.2307/23019214>
- Charmaz, K. (2006). An invitation to grounded theory. *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*, pp. 1–12). Sage.
- Chin, J. L. (2010). Introduction to the special issue on diversity and leadership. *American Psychologist*, 65(3), 150–156. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0018716>
- Chin, J. L. (2011). Women and leadership: Transforming visions and current contexts. *Forum on public policy online* (Vol. 2011, No. 2). Oxford Round Table.
- Chin, J. L., & Trimble, J. E. (2014). *Diversity and leadership*. Sage.
- Chisholm-Burns, M. A., Spivey, C. A., Hagemann, T., & Josephson, M. A. (2017). Women in leadership and the bewildering glass ceiling. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*, 74(5), 312–324. <https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp160930>
- Chu, D. C., & Abdulla, M. M. (2014). Self-efficacy beliefs and preferred gender role in policing: An examination of policewomen’s perceptions in Dubai, the United Arab Emirates. *The British Journal of Criminology*, 54(3), 449–468. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azu010>
- Chyu, J., Peters, C. E., Nicholson, T. M., Dai, J. C., Taylor, J., Garg, T., ... & Psutka, S. P. (2021). Women in leadership in urology: The case for increasing diversity and equity. *Urology*, 150, 16–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.urology.2020.07.079>

- Clark, C. M., & Harrison, C. (2018). Leadership: the complexities and state of the field. *European Business Review*, 30(5), 514–528.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-07-2017-0139>
- Coe, I. R., Wiley, R., & Bekker, L. G. (2019). Organisational best practices towards gender equality in science and medicine. *The Lancet*, 393(10171), 587–593.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)33188-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)33188-X)
- Cole, L. L. (2019). Countering gender disparity: Creating anti-predictions using data science. *ISSA Journal*, 17(3), 21–25.
- Coleman, M. (2020). Women leaders in the workplace: Perceptions of career barriers, facilitators, and change. *Irish Educational Studies*, 39(2), 233–253.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2019.1697952>
- Cook, B. G., & Cook, L. (2016). Research designs and special education research: Different designs address different questions. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 31(4), 190–198. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ldrp.12110>
- Crawford, D. E., Patel, M., Chomilo, N. T., Krug, L., Glusman, M., & Kaplan-Sanoff, M. (2019). Let up: A systematic approach to responding to cultural bias in health care. *Zero to Three*, 40(2), 10–17.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Curtis, S. (2017). Black women’s intersectional complexities: The impact on leadership. *Management in Education*, 31(2), 94–102.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0892020617696635>

- Dambe, M., & Moorad, F. (2008). From power to empowerment: A paradigm shift in leadership. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 22(3), 575–587.
<https://doi.org/10.4314/sajhe.v22i3.25803>
- Daniel, B. K. (2019a). Student experience of the maximum variation framework for determining sample size in qualitative research. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Research Methods for Business & Management Studies*, 92–100.
<https://doi.org/10.34190/RM.19.075>
- Daniel, B. K. (2019b). Using the TACT framework to learn the principles of rigour in qualitative research. *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 17(3), 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.34190/JBRM.17.3.002>
- Dasgupta, N., & Stout, J. G. (2014). Girls and women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics: STEMing the tide and broadening participation in STEM careers. *Policy Insights from the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 1(1), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732214549471>
- Davies, C., & Fisher, M. (2018). Understanding research paradigms. *Journal of the Australasian Rehabilitation Nurses' Association*, 21(3), 21–25.
- Davis, M., C. (2017, September 2). Why STEM for women of color is important to us all! *Huffington Press*. https://www.huffpost.com/entry/why-stem-for-women-of-col_b_11815008
- De la Croix, A., Barrett, A., & Stenfors, T. (2018). How to...do research interviews in different ways. *The Clinical Teacher*, 15(6), 451–456.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/tct.12953>

- Dean, M., & Perrett, R. (2020). Overcoming barriers to women's workplace leadership: Insights from the interaction of formal and informal support mechanisms in trade unions. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 51(3), 169–184.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/irj.12287>
- DePaulo, P. (2000). Sample size for qualitative research: The risk of missing something important. *Quirk's Marketing Research Review*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732315617444>
- Development Dimensions International (2022). *Global Leadership Forecast 2014|2015*.
<https://www.ddiworld.com/research/global-leadership-forecast-2015>
- Diehl, A. B., & Dzubinski, L. M. (2016). Making the invisible visible: A cross-sector analysis of gender-based leadership barriers. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 27(2), 181–206. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.21248>
- Diekman, A. B., Clark, E. K., & Belanger, A. L. (2019). Finding common ground: Synthesizing divergent theoretical views to promote women's STEM pursuits. *Social Issues and Policy Review*, 13(1), 182–210.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/sipr.12052>
- Dipboye, R. L. (2018). Leader emergence and effectiveness in organizations. *The emerald review of industrial and organizational psychology* (pp. 441–493). Emerald Group Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78743-785-220181012>
- Dobrovolny, J. L., & Fuentes, S. C. G. (2008). Quantitative versus qualitative evaluation: A tool to decide which to use. *Performance Improvement*, 47(4), 7–14.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/pfi.197>

- Dodd, F. (2012). Women leaders in the creative industries: A baseline study. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 4(2), 153–178.
- Doepke, M., Hazan, M., & Maoz, Y. D. (2015). The baby boom and World War II: A macroeconomic analysis. *Review of Economic Studies*, 82(3), 1031–1073. <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdv010>
- Dugan, J. P., Fath, K. Q., Howes, S. D., Lavelle, K. R., & Polanin, J. R. (2013). Developing the leadership capacity and leader efficacy of college women in science, technology, engineering, and math fields. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 7(3), 6–23. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jls.21292>
- Dziak, M. (2019). *Great man theory*. Salem Press.
- Eagly, A. H., & Carli, L. L. (2007). *Through the labyrinth: The truth about how women become leaders*. Harvard Business Press.
- Eagly, A. H., & Chin, J. L. (2010). Diversity and leadership in a changing world. *American Psychologist*, 65(3), 216–224. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0018957>
- Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2002). Motivational beliefs, values, and goals. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53(1), 109–132. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.53.100901.135153>
- Efron, S. E., & Ravid, R. (2018). *Writing the literature review: A practical guide*. The Guilford Press.
- Eibl, B., Lang, F. R., & Niessen, C. (2020). Employee voice at work: The role of employees' gender, self-efficacy beliefs, and leadership. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 29(4), 570–585. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2020.1733979>

- Epperson, M., Gouveia, C. J., Tabangin, M. E., Takiar, V., Howell, R., Altaye, M., ... & Tang, A. L. (2020). Female representation in otolaryngology leadership roles. *The Laryngoscope*, 130(7), 1664–1669. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lary.28308>
- Erkutlu, H. (2008). The impact of transformational leadership on organizational and leadership effectiveness. *Journal of Management Development*, 27(7), 708–726. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02621710810883616>
- Farrelly, P. (2012). Selecting a research method and designing the study. *British Journal of School Nursing*, 7(10), 508–511. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjsn.2012.7.10.508>
- Fatourou, P., Papageorgiou, Y., & Petousi, V. (2019). Women are needed in STEM: European policies and incentives. *Communications of the ACM*, 62(4), 52–52. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3312565>
- Fernando, D., Cohen, L., & Duberley, J. (2018). What helps? Women engineers' accounts of staying on. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 28(3), 479. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12192>
- Fine, C., Monzon, V. S. & Lawford-Smith, H. (2020). Why does workplace gender diversity matter? Justice, organizational benefits, and policy. *Social Issues and Policy Review*, 14 (1), 36–72. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sipr.12064>
- Flippin, C. S. (2017). The glass ceiling is breaking, now what? *Generations*, 41(3), 34–42. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26556298>
- Flory, J. A., Leibbrandt, A., Rott, C., & Stoddard, O. (2021). Increasing workplace diversity: Evidence from a recruiting experiment at a Fortune 500 company. *Journal of Human Resources*, 56(1), 73. <https://doi.org/10.3368/jhr.56.1.0518-9489R1>

- Foti, R. J., Hansbrough, T. K., Epitropaki, O., & Coyle, P. T. (2017). Dynamic viewpoints on implicit leadership and followership theories: Approaches, findings, and future directions. *Leadership Quarterly*, 28(2), 261–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2017.02.004>
- Fowler, J. (2021). Team working part 3: Leading a team. *British Journal of Nursing*, 30(14), 872. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2021.30.14.872>
- Fox, C. W., Duffy, M. A., Fairbairn, D. J., & Meyer, J. A. (2019). Gender diversity of editorial boards and gender differences in the peer review process at six journals of ecology and evolution. *Ecology and Evolution*, 9(24), 13636–13649. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.5794>
- Fusch, P., Fusch, G. E., & Ness, L. R. (2018). Denzin’s paradigm shift: Revisiting triangulation in qualitative research. *Journal of Social Change*, 10(1), 19–32. <https://doi.org/10.5590/JOSC.2018.10.1.02>
- Gandolfi, F., & Stone, S. (2018). Leadership, leadership styles, and servant leadership. *Journal of Management Research*, 18(4), 261–269.
- GAO analysis of the U.S. Census Bureau’s American community survey data. Women in management: Women remain underrepresented in management positions and continue to earn less than male managers. GAO-22-105796. Published: Mar 07, 2022. Publicly Released: Mar 15, 2022.
- Gaviria-Rivera, J. I., & López-Zapata, E. (2019). Transformational leadership, organizational climate, and job satisfaction in work teams. *European Research Studies Journal*, 22(3), 68–82. <https://doi.org/10.35808/ersj/1457>

- Germain, M. L. (2012). Traits and skills theories as the nexus between leadership and expertise: Reality or fallacy? *Performance Improvement, 51*(5), 32–39.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/pfi.21265>
- Gerring, J. (2017). Qualitative methods. *Annual Review of Political Science, 20*, 15–36.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-092415-024158>
- Gierlich-Joas, M., Hess, T., & Neuburger, R. (2020). More self-organization, more control—or even both? Inverse transparency as a digital leadership concept. *Business Research, 13*(3), 921–947. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40685-020-00130-0>
- Gipson, A. N., Pfaff, D. L., Mendelsohn, D. B., Catenacci, L. T., & Burke, W. W. (2017). Women and leadership: Selection, development, leadership style, and performance. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science, 53*(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0021886316687247>
- Glass, C., & Cook, A. (2016). Leading at the top: Understanding women’s challenges above the glass ceiling. *The Leadership Quarterly, 27*(1), 51–63.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2015.09.003>
- Gnilka, P. B., & Novakovic, A. (2017). Gender differences in STEM students’ perfectionism, career search self-efficacy, and perception of career barriers. *Journal of Counseling & Development, 95*(1), 56–66.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jcad.12117>
- Gobaw, M. K. (2017). Women’s role and their styles of leadership. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies, 9*(3), 28–34.
<https://doi.org/10.5897/IJEAPS2015.0415>

- Goris, T. (2020). Where are they? Limited female presence in STEM professions. *The Midwest Quarterly*, 61(3), 330. <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A628285352/AONE?u=anon~d2253df7&sid=googleScholar&xid=38bc82cd>
- Goryunova, E., Scribner, R. T., & Madsen, S. R. (2017). The current status of women leaders worldwide. *Handbook of research on gender and leadership*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Gratton, L., Voigt, A., & Erickson, T. (2011). Bridging faultlines in diverse teams. *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, 39(1), 80–90. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMR.2011.5729976>
- Griffiths, O., Roberts, L., & Price, J. (2019). Desirable leadership attributes are preferentially associated with women: A quantitative study of gender and leadership roles in the Australian workforce. *Australian Journal of Management*, 44(1), 32–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0312896218781933>
- Grunspan, D. Z., Eddy, S. L., Brownell, S. E., Wiggins, B. L., Crowe, A. J., & Goodreau, S. M. (2016). Males under-estimate academic performance of their female peers in undergraduate biology classrooms. *PloS One*, 11(2), e0148405. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148405>
- Guest, G., Bunce, A., & Johnson, L. (2006). How many interviews are enough? An experiment with data saturation and variability. *Field methods*, 18(1), 59–82. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1525822X05279903>

- Guillén, L., Mayo, M., & Karelaiia, N. (2018). Appearing self-confident and getting credit for it: Why it may be easier for men than women to gain influence at work. *Human Resource Management*, 57(4), 839–854. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21857>
- Gunter, R. (2009). The emergence of gendered participation styles in science-related discussions: Implications for women's place in science. *Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering*, 15(1), 53–75. <https://doi.org/10.1615/JWomenMinorScienEng.v15.i1.40>
- Hadary, S. & Henderson, L. (2013). Success strategy two: Own your own destiny. *How women lead: 8 essential strategies successful women know*, (pp. 17–44). McGraw-Hill.
- Haile, S., Emmanuel, T., & Dzathor, A. (2016). Barriers and challenges confronting women for leadership and management positions: review and analysis. *International Journal of Business and Public Administration*, 13(1), 1–17.
- Hamilton, J. B. (2020). Rigor in qualitative methods: An evaluation of strategies among underrepresented rural communities. *Qualitative Health Research*, 30(2), 196–204. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732319860267>
- Han, H., Kim, Y., Kim, S., Cho, Y., & Chae, C. (2018). Looking into the labyrinth of gender inequality: Women physicians in academic medicine. *Medical Education*, 52(10), 1083. <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.13682>
- Hancock, D. R., & Algozzine, B. (2017). *Doing case study research: A practical guide for beginning researchers* (3rd ed.). Teachers College Press.

- Hart, J. (2016). Dissecting a gendered organization: Implications for career trajectories for mid-career faculty women in STEM. *Journal of Higher Education*, 87(5), 605–634. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jhe.2016.0024>
- Hartman, R. L., & Barber, E. G. (2020). Women in the workforce: The effect of gender on occupational self-efficacy, work engagement and career aspirations. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 35(1), 92–118. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GM-04-2019-0062>
- Hasler, M. G. (2005). *Leadership development and organizational culture: Which comes first?* (pp. 996–1003). Retrieved December 6, 2020 from https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&ved=0CAMQw7AJahcKEwiA4Ojm3-z5AhUAAAAAHQAAAAAQAg&url=https%3A%2F%2Ffiles.eric.ed.gov%2Ffulltext%2FED492357.pdf&psig=AOvVaw3UGiEZj7U1Qxet2IwXI_Kp&ust=1661886499269372
- Hayashi, Jr., P., Abib, G., & Hoppen, N. (2019). Validity in qualitative research: A processual approach. *The Qualitative Report*, 24(1), 98–112. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2019.3443>
- Helman, A., Bear, A., & Colwell, R. (2020). *Promising practices for addressing the underrepresentation of women in science, engineering, and medicine: opening doors*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25585>
- Herbst, T. H. H. (2020). Gender differences in self-perception accuracy: The confidence gap and women leaders' underrepresentation in academia. *South African Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 46, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajip.v46i0.1704>

- Hernandez, P. R., Schultz, P. W., Estrada, M., Woodcock, A., & Chance, R. C. (2013). Sustaining optimal motivation: A longitudinal analysis of interventions to broaden participation of underrepresented students in STEM. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 105*(1), 89. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029691>
- Hersey, P., Blanchard, K. H., & Natemeyer, W. E. (1979). Situational leadership, perception, and the impact of power. *Group & Organization Studies, 4*(4), 418–428. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105960117900400404>
- Hickey, P. J., & Cui, Q. (2020). Gender diversity in US construction industry leaders. *Journal of Management in Engineering, 36*(5). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ME.1943-5479.0000838](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000838)
- Hinds, D. (2002). Research instruments. *The researcher's toolkit* (pp. 57–58). Routledge.
- Holman, L., Stuart-Fox, D., & Hauser, C. E. (2018). The gender gap in science: How long until women are equally represented? *PLoS biology, 16*(4), e2004956. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2004956>
- Hoyt, C. L., Burnette, J. L., & Innella, A. N. (2012). I can do that: The impact of implicit theories on leadership role model effectiveness. *Personality & Social Psychology Bulletin, 38*(2), 257. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167211427922>
- Hurley, D., & Choudhary, A. (2016). Factors influencing attainment of CEO position for women. *Gender in Management: An International Journal, 31*(4), 250–265. <https://doi.org/10.1108/gm-01-2016-0004>
- Hutchison, K. (2020). Four types of gender bias affecting women surgeons and their cumulative impact. *Journal of Medical Ethics, 46*(4), 236–241. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2019-105552>

- Hyett, N., Kenny, A., & Dickson-Swift, V. (2014). Methodology or method? A critical review of qualitative case study reports. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health & Well-Being*, 9, 1. <https://doi.org/10.3402/qhw.v9.23606>
- Iqbal, A., Shah, M. A.-H., Ali, M. S., & Shahzadi, S. (2021). The indicators of organizational learning and their correlation with organizational innovation strategies. *Ilkogretim Online*, 20(2), 420–427. <https://doi.org/10.17051/ilkonline.2021.02.45>
- Izraeli, D. N., Adler, N. J., & Izraeli, D. N. (1994). *Competitive frontiers: Women managers in a global economy* (pp. 3–21). Cambridge.
- Janicijevic, N. (2013). The mutual impact of organizational culture and structure. *Economic Annals*, 58(198), 35–60. <https://doi.org/10.2298/EKA1398035J>
- Johnson, J. L., Adkins, D., & Chauvin, S. (2020). A review of the quality indicators of rigor in qualitative research. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 84(1), 7120. <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe7120>
- Jones, J., Williams, A., Whitaker, S., Yingling, S., Inkelas, K., & Gates, J. (2018). Call to action: Data, diversity, and STEM education. *Change*, 50(2), 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00091383.2018.1483176>
- Kahai, S., Fjermestad, J., Zhang, S., & Avolio, B. (2007). Leadership in virtual teams: Past, present, and future. *International Journal of E-Collaboration*, 3(1).
- Kalaitzi, S., Czabanowska, K., Azzopardi-Muscat, N., Cuschieri, L., Petelos, E., Papadakaki, M., & Babich, S. (2020). Women, healthcare leadership and societal culture: A qualitative study. *Journal of Healthcare Leadership*, 43. <https://doi.org/10.2147/JHL.S194733>

- Kalman, M. (2019). It requires interest, time, patience and struggle: Novice researchers' perspectives on and experiences of the qualitative research journey. *Qualitative Research in Education*, 8(3), 341. <https://doi.org/10.17583/qre.2019.4483>
- Kamalizeni, C., Hoque, M., Kader, A., & Mapudzi, H. (2018). Gender inclusive leadership: Exploring women under-representation in public enterprises: The case of Swaziland. *Journal of Public Administration*, 53(4), 849–872. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC-1723ffe270>
- Killawi, A., Khidir, A., Elnashar, M., Abdelrahim, H., Hammoud, M., Elliott, H., ... & Fetters, M. D. (2014). Procedures of recruiting, obtaining informed consent, and compensating research participants in Qatar: Findings from a qualitative investigation. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 15, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6939-15-9>
- Kivunja, C., & Kuyini, A. B. (2017). Understanding and Applying Research Paradigms in Educational Contexts. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v6n5p26>
- Klassen, R. M., & Chiu, M. M. (2010). Effects on teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction: Teacher gender, years of experience, and job stress. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 102(3), 741. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0019237>
- Klein, M. (2020). Leadership characteristics in the era of digital transformation. *Business and Management Studies: An International Journal*, 8(1), 883–902. <https://doi.org/10.15295/bmij.v8i1.1441>
- Koomans, M., & Hilders, C. (2016). Design-driven leadership for value innovation in healthcare. *Design Management Journal*, 11(1), 43–57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dmj.12031>

- Korn Ferry (2019, April 17). *Analysis of largest U.S. companies shows percentage of women in c-suite inches up from previous year*. https://www.kornferry.com/about-us/press/korn-ferry-analysis-of-largest-us-companies-shows-percentage-of-women-in-c-suite-roles-inches-up-from-previous-year?mod=article_inline
- Korstjens, I., & Moser, A. (2017). Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 2: Context, research questions and designs. *The European Journal of General Practice*, 23(1), 274–279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2017.1375090>
- Kossek, E. E., & Buzzanell, P. M. (2018). Women’s career equality and leadership in organizations: Creating an evidence-based positive change. *Human Resource Management*, 57(4), 813–822. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21936>
- Kozioł-Nadolna, K., & Beyer, K. (2021). Determinants of the decision-making process in organizations. *Procedia Computer Science*, 192, 2375–2384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.09.006>
- Kukenberger, M. R., & D’Innocenzo, L. (2020). The building blocks of shared leadership: The interactive effects of diversity types, team climate, and time. *Personnel Psychology*, 73(1), 125. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12318>
- Kunze, A., & Miller, A. R. (2017). Women helping women? Evidence from private sector data on workplace hierarchies. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 99(5), 769–775. <https://doi.org/http://www.mitpressjournals.org/loi/rest>
- Landivar, L. C. (2013). Disparities in STEM employment by sex, race, and Hispanic origin. *Education Review*, 29(6), 911–922. <https://www.census.gov/prod/2013pubs/acs-24.pdf>

- Law, M., Stewart, D., Letts, L., Pollock, N., Bosch, J., & Westmorland, M. (1998). *Guidelines for critical review of qualitative studies* (version 2.0). McMaster University Occupational Therapy Evidence-Based Practice Research Group, 1–9.
- Lee, J. Y. (2014). The plateau in U.S. women’s labor force participation: A cohort analysis. *Industrial Relations*, 53(1), 46–71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/irel.12046>
- Lee, K. (2014, May 19). *Announcing the White House science fair and celebrating girls excelling in STEM*. The White House. <https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/blog/2014/05/19/announcing-white-house-science-fair-and-celebrating-girls-excelling-stem>
- Leedy, P. D., & Ormrod, J. E. (2018). *Practical research: Planning and design* (12th ed.). Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Lemkau, J. P. (1979). Personality and background characteristics of women in male-dominated occupations: A review. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 4(2), 221–240. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-6402.1979.tb00710.x>
- Leung, S. A. (2008). The big five career theories. In *International handbook of career guidance* (pp. 115–132). Springer.
- Lewis, K. (2018). Gender-gaps, gender-based social norms, and conditioning from the vantage point of leadership theories. *International Forum of Teaching and Studies*, 14(1), 17–25).
- Li, J., de Souza, R., Esfandiari, S., & Feine, J. (2019). Have women broken the glass ceiling in North American dental leadership? *Advances in Dental Research*, 30(3), 78–84. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0022034519877397>

- Li, S., Malin, J. R., & Hackman, D. G. (2018). Mentoring supports and mentoring across difference: Insights from mentees. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 26(5), 563–584. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13611267.2018.1561020>
- Liao, H., & Hitchcock, J. (2018). Reported credibility techniques in higher education evaluation studies that use qualitative methods: A research synthesis. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 68, 157–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2018.03.005>
- Litmanovitz, M. (2010). Beyond the classroom: Women in education leadership. *Kennedy School Review*, 11, 25–28.
- Lord, R. G., Foti, R. J., & De Vader, C. L. (1984). A test of leadership categorization theory: Internal structure, information processing, and leadership perceptions. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 34(3), 343–378. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(84\)90043-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(84)90043-6)
- Lord, R. G., & Maher, K. J. (1991). *Leadership and information processing: Linking perceptions and performance*. Unwin Hyman.
- Loy, J. (2019). Women and technology: Disrupting leadership in engineering education. In *Challenges and Opportunities for Women in Higher Education Leadership* (pp. 252–267). IGI Global.
- Maatta, S., & Dahlborg Lyckhage, E. (2011). The influence of gender in academia: A case study of a university college in Sweden. *Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion: An International Journal*, 30(5), 379–393. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02610151111150636>

- MacDonald, H., Sulsky, L., & Brown, D. (2008). Leadership and perceiver cognition: Examining the role of self-identity in implicit leadership theories. *Human Performance, 21*(4), 333–353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08959280802347031>
- Machida, M., & Feltz, D. L. (2013). Studying career advancement of women coaches: The roles of leader self-efficacy. *International Journal of Coaching Science, 7*(2), 53–71.
- Macklem, G.L. (2020). Self-efficacy and goal setting. *Brief SEL Interventions at School*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65695-9_10
- Madsen, S. R., & Andrade, M. S. (2018). Unconscious gender bias: Implications for women’s leadership development. *Journal of Leadership Studies, 12*(1), 62. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jls.21566>
- Main, J. B., Wang, Y., & Tan, L. (2022). Preparing industry leaders: The role of doctoral education and early career management training in the leadership trajectories of women STEM PhDs. *Research in Higher Education, 63*(3), 400–424. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-021-09655-7>
- Makarem, Y., & Wang, J. (2020). Career experiences of women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics fields: A systematic literature review. *Human Resource Development Quarterly, 31*(1), 91–111. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.21380>
- Malos, R. (2012). The most important leadership theories. *Annals of Eftimie Murgu University Resita, Fascicle II, Economic Studies, 413–420*.

- Malterud, K., Siersma, V. D., & Guassora, A. D. (2016). Sample size in qualitative interview studies: Guided by information power. *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13), 1753–1760. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732315617444>
- Martin, J. (2015). Transformational and transactional leadership: An exploration of gender, experience, and institution type. *Portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 15(2), 331–351. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2015.0015>
- Martinez, A., & Christnacht, C. (2021). *Women making gains in STEM occupations but still underrepresented*. United States Census Bureau. <https://www.census.gov/library/stories/2021/01/women-making-gains-in-stem-occupations-but-still-underrepresented.html>
- Martinez, M. G., Zouaghi, F., & Garcia Marco, T. (2017, March 1). Diversity is strategy: The effect of R&D team diversity on innovative performance. *R & D Management*, 47(2). <https://doi.org/10.1111/radm.12244>
- Maxwell, J. (2018). Collecting qualitative data: A realist approach. *The sage handbook of qualitative data collection* (pp. 19–31). Sage.
- Mayer, I. (2015). Qualitative research with a focus on qualitative data analysis. *International Journal of Sales, Retailing & Marketing*, 4(9), 53–67.
- McCabe, K. O., Lubinski, D., & Benbow, C. P. (2020). Who shines most among the brightest? A 25-year longitudinal study of elite STEM graduate students. *Journal of Personality & Social Psychology*, 119(2), 390–416. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000239>
- McCausland, T. (2021). Why innovation needs more diversity. *Research Technology Management*, 64(2), 59–63. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08956308.2021.1868003>

- McCullough, L. (2011). Women's leadership in science, technology, engineering and mathematics: Barriers to participation. In *Forum on Public Policy Online*, 2011(2).
- McCullough, L. (2020). Proportions of women in STEM leadership in the academy in the USA. *Education Sciences*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10010001>
- McGee, K. (2018). The influence of gender, and race/ethnicity on advancement in information technology (IT). *Information and Organization*, 28(1), 1–36.
- Merriam, S. B. (1998). Case studies as qualitative research. *Qualitative research and case study applications in education: Revised and expanded from case study research in education*, (pp. 26–43). Jossey-Bass.
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2015). Six common qualitative research designs. *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*, (pp. 22–42). John Wiley & Sons.
- Mewton, L., Ware, J., & Grantham, C. (2005). A question of leadership: Which skills and competencies will be most critical for leaders as the workplace continues to evolve? *Leadership in Action*, 24(6), 14–15. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lia.1093>
- Mikkelsen, M. F. (2020). The complex project complexity: Identification of five ideal research types. *Journal of Modern Project Management*, 7(4), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.19255/JMPM02201>
- Mills, M. J., Culbertson, S. S., Huffman, A. H., & Connell, A. R. (2012). Assessing gender biases: Development and initial validation of the gender role stereotypes scale. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 27(8), 520–540. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17542411211279715>

- Minehart, R. D., Foldy, E. G., Long, J. A., & Weller, J. M. (2020). Challenging gender stereotypes and advancing inclusive leadership in the operating theatre. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, *124*(3), e148–e154.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bja.2019.12.015>
- Moak, T. N., Cress, P. E., Tenenbaum, M., & Casas, L. A. (2020). The leaky pipeline of women in plastic surgery: Embracing diversity to close the gender disparity gap. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal*, *40*(11), 1241–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1093/asj/sjz299>
- Morse, J. M. (2000). Determining sample size. *Qualitative Health Research*, *10*(1), 3–5.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/104973200129118183>
- Moser, A., & Korstjens, I. (2018). Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 3: Sampling, data collection and analysis. *The European Journal of General Practice*, *24*(1), 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2017.1375091>
- Moss-Racusin, C. A., Sanzari, C., Caluori, N., & Rabasco, H. (2018). Gender bias produces gender gaps in STEM engagement. *Sex Roles*, *79*(11), 651–670.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-018-0902-z>
- Mouton, N. (2019). A literary perspective on the limits of leadership: Tolstoy’s critique of the great man theory. *Leadership*, *15*(1), 81–102.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1742715017738823>
- Moylan, C. A., & Wood, L. (2016). Sexual harassment in social work field placements. *Affilia Journal of Women and Social Work*, *31*(4), 405.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0886109916644643>

- Nash, M., Davies, A., & Moore, R. (2017). What style of leadership do women in STEM fields perform? Findings from an international survey. *PLoS One*, *12*(10), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0185727>
- Nash, M., & Moore, R. (2019). I was completely oblivious to gender: An exploration of how women in STEM navigate leadership in a neoliberal, post-feminist context. *Journal of Gender Studies*, *28*(4), 449–461. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09589236.2018.1504758>
- Nassaji, H. (2020). Good qualitative research. *Language Teaching Research*, *24*(4), 427–431. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168820941288>
- National Center for Educational Statistics. (2019). *Digest of education statistics: 2019 tables and figures*. Digest of Education Statistics. https://nces.ed.gov/programs/digest/d19/tables/dt19_318.45.asp?current=yes
- Navarro-Astor, E., Román-Onsalo, M., & Infante-Perea, M. (2017). Women’s career development in the construction industry across 15 years: Main barriers. *Journal of Engineering, Design & Technology*, *15*(2), 199–221. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jedt-07-2016-0046>
- Neuman, W. L. (2011). What are the major types of social research? *Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches* (5th ed.), (pp. 25–54). Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Newkumet, M. B. (1993). Vietnam women's memorial dedicated with love and honor. *Minerva's Bulletin Board*, *6*(4), 3.

- Noland, M., Moran, T., & Kotschwar, B. R. (2016). *Is gender diversity profitable? Evidence from a global survey* [No. 16–3]. Peterson Institute for International Economics. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2729348>
- Northouse, P. G. (2018). *Leadership: Theory and practice interactive ebook* (8th ed.). University of Phoenix.
- Nosek, B. A., Smyth, F. L., Sriram, N., Lindner, N. M., Devos, T., Ayala, A., & Greenwald, A. G. (2009). National differences in gender–science stereotypes predict national sex differences in science and math achievement. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *106*(26), 10593–10597. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0809921106>
- O’Reilly, A., & Garrett, P. M. (2017). Playing the game? The sexual harassment of female social workers across professional workspaces. *International Social Work*, *62*(1), 105–118. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872817706410>
- Olofsdotter, G., & Rasmusson, M. (2016). Gender (in)equality contested: Externalizing employment in the construction industry. *New Technology, Work & Employment*, *31*(1), 41–57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ntwe.12057>
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Leech, N. L. (2005). On becoming a pragmatic researcher: The importance of combining quantitative and qualitative research methodologies. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, *8*(5), 375–387. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570500402447>
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Leech, N. L. (2007). A call for qualitative power analyses. *Quality and Quantity*, *41*(1), 105. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-005-1098-1>

- Patino, C. M., & Ferreira, J. C. (2018). Inclusion and exclusion criteria in research studies: Definitions and why they matter. *Jornal Brasileiro de Pneumologia*, 44, 84–84. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1806-375620180000000088>
- Perdue, A. (2017). Man up or go home: Exploring perceptions of women in leadership. *Marquette Law Review*, 100(4), 1233–1308.
- Peterson, J. (2020, October 5). *Legislative update: Update on federal funding and the Rural STEM Education Act*. National Science Teaching Association. <https://www.nsta.org/blog/update-federal-funding-and-rural-stem-education-act>
- Pidgeon, K. (2017). The keys for success: Leadership core competencies. *Journal of Trauma Nursing*, 24(6), 338–341. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JTN.0000000000000322>
- Place, K. R., & Vardeman-Winter, J. (2018). Where are the women? An examination of research on women and leadership in public relations. *Public Relations Review*, 44(1), 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2017.10.005>
- PR Newswire. (1990, November 12). *Study finds more top corporate women than men show leadership traits*. <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A9589341/ITOF?u=uphoenix&sid=bookmark-ITOF&xid=0763965f>
- Pretorius, S., Steyn, H., & Bond-Barnard, T. J. (2018). Leadership styles in projects: Current trends and future opportunities. *South African Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 29(3), 161–172. <https://doi.org/10.7166/29-3-2057>
- Purvanova, R. K., & Bono, J. E. (2009). Transformational leadership in context: Face-to-face and virtual teams. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 20(3), 343–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2009.03.004>

- Rajput, N., Bhatia, S. P., & Malhotra, B. (2019). Generational diversity: An exploratory study on managing multigenerational workforce, a sustainable solution. *Global Journal of Enterprise Information System*, 11(3), 37–43.
<https://doi.org/10.18311/gjeis/2019>
- Randsley de Moura, G., Leicht, C., Leite, A. C., Crisp, R. J., & Gocłowska, M. A. (2018). Leadership diversity: Effects of counter stereotypical thinking on the support for women leaders under uncertainty. *Journal of Social Issues*, 74(1), 165–183.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12262>
- Rashid, Y., Rashid, A., Akib Warraich, M., Sabir, S., & Waseem, A. (2019). Case study method: A step-by-step guide for business researchers. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406919862424>
- Reinking, A., & Martin, B. (2018). The gender gap in STEM fields: Theories, movements, and ideas to engage girls in STEM. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research*, 7(2), 148. <https://doi.org/10.7821/naer.2018.7.271>
- Repacholi, B. M., Meltzoff, A. N., Toub, T. S., & Ruba, A. L. (2016). Infants' generalizations about other people's emotions: Foundations for trait-like attributions. *Developmental Psychology*, 52(3), 364.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000097>
- Ridder, H.-G. (2017). The theory contribution of case study research designs. *Business Research*, 10(2), 281–305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40685-017-0045-z>
- Rindfuss, R. R., Brewster, K. L., & Kavee, A. L. (1996). Women, work, and children: Behavioral and attitudinal change in the United States. *Population and Development Review*, 22(3), 457–482. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2137716>

- Roberts, R. E. (2020). Qualitative interview questions: Guidance for novice researchers. *Qualitative Report*, 25(9), 3185–3203.
<https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2020.4640>
- Rodriguez, S., Cunningham, K., & Jordan, A. (2019). STEM identity development for Latinas: The role of self and outside recognition. *Journal of Hispanic Higher Education*, 18(3), 254–272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1538192717739958>
- Rooddehghan, Z., ParsaYekta, Z., & Nasrabadi, A. N. 1. (2019). Equity in nursing care: A grounded theory study. *Nursing Ethics*, 26(2), 598–610.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733017712079>
- Rose, E. K. (2018). The rise and fall of female labor force participation during World War II in the United States. *The Journal of Economic History*, 78(3).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022050718000323>
- Rosenbach, W. E. (2018). *Contemporary issues in leadership*. Routledge.
- Ruggieri, S. (2009). Leadership in virtual teams: A comparison of transformational and transactional leaders. *Social Behavior & Personality: An International Journal*, 37(8). <https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2009.37.8.1017>
- Ruiz-Jiménez, J. M., & Fuentes-Fuentes, M. del M. (2016). Management capabilities, innovation, and gender diversity in the top management team: An empirical analysis in technology-based SMEs. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 19(2), 107–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brq.2015.08.003>
- Ruzgar, N. (2018). The effects of decision-making styles of leadership on employees knowledge sharing within the organization. *Journal of Knowledge Economy & Knowledge Management*, 13(2), 107–120.

- Rykers, K. (2016). The impact of diversity, bias, and stereotype: Expanding the medical physics and engineering STEM workforce. *Australasian Physical & Engineering Sciences in Medicine*, 39(3), 593–600. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13246-016-0473-7>
- Saint-Michel, S. E. (2018). Leader gender stereotypes and transformational leadership: Does leader sex make the difference? *Management*, 21(3), 944–966. <https://doi.org/10.3917/mana.213.0944>
- Salas-Lopez, D., Deitrick, L. M., Mahady, E. T., Gertner, E. J., & Sabino, J. N. (2011). Women leaders: Challenges, successes, and other insights from the top. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 5(2), 34–42. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jls.20216>
- Saldana, J., & Omasta, M. (2018). Analyzing interviews: Condensing and coding. *Qualitative research: Analyzing life* (pp. 89–116). Sage.
- Santos, K. da S., Ribeiro, M. C., Queiroga, D. E. U. de, Silva, I. A. P. da, & Ferreira, S. M. S. (2020). The use of multiple triangulations as a validation strategy in a qualitative study. *Ciencia & Saude Coletiva*, 25(2), 655–664. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232020252.12302018>
- Sassler, S., Glass, J., Levitte, Y., & Michelmore, K. M. (2017). The missing women in STEM? Assessing gender differentials in the factors associated with transition to first jobs. *Social Science Research*, 63, 192–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2016.09.014>
- Schein, E. H. (2009). Organizational culture. *American Psychologist*, 45(2), 109–119. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.45.2.109>
- Schein, E. H., & Schein, P. (1991). *Organizational culture and leadership: A dynamic view*. John Wiley & Sons.

- Schell, W. J., & Hughes, B. E. (2017, June). *Approach to understand the role of identity in engineering leadership. 2017 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition.*
<https://doi.org/10.18260/1-2-27550>
- Schmitt, M., Lauer, S., & Wilkesmann, U. (2021). Work motivation and career autonomy as predictors of women's subjective career success in STEM. *Acta Paedagogica Vilnensia*, 46, 73–89. <https://doi.org/10.15388/ActPaed.2021.46.5>
- Schwanke, D. A. (2013). Barriers for women to positions of power: How societal and corporate structures, perceptions of leadership and discrimination restrict women's advancement to authority. *Earth Common Journal*, 3(2).
<https://doi.org/10.31542/j.ecj.125>
- Schyns, B. (2006). The role of implicit leadership theories in the performance appraisals and promotion recommendations of leaders. *Equal Opportunities International*, 25(3), 188–199. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02610150610687836>
- Schyns, B., Kiefer, T., Kerschreiter, R., & Tymon, A. (2011). Teaching implicit leadership theories to develop leaders and leadership: How and why it can make a difference. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 10(3), 397–408.
<https://doi.org/10.5465/amle.2010.0015>
- Seo, G., Huang, W., & Han, S. H. C. (2017). Conceptual review of underrepresentation of women in senior leadership positions from a perspective of gendered social status in the workplace. *Human Resource Development Review*, 16(1), 35–59.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484317690063>

- Sergiovanni, T. J., & Corbally, J. E. (Eds.). (1986). *Leadership and organizational culture: New perspectives on administrative theory and practice*. University of Illinois Press.
- Seyranian, V., Madva, A., Duong, N., Abramzon, N., Tibbetts, Y., & Harackiewicz, J. M. (2018). The longitudinal effects of STEM identity and gender on flourishing and achievement in college physics. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-018-0137-0>
- Shafique, I., & Beh, L. S. (2017). Shifting organizational leadership perspectives: An overview of leadership theories. *International Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 11(4), 134–143.
- Shah, S. R., & Al-Bargi, A. (2013). Research paradigms: Researchers' worldviews, theoretical frameworks and study designs. *Arab World English Journal*, 4(4), 252–264.
- Shatnawi, D., & Fishback, P. (2018). The impact of World War II on the demand for female workers in manufacturing. *Journal of Economic History*, 78(2), 539–74. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022050718000232>
- Shein, E. (2018). Broadening the path for women in STEM: Organizations work to address a notable absence of women in the field. *Communications of the ACM*, 61(8), 19–21. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3231170>
- Sherbin, L. (2015, June 2011). Female scientists feel the bias in their labs. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/roomfordebate/2015/06/11/nobel-winning-sexism-in-the-lab/female-scientists-feel-the-bias-in-their-labs>

- Shinbrot, X. A., Wilkins, K., Gretzel, U., & Bowser, G. (2019). Unlocking women's sustainability leadership potential: Perceptions of contributions and challenges for women in sustainable development. *World Development*, *119*, 120–132.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2019.03.009>
- Shirey, M. R. (2020). Self-efficacy and the nurse leader. *Nurse Leader*, *18*(4), 339–343.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mnl.2020.05.001>
- Silverthorne, C. (2000). Situational leadership theory in Taiwan: A different culture perspective. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, *21*(2), 68–74.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730010318156>
- Sim, J., Saunders, B., Waterfield, J., & Kingstone, T. (2018). Can sample size in qualitative research be determined a priori? *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, *21*(5), 619–634.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2018.1454643>
- Sims, R., & Weinberg, F. J. (2022). More than follow the leader: Expectations, behaviors, stability, and change in a co-created leadership process. *Group & Organization Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10596011221093456>
- Simona, S. A., & George, T. S. (2018). Women in business leadership. *Ovidius University Annals: Economic Sciences Series*, *XVIII*(1), 388–393.
<https://doaj.org/article/ef898b54793f4aa4ae2700ecf6eb8c59>
- Slavik, J., Putnova, A., & Cebakova, A. (2015). Leadership as a tool of strategic management. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, *26*, 1159–1163.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00946-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00946-6)

- Smeding, A. (2012). Women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM): An investigation of their implicit gender stereotypes and stereotypes' connectedness to math performance. *Sex Roles: A Journal of Research*, 67(11–12), 617–629. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-012-0209-4>
- Smyth, J. D., Swendener, A., & Kazyak, E. (2018). Women's work? The relationship between farmwork and gender self-perception. *Rural Sociology*, 83(3), 654–676. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ruso.12207>
- Spector, B. A. (2016). Carlyle, Freud, and the great man theory more fully considered. *Leadership*, 12(2), 250–260. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1742715015571392>
- Stoker, J. I., Van der Velde, M., & Lammers, J. (2012). Factors relating to managerial stereotypes: The role of gender of the employee and the manager and management gender ratio. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 27(1), 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-011-9210-0>
- Stuke, K. B. (2013). Understanding leadership through leadership understandings. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 7(2), 55–61. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jls.21291>
- Su, R., & Rounds, J. (2015). All STEM fields are not created equal: People and things interests explain gender disparities across STEM fields. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6, 189. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00189>
- Super, J. F. (2020). Building innovative teams: Leadership strategies across the various stages of team development. *Business Horizons*, 63(4), 553–563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2020.04.001>

- Surmiak, A. (2018). Confidentiality in qualitative research involving vulnerable participants: Researchers' perspectives. *Research Ethics in Qualitative Research*, 19(3), 393–418. <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-19.3.3099>
- Swafford, M., & Anderson, R. (2020). Addressing the gender gap: Women's perceived barriers to pursuing STEM careers. *Journal of Research in Technical Careers*, 4(1), 61–74.
- Swanson, J., & Woitke, M. (1997). Theory into practice in career assessment for women: Assessment and interventions regarding perceived career barriers. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 5(4), 443–462. <https://doi.org/10.1177/106907279700500405>
- Swanson, S., Billsberry, J., Kent, A., Skinner, J., & Mueller, J. (2020). Leader prototypicality in sport: The implicit leadership theories of women and men entering sport management careers. *Sport Management Review*, 23(4), 640–656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smr.2019.08.002>
- Tabassi, A. A., & Bakar, A. H. A. (2010). Towards assessing the leadership style and quality of transformational leadership. The case of construction firms of Iran. *Journal of Technology Management in China*, 5(3), 245–258. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17468771011086256>
- Tabassum, N., & Nayak, B. S. (2021). Gender stereotypes and their impact on women's career progressions from a managerial perspective. *IIM Kozhikode Society & Management Review*, 10(2), 192–208. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2277975220975513>
- Tavakol, M. & Sandars, J. (2014). Quantitative and qualitative methods in medical education research: AMEE Guide No 90: Part II. *Medical Teacher*, 36(10), 838–848. <https://doi.org/10.3109/0142159X.2014.915297>

- Tavares, G. M., Sobral, F., Goldszmidt, R., & Araújo, F. 2018. Opening the implicit leadership theories' black box: An experimental approach with conjoint analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 100. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00100>
- Taylor, S. N., Sturm, R. E., Atwater, L. E., & Braddy, P. W. (2016). Underestimating one's leadership impact: Are women leaders more susceptible? *Organizational Dynamics*, 45(2), 132–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2016.02.007>
- Teague, L. J. (2015). Higher education plays critical role in society: More women leaders can make a difference. In *Forum on Public Policy Online*, 2015 (2).
- Theofanidis, D., & Fountouki, A. (2018). Limitations and delimitations in the research process. *Perioperative Nursing*, 7(3), 155–163. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552022>
- Thomas, G. (2013). *How to do your research project: A guide for students in education and applied social sciences* (2nd ed.). Sage.
- Thornton, G. (2020). *Woman in business 2020: Putting the blueprint into action*. <https://www.grantthornton.global/globalassets/1-member-firms/global/insights/women-in-business/2020/women-in-business-2020-report.pdf>
- Thurairajah, K. (2019). Uncloaking the researcher: Boundaries in qualitative research. *Qualitative Sociology Review*, 15(1), 132–147. <https://doi.org/10.18778/1733-8077.15.1.06>
- Tufford, L., & Newman, P. (2012). Bracketing in qualitative research. *Qualitative Social Work*, 11(1), 80–96. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1473325010368316>

- Turban, S., Wu, D., & Zhang, L. (2019, February 11). *Research: When gender diversity makes firms more productive*. Harvard Business Review. <https://hbr.org/2019/02/research-when-gender-diversity-makes-firms-more-productive>
- Turner, J. R., & Baker, R. (2018). A review of leadership theories: identifying a lack of growth in the HRD leadership domain. *European Journal of Training & Development*, 42(7/8), 470–498. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-06-2018-0054>
- U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2016, December 9). *Women in the labor force: A data book* (No. 1059). BLS Reports. <https://www.bls.gov/opub/reports/womens-databook/archive/women-in-the-labor-force-a-databook-2015.pdf>
- U.S. Department of Labor (n.d.). Women's Bureau. *History: An overview 1920-2021*. <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/wb/about/history>
- U.S. Department of Labor (2019). *Women in the labor force*. <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/wb/data/facts-over-time/women-in-the-labor-force#womenstem>
- van Aalderen-Smeets, S. I., Walma van der Molen, J. H., & Xenidou-Dervou, I. (2019). Implicit STEM ability beliefs predict secondary school students' STEM self-efficacy beliefs and their intention to opt for a STEM field career. *Journal of research in science teaching*, 56(4), 465–485. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21506>
- Van Esch, C., Hopkins, M. M., O'Neil, D. A., & Bilimoria, D. (2018). How perceived riskiness influences the selection of women and men as senior leaders. *Human Resource Management*, 57(4), 915–930. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21902>

- Van Oosten, E. B., Buse, K., & Bilimoria, D. (2017). The leadership lab for women: Advancing and retaining women in STEM through professional development. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 2138. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.02138>
- Van Wart, M. (2013). Lessons from leadership theory and the contemporary challenges of leaders. *Public Administration Review*, 73(4), 553–565. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12069>
- Vasileiou, K., Barnett, J., Thorpe, S., & Young, T. (2018). Characterising and justifying sample size sufficiency in interview-based studies: Systematic analysis of qualitative health research over a 15-year period. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 18(1), 148. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-018-0594-7>
- Video Age Productions. (2014, January 01). *What leaders need to know, in leadership skills and values series*. [Video/DVD]. <https://www.proquest.com/audio-video-works/what-leaders-need-know-leadership-skills-values/docview/1822824194/se-2>
- Voosen, P. (2016, March 11). The subtle ways gender gaps persist in science. *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, 62(26), A12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2019.00060>
- Wa-Mbaleka, S. (2019, October). The researcher as an instrument. *World Conference on Qualitative Research* 1086, 33–41. Springer.
- Wajngurt, C., & Sloan, P. J. (2019). Overcoming gender bias in STEM: The effect of adding the Arts (STEAM). *InSight: A Journal of Scholarly Teaching*, 14, 13–28. <https://doi.org/10.46504/14201901wa>

- Walker, R. C., & Aritz, J. (2015). Women doing leadership: Leadership styles and organizational culture. *International Journal of Business Communication*, 52(4), 452–478. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2329488415598429>
- Walls, E. (2019). The value of situational leadership. *Community Practitioner*, 92(2), 31–33.
- Webb, J. G. (2010). The evolution of women's roles within the university and the workplace. *Forum on Public Policy Online*, 2010 (2).
- Weinstein, A. L. (2017). Working women in the city and urban wage growth in the United States. *Journal of Regional Science*, 57(4), 591–610. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jors.12336>
- Welsh, E. T., & Diehn, E. W. (2018). Mentoring and gender: Perception is not reality. *Career Development International*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cdi-11-2017-0198>
- White, H. H. (2019). The equal rights amendment in the twenty-first century: Ratification issues and intersectional effects. *Documents to the People*, 47(4), 34–38. <https://doi.org/10.5860/dttp.v47i4.7216>
- White, R. F. (2011). Toward an integrated theory of leadership. *Politics & the Life Sciences*, 30(1), 116–121. https://doi.org/10.2990/30_1_116
- Witherspoon, P. D., & Wohlert, K. L. (1996). An approach to developing communication strategies for enhancing organizational diversity. *Journal of Business Communication*, 33(4), 375–399. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002194369603300402>
- Wren, J. T. (1995). *The leader's companion: Insights on leadership through the ages*. Free Press.

- Wyrwicka, M. K., & Chuda, A. (2019). The diagnosis of organizational culture as a change's factor in the context application of design thinking. *LogForum*, 15(2), 279–290. <https://doi.org/10.17270/J.LOG.2019.319>
- Xu, Y. (2015). Focusing on women in STEM: A longitudinal examination of gender-based earning gap of college graduates. *Journal of Higher Education*, 86(4), 489–523. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jhe.2015.0020>
- Yates, J., & Skinner, S. (2021). How do female engineers conceptualise career advancement in engineering? A template analysis. *Career Development International*, 26(5), 697–719. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-01-2021-0016>
- Yates, L. (2019). How courage shapes your leadership footprint. *2019 International Leadership Association 21st Annual Global Conference*, Ottawa, Canada. <https://ilaglobalnetwork.org/events/21st-global-conference-ottawa-2019/>
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods* (6th ed.). Sage.
- Yukl, G. (2013). *Leadership in organizations* (8th ed.). Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Zarubin, A., Koval, A., Filippov, A., & Moshkin, V. (2017). Application of syntagmatic patterns to evaluate answers to open-ended questions. *Conference on Creativity in Intelligent Technologies and Data Science* (pp. 150–162). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-65551-2_11

Appendix A

The Status of Women in Stem Leadership Positions:
a Qualitative Exploratory Case Study

Tamara B. Smith

Soliciting Participants

A University of Phoenix Doctoral Candidate Is
Conducting a Research Study on:

**THE STATUS OF WOMEN IN
STEM LEADERSHIP POSITIONS**

Women are underrepresented in the STEM career fields and even more importantly at the leadership levels. The purpose of the case study is to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions.

You May Qualify for This Study:

Are you a leader and former leader located in the U.S Northeast Region?
Do you or did you work in the Engineering field?

A current copy of your curriculum vitae will be requested.

Your participation will involve an individual audio taped interview consisting of a series of research questions. Semi-structured interviews will last approximately 60 minutes with each participant and will be conducted after 5pm Mondays to Fridays and during the participant's available hours on the weekend days.

If you are interested to share your experiences, please email your contact information to tammytee93@email.phoenix.edu. All participant's information will be kept confidential and anonymous.

Appendix B

Research Participant Recruitment Request Email

Good day,

I am a doctoral scholar at the University of Phoenix, School of Advanced Studies. I am pursuing the Doctor of Management degree in Organizational Leadership. I will be conducting an independent study on THE STATUS OF WOMEN IN STEM LEADERSHIP POSITIONS: AN EXPLORATORY CASE STUDY. The purpose of the qualitative exploratory case study is to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions.

I am requesting permission to recruit participants who meet the following criteria: leaders and former leaders, males, or females, located in the U.S Northeast Region. A current curriculum vitae will be requested, and it may be provided at the time of the interview or submitted via email. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants will be maintained. The names of the participants or the place of employment will be omitted in the dissertation document. The organization's name and contact details on the attached permission request form will be blanked out on the signed copy. Participants will be informed that this is an independent study, and that the organization is not affiliated with the study or its findings. I will use semi-structured interviews conducted after 5pm Mondays to Friday and during the participant's available hours on the weekend days. Interviews will be held online or via the telephone depending on each participant's availability and meeting preference. The organization's premises will not be used to conduct interviews neither will interviews be held during work hours.

Please review, sign, and return the attached participant Informed Consent form.

Please let me know if you have any questions or comments.

Thank you for your support. I greatly appreciate it.

Regards,

Tamara Smith

Appendix C

Informed Consent: Participants 18 Years of Age and Older

Greetings,

My name is Tamara Smith, and I am a student at the University of Phoenix working on a doctoral degree in Organizational Leadership. I am conducting a research study entitled *The Status of Women in STEM Leadership Positions: A Qualitative Exploratory Case Study*.

The purpose of the research study is to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions.

Your participation will involve an individual audio taped interview consisting of a series of research questions regarding the experience and perceptions of obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions. Semi-structured interviews lasting approximately 60 minutes with each participant to be conducted after 5pm Mondays to Fridays and during the participant's available hours on the weekend days. Interviews will be held online or via telephone depending on the participants availability and meeting preference. Your participation in the research may involve a follow-up interview if necessary, for clarification purposes.

The confidentiality of the participants and participant's organization will be maintained. The names of the participants or organization will not be mentioned or named in the dissertation document. A voice recorder will be used during the interview. Participants' names will not be used during the interview. Once participation is agreed upon, each participant will be assigned an alias which will be used for the entirety of the project. Tamara B. Smith (researcher) will be the only person to have direct knowledge of each person's identity. All documents and research will strictly utilize the participant alias.

You can decide to be a part of this study or not. Once you start, you can withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The results of the research study may be published but your identity will remain confidential, and your name will not be made known to any outside parties.

In this research, there are no foreseeable risks to you research and no likely circumstances by which participants should be uncomfortable.

Although there may be no direct benefit to you, a possible benefit from your being part of this study is to share the results from this study that may help practitioners understand the types of obstacles female employees are experiencing which may potentially increase leadership diversity in the field. Diversifying leadership in the workplace create an environment where new associations are formed and could potentially increase efficiency and equality in workplaces.

If you have any questions about the research study, please call me at 8606559270 or email me at tammytee93@email.phoemix.edu. For questions about your rights as a study participant, or any concerns or complaints, please contact the University of Phoenix Institutional Review Board at IRB@phoenix.edu.

As a participant in this study, you should understand the following:

1. You may decide not to be part of this study, or you may want to withdraw from the study at any time. If you want to withdraw, please call me at (860)655-9270 or email me at tammytee93@email.phoenix.edu.
2. Your identity will be kept confidential.
3. Tamara Smith, the researcher, has fully explained the nature of the research study and has answered all your questions and concerns.
4. Before interviews are conducted, you must give permission for the researcher, Tamara Smith, to audio record the interview session. The information from the audio recorded interviews will be transcribed by Tamara Smith, and the data will be coded to assure that your identity is protected.
5. Your interview will be audio recorded. For your interview to be recorded you must provide verbal permission to the researcher. You understand that the information from the interview sessions will be transcribed and the data coded to protect your identity.
6. A current curriculum vitae is requested, and it can be provided at the time of the interview session or via email
7. Data will be kept secure in a locked container in the researcher's residence. Electronic files will be kept on a password protected digital device. All hard copy data will be shredded, and audio recordings will be erased from the digital device as soon as data is transcribed, and member checked.
8. The results of the study may be published.
9. There is no direct benefit to participation, participants will not be paid, and participation is strictly voluntary.
10. Neither participants nor participants' place of employment are subjects or case under study.

By signing this form, you agree that you understand the nature of the study, the possible risks, and benefits to you as a participant, and how your identity will be kept confidential. When you sign this form, this means that you are 18 years old or older and that you give your permission to volunteer as a participant in the study that is described here.

I accept the above terms. I do not accept the above terms. **(CHECK ONE)**

Signature of the research participant _____ Date _____

Signature of the researcher _____ Date _____

Appendix D

Initial Interview Protocol

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this research. My name is Tamara Smith. I am a doctoral candidate at the University of Phoenix's College of Doctoral Studies, in the Organizational Leadership program. I am the Principal Investigator, and I am conducting research for my doctoral dissertation. The research is entitled, The Status of Women in STEM Leadership Positions: A Qualitative Exploratory Case Study.

The purpose of the proposed qualitative exploratory case study is to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions.

As the Principal Investigator, I will be conducting a 60-minute interview with you. Before we begin, please note the following information:

- I received your signed Informed Consent document. Please confirm that this form was signed and provided by you.
- As a reminder, your participation in this research is voluntary and you may withdraw at any time.
- I encourage you to answer each question, but you are free to omit answering any of the interview questions.
- This interview must be in an environment that is considered a private space where there can be absolutely no interruptions.
- The interview will be recorded using an audio recorder. If you agree to be audio recorded, please answer yes for the record.

Thank you. Please let us begin.

RQ1 – Females only

1. How did you become interested in STEM? When did your STEM career begin?
2. Describe your experience as a leader working in the STEM industry.
3. What challenges, biases, or barriers (if any) did you encounter ascending to leadership role in STEM?
4. Describe a time when you believe gender played a negative role in a female obtaining a leadership role in STEM?
5. Describe a time when you believe gender played a negative role in a male obtaining a leadership role in STEM?
6. Do you think there is an ideal leadership prototype? Describe what leadership competencies are required for a STEM leadership role?
7. Is there anything else you would like to discuss or add regarding obstacles to career advancement in STEM?

RQ2 – Males only

1. Describe your promotion and tenure process in your current position?
2. Who do you feel contributed to your success achieving a leadership role?
3. What professional development opportunities have you had that contributed to your role?

4. What professional development opportunities or training do you feel will be beneficial for women who want to advance to leadership positions in STEM?
5. What do you think is contributing to the underrepresentation of women in STEM leadership positions?
6. Have you mentored women seeking leadership roles in STEM?
7. Do you think there is an ideal leadership prototype? If so, can you describe what leadership competencies are required for a STEM leadership role?
8. Is there anything else you would like to discuss or add regarding the facilitators of career progress?

The interview is concluded. The confidential data has identifiers; however, the data will be managed that privacy of research participants are protected. To maintain confidentiality, a coding process will be used to separate identifiers from data. The data that is collected today will be kept confidential per the signed Informed Consent document. Again, thank you for participating in this research study.

Appendix E

Interview Protocol

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this research. My name is Tamara Smith. I am a doctoral candidate at the University of Phoenix's College of Doctoral Studies, in the Organizational Leadership program. I am the Principal Investigator, and I am conducting a research for my doctoral dissertation. The research is entitled, The Status of Women in STEM Leadership Positions: A Qualitative Exploratory Case Study.

The purpose of the proposed qualitative exploratory case study is to understand what engineering industry leaders and former leaders perceive as obstacles to female career advancement to STEM leadership positions.

As the Principal Investigator, I will be conducting a 60-minute interview with you. Before we begin please note the following information:

- I received your signed Informed Consent document. Please confirm that this form was signed and provided by you.
- As a reminder, your participation in this research is voluntary and you may withdraw at any time.
- I encourage you to answer each question, but you are free to omit answering any of the interview questions.
- This interview must be in an environment that is considered a private space where there can be absolutely no interruptions.
- The interview will be recorded using an audio recorder. If you agree to be audio recorded, please answer yes for the record.

Thank you. Please let us begin.

RQ1 – Females only

1. How did you become interested in STEM? When did your STEM career begin?
2. Describe your experience as a leader working in the STEM industry.
3. Did you encounter challenges, biases, or barriers ascending to leadership role in STEM? If so, please describe them.
4. Did you have any mentors that contributed to your career trajectory to leadership?
5. Describe a time when you believe perceived gender played a negative role in a female obtaining a leadership role in STEM?
6. Describe a time when you believe perceived gender played a negative role in a male obtaining a leadership role in STEM?
7. What leadership competencies do you believe are required for a STEM leadership role?
8. Is there anything else you would like to discuss or add regarding obstacles to career advancement in STEM?

RQ2 – Males only

1. Describe your promotion and tenure process in your current position?
2. Who do you feel contributed to your success achieving a leadership role?

3. What professional development opportunities or involvement in professional organizations/committees have you had that contributed to your role?
4. What professional development opportunities, training, or involvement in professional organizations/committees do you feel will be beneficial for women who want to advance to leadership positions in STEM?
5. What do you think is contributing to the underrepresentation of women in STEM leadership positions?
6. Have you mentored women seeking leadership roles in STEM?
7. Do you think there is an ideal leadership prototype? If so, what leadership competencies do you think are required for a STEM leadership role?
8. Is there anything else you would like to discuss or add regarding the facilitators of career progress?

The interview is concluded. The confidential data has identifiers; however, the data will be managed that privacy of research participants are protected. To maintain confidentiality, a coding process will be used to separate identifiers from data. The data that is collected today will be kept confidential per the signed Informed Consent document. Again, thank you for participating in this research study.